

**Formalising the Informal: Challenges in Improving Waste
Electrical and Electronic Equipment Management in
Nigeria.**

A thesis presented in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

at the University of the West of Scotland

by

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Declaration

I certify hereby that the work written in this thesis titled “Formalising the informal: challenges in improving WEEE management in Nigeria” has never been submitted for a degree or has been submitted as part of degree requirements to another university or institution other than the University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, United Kingdom, February 2024. I certify that this thesis is an original work of research that has been written by me. Also, the assistance I received during my research work and the thesis write-up itself has been appropriately acknowledged. I also, declare that some parts of this thesis include some published papers:

- Okwu, O., Viza, E., Hursthouse, A., & Idoko, L. (2022). Menace of informal waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13762-022-04663-1/FIGURES/7>
- Okwu, O., Hursthouse, A., Viza, E., & Idoko, L. (2022). New Models to Reduce the Health Risks of Informal WEEE Recyclers in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Toxics*, 10(2), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/TOXICS10020084>
- Okwu, O., Hursthouse, A., Viza, E., & Idoko, L. (2021). Enhancement of WEEE Management Practices in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Recycling*, 6(4), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RECYCLING6040077>

This research presented was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences. University of the West of Scotland (reference number 21-8607-3338).

Signed.....

Date.....

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Abstract

Informal recyclers appear to be the key actors in the management of Waste electrical and electronic equipment in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Still, they lack the right skills and knowledge for effective and sustainable WEEE management. This study focuses on a geographical location, the MTN Phone Village in Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, which has garnered little attention in past studies on informal WEEE management. By focusing on this specific context, the study provides insights into the unique problems, practices, and dynamics of WEEE management within a specific informal sector environment. Hence, the study focuses on the formalisation of informal WEEE management practices in the MTN Phone Village. While the informal recycling sector has been researched in a variety of contexts, there is little awareness of the opportunities and challenges associated with formalising this sector in Nigeria. By studying the possible advantages and formalisation options, the study adds to the emerging discourse on sustainable waste management practices in the location. The WEEE management system adopted by the study comprises the application of two key concepts. The first concept includes limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only. This implies WEEE treatment, dismantling, etc., are carried out by government-approved agencies and experts. The second concept involves the application of the just-in-time (JIT) management concept for managing WEEE. The concept ensures that WEEE is only requested from the recycler or the individuals in possession only on demand. The study adopted a mixed research approach to enable the assessment of both qualitative and quantitative aspects of the research. The qualitative and quantitative data for the study were achieved with the use of semi-structured phone interviews and survey questionnaires respectively. The study outcome limits the activities of the informal recyclers to WEEE collection only, where informal recyclers gain revenue from WEEE collection. A reduction in the waiting time of workers and WEEE storage space is achieved. This offers safety, efficiency, and increases in WEEE processes. This will help to revolutionise the WEEE management system in the location. The study findings also help to create more awareness of the need for WEEE to be handled by properly trained and experienced personnel. It also adds to the existing knowledge of WEEE management.

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List of Abbreviations

MTN - Mobile Telephone Network
JIT -Just-in-time
NVA – Nonvalue added.
CRT - Cathode ray tube
EEE - Electrical and electronic equipment
EoL - End of life
EW - Electronic waste
WEEE - Waste electrical and electronic equipment
EPR – Extended producer responsibility
NGO – Non-governmental organisation
PCB – Printed circuit board
PWB – Printed wiring board
PVC – Polyvinyl chloride
POP – Persistent organic pollutants
PPE – Personal protective equipment
IQ – Intelligent quotient
HEI – Higher education institution
BFR – Brominated Flame Retardant
sCO₂ – Supercritical carbon dioxide
IT or ICT – Information (communication) technology
IC – Integrated circuit
PC – Personal computer
TV – Television
Cd – Cadmium
Au – Aluminium
Be – Beryllium
Li – Lithium
ILO – International Labour Organisation

Ni – Nickel

Zn – Zinc

Pb – Lead

Cu – Copper

Ag – Silver

Au – Gold

Pd – Palladium

Hg – Mercury

Sn – Tin

Ba – Barium

Sr – Strontium

Y – Yttrium

Eu – Europium

Se – Selenium

Cr – Chromium

As – Arsenic

Am – Americium

Sb – Antimony

CFC – Chlorofluorocarbon

HCFC – Hydrochlorofluorocarbon

HFC – Hydrofluorocarbon

LCD – Liquid crystal display

LED – Light-emitting diode

PBDEs – Polybrominated diphenyl ethers

PCBs – Polychlorinated Biphenyls

PBBs – Polybrominated biphenyl

OECD - Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

PC – Personal computer

PCB – Printed circuit board

PTV – Plasma television

ton – Mass unit, tonnage, metric ton, 106 grams

TV – Television

WPCB – Waste printed circuit board

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Chapter 1:

Introduction

This thesis presents studies addressing the behaviour change in a group of informal recyclers to reduce their exposure to potentially harmful substances at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The approach can be adopted in other locations that are faced with similar challenges. Tackling the challenges associated with informal WEEE management due to the uncontrolled activities of informal recyclers is all that is required to prevent pollution such as land, air, and water, as well as environmental pollution in the selected research location and other areas affected by similar problems. To tackle the challenges associated with informal recycling, this study adopted a combination of two key approaches. The approaches are reducing the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only and the adoption of the Just-in-time concept to WEEE management.

When individuals or small groups work outside of official waste management systems, it is referred to as informal recycling because they collect and process waste materials in an unorganized manner. This practice is common in many developing nations, where the infrastructure for waste management is frequently insufficient or non-existent. In industrialized nations, however, informal recycling is also common. Here, it could be motivated by financial incentives or a desire to cut waste. A variety of difficulties can arise from informal recycling practices, such as threats to employees' health and safety, environmental damage, and rivalry with established trash management systems.

Why is informal WEEE management system in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, a problem? Konya, Babatunde and Iniefe (2015), state that informal waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) handling in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, causes numerous significant challenges. According to Echendu and Georgeou (2021), an issue that affects any area in Port Harcourt, affects Rivers State, Nigeria. Nnorom and Odeyingbo (2020), posit that informal recycling causes environmental pollution. Informal WEEE management techniques sometimes use crude techniques for dismantling as well as disposal, for example, dumping and burning, which emit dangerous compounds into the environment. This a d d s to water a n d soil contamination, ecosystem deterioration, and air pollution, ultimately causing long-lasting environmental damage.

Jk *et al.* (2017), state that informal WEEE management exposes individuals to public health risk. In a related study by Decharat and Kiddee (2020), workers and nearby residents are

exposed to health risks as a result of harmful compounds such as lead, brominated flame retardants, and mercury, being released during informal WEEE management. Workers engaged in recycling and dismantling operations are especially prone to respiratory disorders, skin ailments, and other health problems caused by exposure to toxic materials. Shittu, Williams, and Shaw (2021), put forward that the informal WEEE management system lacks proper regulation. It takes place outside of regulatory frameworks, resulting in a lack of control and enforcement of health and environmental standards. This leads to unregulated disposal methods and insufficient protective measures, aggravating public health hazards and environmental pollution. Based on studies carried out by Ramprasad *et al.* (2022), and Shittu, Williams, and Shaw (2021), create room for resource waste. Informal WEEE management frequently fails to recover valuable components and materials from electronic devices effectively. As a result, precious resources including plastics, metals, as well as rare earth elements are depleted, limiting chances for resource recovery and recycling. According to Malik (2023), individuals involved with informal recycling have social issues. Informal WEEE management frequently involves marginalised and disadvantaged populations, such as garbage pickers and recyclers who may not have appropriate social protection or accessibility to healthcare. These people suffer insecure working conditions, poor earnings, and limited education and training opportunities, reinforcing social justice and cycles of poverty. Shittu, Williams, and Shaw (2021), assume that informal WEEE management takes place in a legal grey area, with little responsibility or recourse procedures for social and environmental damage brought about by unregulated practices. This hampers efforts to address the challenge via enforcement measures and regulatory interventions.

Therefore, informal WEEE management in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, is problematic due to negative environmental impacts, public health hazards, a lack of regulation, resource waste, economic consequences, social issues, legal and regulatory challenges mentioned above. Addressing these difficulties requires concerted measures to formalise and regulate the industry, improve the enforcement of environmental and health standards, encourage appropriate recycling techniques, and offer assistance for informal workers moving to formal employment.

Why should the informal WEEE management at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria be formalised? Okwu *et al* (2022), put forward that the informal WEEE management system in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi usually involves unsafe

dismantling and disposal techniques, resulting in environmental pollution by the discharge of toxic compounds like cadmium, lead, and mercury into the soil and neighbouring water bodies. Adami and Schiavon (2021), proposed that formalisation can enable regulated handling, disposal systems, and reduce environmental deterioration.

Abalansa *et al.* (2021), suggest that improper WEEE management endangers the health of workers and neighbouring residents. According to Masud *et al.* (2023), formalising WEEE management will ensure the adoption of safer methods, lowering health risks for workers, residents, and individuals that visit the location frequently. A related study carried out by Anandh *et al.* (2021), shows that WEEE contains important materials, which may be recovered and reused in production processes. Modoi and Mihai (2022), explained that formalisation can help to create collection locations and recycling facilities, that are equipped with the necessary technologies for successful resource recovery. This would help with resource conservation and encourage a circular economy approach. Bimpong, Asibey, and Inkoom (2023), state that formalising the informal WEEE management industry in MTN phone village in Rumukurushi, can provide job opportunities by establishing regulated recycling facilities, training programmes, and related services like material and logistics recovery. This can help to alleviate poverty and promote economic growth in Rumukurushi and the neighbouring communities. According to a study carried out by Tiwari, Mehra, and Gauba Dhawan (2023), formalisation will guarantee compliance with the existing waste and environmental management regulations in Rivers State and Nigeria. This includes getting licences, complying with health and safety standards, and meeting reporting obligations, which reduces the risk of legal penalties for noncompliance while also strengthening overall sector governance.

Anuardo *et al.* (2023), proposed that formalising WEEE management requires collaborating with the local community to increase awareness of the necessity of effective waste management practices and the possible advantages of formalisation. This would increase community engagement and support for long-term initiatives to improve public, environmental, and health outcomes (Pedro *et al.*, 2021). According to a study carried out by Franz and Luiz Da Silva (2022), formalising WEEE management aligns with sustainable development goals by tackling environmental, social, and economic concerns. Anuardo *et al.* (2023), put forward that it encourages responsible consumption and production practices, promotes the conservation of the environment, and helps to improve the well-being of local communities and the overall resilience of the region's economy.

To address the informal WEEE management and its associated challenges in the location, this study was carried out to address the behavioural change and potential to embed in the informal sector by:

- Raising awareness and informing people about the advantages of official waste management systems and the risks associated with unauthorized recycling. This may assist in lowering the demand for shady recycling services.
- Initiating a formal waste management strategy that is inexpensive and accessible to all community members in order to provide official waste management services. This may lessen the need for informal recycling activities.
- Creating more emphasis that providing informal recyclers support and training can help them improve working conditions and lower health and safety hazards. This might involve giving instructions on how to handle materials safely, providing safety gear, and aiding in the formation of cooperatives or other official institutions.
- Initiating an incentive system where informal recyclers are allowed to engage in WEEE collection only and be paid for the service while the other aspects of WEEE management are being handled by government-trained experts.
- Adopting the use of the Just-in-time concept for informal WEEE management helps to reduce the waiting time of workers and WEEE storage space. It also offers safety, efficiency, and increased productivity.
- Encouraging partnerships between informal recyclers and government agencies for a collective and effective WEEE management system.

1.1 Motivation and Background of the Study

The desire to engage in this research is the need to address the unending health and environmental challenges faced by the individuals in the research location due to indiscriminate disposal of WEEE and the activities of informal WEEE recyclers. Ineffective waste management techniques that can cause health risks and environmental pollution are frequently linked to informal recycling. To reduce environmental risks, it can be helpful to identify the problems and create solutions. Ph.D. study on the issues of informal recycling can further our knowledge of this crucial problem and aid in the development of workable solutions to the environmental, social, and economic issues it raises.

According to Rudăreanu (2014), One of the waste streams that are expanding the fastest globally is waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE). WEEE poses a double

environmental problem globally: on the one hand, the substances contained in e-waste are highly toxic and pose a serious threat to the environment if they contaminate the soil, water, or air. On the other hand, precious materials that can be recovered from WEEE, and used in the creation of other goods are also present. Due to these two issues, managing WEEE is one of the top priorities for organisations and governments worldwide. Shittu et al. (2021), state that future predictions indicate both the demand for and the production of EEE will increase. WEEE creation is anticipated to significantly grow as a result of technical advancements, improved accessibility, and expanded penetration of electronics. Mufti et al (2022), state that the pervasive, negligent, and thoughtless disposal of electronic & electrical garbage, along with government incompetence and no systematic oversight of it in any community, is unquestionably dangerous and harmful to the nation's economy and public health. E-waste left untreated poses a serious risk to public health and people's general quality of life. Additionally, it breaks and makes the environment useless for no apparent reason.

An “electrical and electronic equipment (EEE)” can be defined as a device or piece of equipment that needs electrical currents or electromagnetic fields to function as intended (Shittu et al., 2021, p. 549). Globally, 40–50 million tonnes of WEEE are produced each year, most of which are dumped in underdeveloped nations. Because of its cross-border impacts and the fact that it eventually causes contamination in industrialised nations, therefore WEEE is not a problem that can be solved by a single nation (Khan *et al.*, 2014). The WEEE material composition is very diverse and challenging to generalise due to a large number of electric and electronic appliances, the year of manufacturing, the origin, as well as the manufacturer (Cesaro *et al.*, 2018). Conversely, Okwu et al. (2022), argued that their recycling approach was incompatible with "contemporary waste management practices" due to the difficulties involved with the way the informal recycler carried out their tasks.

1.1.1 The need to manage WEEE and the activities of informal recyclers.

According to Herat & Agamuthu (2012), because of its hazardous components, improper management of e-waste may be harmful to both the environment and human health. Numerous nations are currently battling to deal with this new threat on a global scale. Osibanjo & Nnorom (2007) state that WEEE needs to be managed as there is no infrastructure for effective waste management, no law that addresses e-waste particularly, no framework for end-of-life (EoL) product take-back, and no “extended producer responsibility” programme (EPR). Omondi et al. (2022), argued that the majority of nations have demonstrated little to no effort to manage

the e-waste stream effectively. The reasons for this inactivity include a lack of understanding of the potential effects of the e-waste stream, ineffective enforcement by accountable regulatory agencies, a lack of recycling technology, and inadequate infrastructure for trash disposal. For instance, e-waste management standards are poorly implemented and the majority of people in poorer countries are unaware of them. According to Adanu et al. (2020), the majority of e-waste employees, according to study findings, are young and poorly educated. The employment of unsustainable technology to handle e-waste has led to worker injury and environmental contamination. Satyanarayan & Satyanarayan (2015), posit that several issues brought on by this garbage are irreversible and may cause the extinction of many living species and disturb the balance of the ecosystem. WEEE/e-waste components may contain more than 1000 different chemicals, both of which are recognised as being extremely dangerous and non-toxic. To safeguard our race and the environment, the quantity of this waste produced must be managed urgently and properly.

1.2 Research questions

- How can safe and sustainable disposal of hazardous materials at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, and cities in other nations faced with similar challenges be enhanced?
- WEEE management and recycling are currently being handled by informal recyclers who have little, or no knowledge of the dangers involved, how can their activities be checked, and reduced?
- What approach can be adopted to favour informal recyclers, and limit their activities because of the challenges associated with their operations?
- Valuable materials are disposed of as WEEE, how can we take full advantage of this source of raw materials?
- What must be done to enable the government to take over WEEE management in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt completely?
- Inhabitants of the location are faced with health challenges as well as loss of life due to exposure to dangerous elements of WEEE, what must be done to tackle these challenges?
- A large proportion of land that would have been put to good use is occupied by WEEE, what steps must be taken to correct this problem?

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

Aim

To address the health and environmental challenges associated with informal WEEE management.

Objectives

- To check and reduce the activities of informal WEEE recyclers since they lack the required skills and experience for proper WEEE treatment, processing, and disposal.
- To enhance safe and sustainable disposal of hazardous materials in the city of Port Harcourt and cities in other nations faced with similar challenges.
- To reduce the amount of land and waiting times used for WEEE storage.
- To facilitate effective recovery, reduction, reuse, repurposing, and recycling of WEEE
- To identify an approach that will favour the existing informal recyclers while measures are introduced to mitigate the challenges associated with their activities.
- To create awareness of the challenges associated with informal WEEE management in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, and the need to formalise the informal WEEE management system in the location.
- To offer recommendations on best practices in the WEEE management system.

1.4 Methodology

The study adopted both a non-experimental research design and a systematic review design and this is because both primary and secondary research studies were required (Menocal *et al.*, 2015). The research methodology is made up of the research philosophy, research approach, data collection method, and data analysis method.

Research Philosophy

To guarantee that both subjective and objective viewpoints were sufficiently taken into account, the study utilised a pragmatic research philosophy. This involves the use of both positivist and interpretivism research philosophies. Also, both qualitative and quantitative studies were adopted (Ragab and Arisha, 2017). By merging the two philosophies, researchers can gain a more thorough grasp of the research topic. Positivism stresses empirical data gathering and statistical analysis, which yield quantitative insights into patterns and trends. In contrast, interpretivism centers around subjective experiences, context, and meanings, providing qualitative richness and depth to the study. Integrating these viewpoints enables

researchers to evaluate both subjective interpretations and objective facts (Mustofa, 2023). Using several research approaches and methods (both qualitative and quantitative) offers strength to the reliability and validity of the findings via triangulation. Triangulation entails cross-validating data collected using several methods, which reduces bias and improves the robustness of the outcome of the study. Positivism approaches like statistical analysis, experiments, and surveys can be complemented with interpretivist techniques like content analysis, Interviews, and observations (Bans-Akutey and Tiimub, 2021)

Research approach

Khaldi (2017), states that in between the qualitative and quantitative research approaches, exists the mixed approach. The study adopted a mixed research approach, hence, both qualitative and quantitative data were used. Ragab and Arisha (2017, p.3), a new theory development can be achieved with the help of two approaches, it is either carried out with the use of “deductive reasoning” or through “inductive theory building”. According to the same research work, the deduction approach allows for quantitative data collection while the inductive approach allows for qualitative data collection.

The use of a mixed-method approach for this study, informal waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) management in the MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, is justified by the complex and multifaceted nature of the research questions, as well as the need to gain comprehensive insights into the phenomenon (Mulisa, 2022). The mixed-method approach mixes qualitative and quantitative approaches to capitalise on their respective strengths and address research questions from various viewpoints (Shrestha and Giri, 2021). The mixed-method approach provides a thorough knowledge of informal WEEE management by capturing both the depth and breadth of the phenomena (Hsueh-Yu and Tseng, 2023). Qualitative techniques, including observations, interviews, and focus groups, may give rich, comprehensive insights into the lived experiences, perspectives, and social dynamics of stakeholders who engage in informal methods of WEEE management (Hamilton and Finley, 2019).

However, quantitative techniques like statistical analysis and surveys can provide more comprehensive patterns, trends, and numerical information on waste generation, recycling rates, as well as socioeconomic indicators (Mohajan, 2020). The study can obtain a more comprehensive grasp of the research issue by combining the two methodologies (Booth, 2023). The mixed-method approach allows for triangulation, which is the process of comparing and

contrasting data from different approaches to improve the study's reliability and validity (Vivek and Nanthagopan, 2021). Triangulation reduces the limits of individual methodologies and gives a more solid foundation for drawing conclusions and making recommendations (Jack and Raturi, 2006). A study carried out by Nooraie *et al.* (2020) put forward that qualitative data may be employed to contextualise and explain quantitative findings, whilst quantitative data can assist in validating qualitative insights.

The mixed-method approach provides adaptability and flexibility to the evolving nature of the research process. It enables researchers to iteratively modify research questions, change data-gathering techniques, and triangulate findings based on emerging insights. This flexibility is especially useful when investigating a dynamic and context-dependent phenomenon like informal WEEE management (Shrestha and Giri, 2021). Qualitative and quantitative methodologies provide complementary insights into distinct parts of the study issues (Gilad, 2021). Qualitative approaches are well-suited for examining complicated social phenomena, comprehending human behaviour, and capturing nuances that quantitative measures may miss (Khan and Razzaque, 2023). Meanwhile, quantitative approaches give numerical data that can be statistically analysed, generalised, and hypothesis tested, resulting in objective and replicable conclusions (Daniel, 2016). While both quantitative and qualitative methods have their strengths, there are inherent limitations. Relying entirely on qualitative methodologies may restrict the generalizability of findings and overlook quantitative patterns and trends. In contrast, depending entirely on quantitative methods risks oversimplifying complex social processes and missing out on valuable qualitative insights. The mixed-method approach addresses these constraints by integrating multiple perspectives (Queirós, Almeida and Faria, 2017; Rahman, 2017).

The use of qualitative methods solely can provide useful insights into stakeholders' lived experiences and views, but it may lack statistical rigour and generalizability. In contrast, a solely quantitative approach may give numerical statistics on waste generation and recycling rates while ignoring the socio-cultural, economic, and institutional aspects that influence informal WEEE management (Mcleod, 2023).

Regarding the balance of deductive and inductive reasoning, the mixed-method approach allows for both styles of reasoning to be used as appropriate to the research context. Inductive reasoning derives general principles from specific observations or data, whereas deductive reasoning tests hypotheses based on established concepts or theories. In this study, qualitative

approaches may use inductive reasoning to investigate themes, patterns, and meanings arising from empirical data. In contrast, quantitative approaches may rely mostly on deductive reasoning to test hypotheses obtained from existing literature or theoretical frameworks (Barroga *et al.*, 2023). The mixed-method approach was adopted in the study to create a balance between deductive and inductive reasoning, utilising quantitative and qualitative methodologies to complement one another and give an in-depth understanding of informal WEEE management at MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria (Mitchell, 2018).

Data collection method.

The data collection method for this study was achieved with the help of a semi-structured interview and survey questionnaires. A semi-structured interview was conducted in this study, and this aligned with a study by Ragab and Arisha (2017, p.12), which hold forth that it creates room for “a set of predetermined questions” to be used. According to the study, it also allows for a reasonable amount of flexibility as new questions can be asked or “existing questions” can be discarded, in that way, new ideas can emerge while the conversation is on. The initial idea was to conduct a face-to-face semi-structured interview but due to the prevailing COVID- 19 pandemic, a semi-structured phone interview was carried out instead. Both primary and secondary data collection was done in the study. Primary data collection was done via semi- structured phone interviews and survey questionnaires. Secondary data collection, on the other hand, was obtained from the review of past works of literature. The semi-structured phone interview was carried out successfully. Conversely, a visit to the site was also carried out to verify the main data collection. This approach was developed to deal with the COVID-19 restrictions, that prevailed during the period of data collection. An attempt was made to include people who can provide rich and detailed information on the study being researched, hence a purposeful sampling strategy was used (Okesina, 2020). Also, a convenience sample approach was used in an effort to include people who are readily available and accessible for the study (Rahi, 2017).

Ensuring data-gathering techniques that are transparent is critical for sustaining the reliability and integrity of research findings (Aguinis, Hill and Bailey, 2019). The study offered a detailed illustration of the methodology adopted, this includes a mixed-method approach, the technique of data collection implemented (for example, observations, surveys, and interviews), and how the data was analysed (Ganesha and Aithal, 2022). The study ensured that ethical issues including gaining informed consent from respondents, maintaining anonymity

and confidentiality as well as addressing any potential conflicts of interest were considered (Brittain *et al.*, 2020). The study ensures proper data management and accuracy in reporting (Moher *et al.*, 2020). The research's aim and objectives were clearly communicated to participants, to ensure they understood the significance of their participation and the expected results (Sreekumar, 2023). During data collection, actively listening to participants' viewpoints, issues, and experiences to establish rapport and trust, and encourage open and honest feedback were adopted (Neill and Bowen, 2021). The study observed cultural norms, beliefs, and viewpoints during interactions with participants to enable meaningful involvement and minimise possible biases (Hecker and Kalpokas, 2022).

An effort was put in place by the study to determine a suitable sample size based on the study's objectives, statistical considerations, and demographic characteristics, to provide adequate data for meaningful analysis and interpretation (Hennink and Kaiser, 2022). The qualitative approach, for example, the interview adopted was carried out in a manner that data saturation is reached. This implies that no new insight or themes arose from subsequent data collection, suggesting that adequate breadth and depth of information were obtained (Braun and Clarke, 2021). The study ensured flexibility is maintained throughout the interviews to adjust semi-structured questions based on the flow of discussion, participants' responses, as well as emerging themes, which allows a deeper examination of relevant areas and maintains data richness (Mashuri *et al.*, 2022). The study created questionnaires based on ideas derived from a thorough examination of relevant literature, including previous research on informal WEEE management, waste management methods, and socioeconomic variables that influence behaviour (Varma Vijayan *et al.*, 2023). Before full-scale deployment, a pilot test was carried out on the questionnaire with a small sample of participants to check the clarity, comprehensibility, and relevancy of the questions, and make any required adjustments based on feedback (Li *et al.*, 2023).

Field visits enable researchers to gather firsthand knowledge about the operational practices, social dynamics, and physical environment, associated with informal WEEE management in the MTN Phone Village. Field visits allow one to evaluate and complement data acquired using other approaches (such as surveys and interviews) by exploring actual WEEE management processes, interactions, and infrastructure (Bisschop, 2012). During field trips, researchers engage with important stakeholders such as informal recyclers, local authorities, and community members, to build up connections, obtain additional information, and create collaboration for lasting solutions (Owusu-Sekyere and Aladago, 2023). Field visits

attempt to complement other data-gathering methods by fostering triangulation of research findings, allowing researchers to validate information gained from secondary sources, surveys, and interviews with first-hand observations and interactions in the field (Frias and Popovich, 2020).

Data analysis method

The data gathered via the semi-structured phone interview was analysed using thematic analysis after audio transcription was carried out. The survey questionnaires were analysed using a graphical method. Analysing quantitative data graphically and qualitative data using thematic analysis in mixed-method research has various benefits and can lead to a better understanding of research questions or phenomena (Guetterman, Fàbregues and Sakakibara, 2021). In mixed-method research, evaluating qualitative data through thematic analysis and quantitative data graphically provides a strong method to enable someone to comprehend complicated phenomena. It encourages exhaustive data exploration, triangulation of findings, integration of perspectives, improved interpretation, and explanation, capturing complexity as well as leveraging the combined strengths of quantitative and qualitative techniques (Fetters, Curry and Creswell, 2013).

Confidentiality and ethical considerations

This study was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences, University of the West of Scotland (reference number 21-8607-3338). An effort was also made to obtain written informed consent from all the interview and survey participants. Every research participant was made aware that they had the option to opt in or out of the data-gathering procedure at any time. Moreover, measures were put in place to make sure that participants' personally identifiable information was not obtained. The research effort made was honest and devoid of plagiarism, and the findings were presented correctly. The report of the study's findings was produced in a way that is free of prejudice and makeup in any way, shape, or form. This is true for the study's design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation of the findings.

Any financial interest that may affect the study's outcomes will be disclosed. By being eager and ready to share the data gathered, its findings, and any newly created tools or equipment, the research was able to guarantee that openness was demonstrated. The collected data was electronically stored in a password-protected computer system. Also, the gathered

information was saved or preserved in a cabinet that was secured with a lock and key. As a result, no unauthorised persons or individuals will be able to update or alter the data.

1.5 The Novelty of the Thesis

The study focuses on a particular geographical location, the MTN Phone Village in Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, which has garnered little attention in past studies on informal WEEE management. By focusing on this specific context, the study provides insights into the unique problems, practices, and dynamics of WEEE management within a specific informal sector environment. The study adopts a mixed-method approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative methods to offer an in-depth understanding of informal WEEE management. While prior studies may have relied only on qualitative or quantitative methodologies, the combination of the two in this study provides for a more nuanced analysis of the research topic, capturing both depth and breadth of ideas. The study focuses on the formalisation of informal WEEE management practices in the MTN Phone Village. While the informal recycling sector has been researched in a variety of contexts, there is little awareness of the opportunities and challenges associated with formalising these sectors in Nigeria. By studying the possible advantages and formalisation options, the study adds to the emerging discourse on sustainable waste management practices in the location.

The study investigates the complex interaction of factors impacting informal WEEE management using ideas from a variety of disciplines, including environmental science, public health, economics, and sociology. Using an interdisciplinary approach, the study illuminates the interconnected economic, social, and environmental dimensions of the research topic, providing a comprehensive knowledge of the challenges at hand. Beyond academic research, the study aims to offer practical recommendations and policy implications for stakeholders in WEEE management, environmental governance, and urban planning in Port Harcourt and other similar situations. The study's goal is to help Nigeria establish sustainable and equitable WEEE management methods by turning research results into practical actions.

1.6 Contributions of the Thesis

- It will enhance the safe and sustainable disposal of hazardous materials in the city of Port Harcourt and cities in other nations faced with similar challenges.
- Valuable materials or precious metals like Gold, Copper, etc., will be efficiently recovered for reuse and recycling.
- The study will help to revolutionise the WEEE management system in Port-Harcourt.

- It will increase the process, efficiency, and safety of personnel during WEEE management.
- It leads to a reduction in the waiting time of workers and WEEE storage space.
- The study adds to the existing knowledge in the area of specialisation.
- It will enhance the efficient sorting of hazardous materials from non-hazardous materials after dismantling, a practice that is carried out improperly.
- It will help to check and reduce the activities of informal WEEE recyclers since they lack the required skills and experience for proper WEEE treatment, processing, and disposal.
- With this system in place, effective recovery, reduction, reuse, repurposing, and recycling of WEEE is possible.
- It will create job opportunities.
- It will offer the government an opportunity to manage WEEE treatment, processing, and disposal in the city of Port Harcourt and other locations faced with the same challenge.
- It will help to reduce other risks associated with informal WEEE processing, treatment, and disposal in the city of Port Harcourt and other locations faced with the same challenge.
- It will help to create awareness of the need for WEEE to be handled by properly trained and experienced personnel.

1.7 Structure of the Thesis

Chapter One introduces the background and context of the thesis, the research questions, the research aim and objectives, methodology adopted which embraces the research paradigm, approach, data collection method as well as data analysis technique adopted in the study. Also mentioned in this segment of the thesis are the confidentiality and ethical considerations observed during the study, contributions of the thesis, outline of thesis structure, and finally, the list of publications.

Chapter two covers an overview of relevant literature and research in the field of informal WEEE management. In this section of the thesis, past works of literature on several aspects of WEEE management were reviewed. These include the methodology of the literature review, WEEE category, hazardous components in WEEE, a review of past works of literature, WEEE status in Nigeria, WEEE practice with health impacts, common activities, and issues, and Waste electrical electronics equipment trends. Other aspects also covered under the overview

of relevant works of literature are the need to recycle WEEE or dispose of WEEE, how to dispose of WEEE, recycling methods in Nigeria, factors that affect the WEEE management system in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria and WEEE management system proposed for MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. This segment of the study also covered the research gaps and challenges in the existing literature.

Chapter three sheds light on the consequences of informal recycling in the mobile telephone network phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers) in Port Harcourt. The level of education, health, and safety awareness of the informal recyclers, their willingness to obey government guidelines, and their knowledge of waste electrical and electronic equipment management were investigated. Other areas covered in this section of the thesis include the research design and approach, data collection and analysis of the questionnaires administered to the participants, ethical considerations, and the outcome of the survey questionnaires offered to the participants.

Chapter four covers the need to eliminate or reduce the role of recyclers in the informal sector, in particular, to reduce health risks associated with the management of WEEE in Rumukurushi, in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. This applies to similar situations in other cities. Other areas covered are details of the newly introduced concept for the management of WEEE by informal recyclers, which limits their activities or services to WEEE collection only. Tables, graphs, and figures are used to illustrate the outcome of the questionnaires administered to participants. Also included is the interpretation and discussion of findings.

Chapter five deals with the effort made to minimise the activities of the informal recyclers (in the selected location and other areas affected by similar challenges) in WEEE management in order to tackle completely the challenges associated with their method of practice. Other aspects of the study covered in this section are the research design and approach, data collection method, and analysis technique adopted in performing semi-structured phone interviews. The two key concepts adopted to tackle the challenges associated with informal recycling were also covered in this section. Also treated are the interpretation and discussion of the findings of the outcome of the semi-structured phone interviews carried out using the thematic analysis method.

Chapter six embraces the overall conclusion, the study's key contributions, and recommendations.

1.8 List of publications

Journal papers

- Okwu, O., Viza, E., Hursthouse, A., & Idoko, L. (2022). Menace of informal waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13762-022-04663-1/FIGURES/7>
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- Okwu, O., Hursthouse, A., Viza, E., & Idoko, L. (2021). Enhancement of WEEE Management Practices in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Recycling*, 6(4), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RECYCLING6040077>
- “An overview of WEEE management system” – to be completed soon

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Chapter 2:

Literature review

Tackling the challenges associated with informal WEEE management due to the uncontrolled activities of informal recyclers is all that is required to prevent pollution such as land, air, and water, as well as environmental pollution in the selected research location and other areas affected by similar problems.

This chapter of the thesis reviews WEEE management system and this embraces the concept of WEEE management. It covers the methodology of the literature review (which includes the inclusion and exclusion criteria), WEEE category, hazardous components in WEEE, a review of past works of literature, the research gap, WEEE practice with health impacts, common activities, and issues, Waste electrical electronics equipment trends. Other areas reviewed are the impact of COVID-19, the waste ban in China, the need to recycle WEEE or dispose of WEEE, how to dispose of WEEE, WEEE management system proposed for MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, the research gap and finally, the main conclusion.

Port Harcourt, an oil city in Nigeria, usually experiences a massive number of individuals entering the location in search of financial benefits from the oil and gas industries. Because of this ever-rising number of inhabitants, there is an increase in the consumption of materials, population, WEEE, and other environmental contaminants. The quantity of WEEE that emerges from these devices when they are no longer useful have been on a steady increase (Konya, Babatunde and Iniefe, 2015). Furthermore, according to the same study, this is largely a result of the increasing need for communication and information technology, enhanced technology in some parts of the world, resulting in the dumping of “old and discarded” electrical and electronic equipment to countries like Nigeria where such items are still gaining patronage. Those items are usually expired or close to expiration before they are transported into poor nations, which tends to increase the quantity of generated WEEE.

According to Kalamaras *et al.* (2021), WEEE, which appears to be among the biggest and ever-rising streams of waste globally has become an issue of serious concern due to its associated challenges. The problem created by WEEE appears to be twofold. First and foremost, it is among the most speedily increasing waste streams globally, standing as a potential threat to humans, animals, and the environment. Secondly, because of its makeup, which is complex,

WEEE is also one of the most difficult waste streams to manage (Danz *et al.*, 2019). In Port Harcourt, a city in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria, the WEEE collectors do not practice formal recycling methods. The system in practice is the informal recycling method carried out majorly at the dumpsite where they engage in the sorting of WEEE as well as recycling (Amadi and Chijioke, 2018).

Ohajinwa *et al.* (2017), put forward that informal recyclers engage in several activities, which include the recycling of WEEE. Their services are usually at a low cost, but the working procedure used is not safe, hence their health is at risk.

In a related study by Amadi and Chijioke (2018), the WEEE and other waste are usually gathered at Igwuruta, Elelenwo, and Abuloma locations in Port Harcourt unsorted. WEEE serves as a source of raw materials but during the informal recycling process, the estimated useful metals recovered is only 25 percent (Leung *et al.*, 2008; Starovoytova, 2018).

WEEE, in a study by Mihai *et al.* (2019), appears to be a growing waste stream worldwide. The inappropriate handling of WEEE creates room for serious pollution and health-related challenges. This is usually the case as the dismantling of WEEE is carried out under “poor conditions”. Dumping WEEE in Africa has been an age-long practice. It is usually carried out by uneducated individuals, and this exposes them to harmful substances. Due to lack of organized collection centres in Nigeria, WEEE is dumped together with waste from the hospital and as well as others from the community and in the process creates more complications in the sector. In some communities, WEEE is dumped inside bodies of water and open fields resulting in environmental pollution. Items considered to be of no use economically are usually burnt regularly to reduce their quantity or deposited in open fields or water bodies. Indiscriminate discarding of WEEE has resulted in the increase in polybrominated diphenyl ethers and polychlorinated biphenyls concentration in the serums of individuals in the location. Fluorinated biphenyls and analogues are also toxic pollutants emitted due to indiscriminate dumping of WEEE (Awere *et al.*, 2020; Bi *et al.*, 2007; Bimir, 2020; Kitila and Woldemikael, 2019; Mihai and Gnoni, 2017; Zhu *et al.*, 2021).

Electronic appliances such as televisions, monitors, etc., are designed to make life simpler and happier for us, but they contain harmful elements that are evident during disposal or recycling. The majority of those who make use of them are not aware of the associated risks of using them frequently (Needhidasan, Samuel and Chidambaram, 2014). The landfills, as well as unauthorised dumping sites, appear to be the terminal point of the majority of the WEEE

gathered (Forti *et al.*, 2020). Harmful gases are usually released into the environment during the burning of WEEE (Mostafa and Sarhan, 2018; Kitila and Woldemikael, 2019). The disposal and recycling of cathode ray tubes (CRTs) have the potential to expose life to health risks due to the presence of lead and antimony. The presence of a high percentage of lead in CRT funnel glass (i.e. 22%) makes it harmful to life. Besides, lead, CRTs consist of fluorescent powders, barium, and cadmium, all of which are toxic. The harmful elements contained in CRTs are easily absorbed in the soil with time and are consequently passed to humans and animals (Ciftci and Cicek, 2017; Lecler *et al.*, 2015; Ledwaba and Sosibo, 2017; Xu *et al.*, 2016).

The presence of devices that contain mercury causes soil pollution as well as health risks. Both non-beneficial and non-essential components of mercury are potential risks to living things globally. The presence of mercury contamination in the environment can result in food chain pollution especially when it accumulates in edible parts of plants. Mercury appears to be more poisonous than lead and cadmium and it causes loss of hearing, vision and mental retardation (Ali and Al-Qahtani, 2012; Ismičić-Tanjo *et al.*, 2021; Natasha *et al.*, 2020). WEEE comprises toxic elements as well as metals and as such constitutes a serious threat to health. The adjectives commonly used to describe WEEE processes are hazardous, toxic, and dangerous, as such a lot of attention is required to help proffer a solution to this environmental challenge. The tissue and surface of edible fresh vegetables easily harbour heavy metals. This exposes human life to poisonous substances. Skin contact and drinking water have also been recognised as means of exposure to metals that are toxic (Ahen and Amankwah-Amoah, 2021; Gebeyehu and Bayissa, 2020; Zhou *et al.*, 2016).

Unprofessional WEEE burning and dismantling methods significantly contribute to the pollution of air. This can result in secondary exposure as some of the pollutants are able to travel over a long distance to other locations from the recycling sites (Attia, Soori and Ghaith, 2021). The soil, as well as the crops grown in the WEEE dumpsites, are usually faced with a high concentration of metals such as lead, zinc, copper, etc. Accumulation and uptake by plants constitute the major entry channel for metals that are toxic to animal and human food. Examples of such toxic metals are metalloids such as lead, mercury, cadmium, selenium, and arsenic. Crops that grow in metal-polluted location usually show a reduction in growth, reduced biomass production, accumulation of metal, and alteration in metabolism. A lot of individuals like to grow crops around and within WEEE dumpsite as they believe the land is fertile and as such, crops will grow well. Research has demonstrated that locations contain a lot of metals

(Clemens, 2006; Nagajyoti, Lee and Sreekanth, 2010; Omorogieva and Tonjoh, 2020; Sagbara *et al.*, 2020).

In recent research by George, Mapa, and Dinggai (2019), the increasing quantity of WEEE is ascribed to several factors, and these are because of technological improvement, availability of assorted electronic and electrical devices for sales, reduction in prices of electronic and electrical devices, and the extreme “high demand” for them. WEEE serves as a good source of rare metals, plastics, etc. This is a result of the continuous need for metals, reducing mineral resources, natural resources exploitation as well as the environmental and cost implications of mining. Several methods are adopted to extract metals, for example, studies have shown that copper present in Printed circuit boards, PCB can be extracted with the use of a mixture of aqueous acid and supercritical CO₂. Studies have also shown that rare earth elements can be recovered via electrochemical recovery. In a recent study, important metals, for instance, copper, silver, and gold were recovered from the printed circuit board of computers that are no longer in use via physical separation after which, the leaching technique is applied. In addition, copper can be directly separated and recovered for waste PCBs via slurry electrolysis carried out with an acidic system. Product designs that are environmentally friendly have been encouraged in the European Union via the legislature to support the recovery of valuable materials from WEEE (Hossain *et al.*, 2019; Hsu *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2019; Tamsalı, Özer and Burat, 2020; Wang, Zhang and Guan, 2016; Wang *et al.*, 2021; Zhang, Schnoor and Zeng, 2012).

According to Cole *et al.* (2019), “the recovery and treatment of WEEE” serves as an alternative source of important elements, for example, copper, gold, etc. The indiscriminate WEEE disposal and the challenges that come with the inappropriate disassembling and management of WEEE, observed in numerous countries that are still developing, result in numerous consequences (Ferronato and Torretta, 2019). An effort made by Khan *et al.* (2014), indicates that most of the WEEE that is globally generated yearly, which amounts to at least 40 million tonnes finds its way to developing countries as their dumping ground. Nigeria now appears as one of the dumpsites for Asia, the US, and Europe WEEE (Lawal, 2019). Ferronato and Torretta (2019), put forward that, the developed countries have seen the export of WEEE to Asia and Africa as a preferred option, instead of using the prospect to develop their national recycling infrastructure, develop an innovative design that stops the existence of further toxic material use and switching to cleaner sustainable technologies.

According to Adeola (2018), it was observed that the amount of WEEE generated worldwide amounted to about “50 million metric tonnes” in 2018. In his work, he emphasized that WEEE production is one of the consequences of the manufacture and usage of electronic devices. Furthermore, the research work indicates that the multipurpose nature of most information and communication technologies (ICTs) has made them desirable to consumers and because of their comparatively short life, there has been a build-up of great capacity of WEEE, which constitutes problems at all levels. WEEE contains hazardous elements, and this poses problems to the government in terms of its management (Wilson *et al.*, 2015). This calls for concern as such, it has attracted a lot of awareness lately due to its uses and effect on the environment (Dagiliūtė *et al.*, 2019). The estimated quantity of WEEE produced worldwide in 2018 increased to 49.8 metric tons. (Adeola, 2018).

2.1 Methodology of the literature review

The study literature review was carried out using databases that are web-based such as Scopus, Google Scholar and General, Web of Science, and Mendeley. The main database used in the study is Google Scholar. The literature review was done with the help of search strings such as “informal recyclers” AND “WEEE management” OR “e-waste management” alongside different keywords. Keywords that relate to WEEE management or e-waste management were considered during the literature search. The keywords are recycling, dismantling, hazards, environmental pollution, risk assessment, reuse, sorting, landfills, dumpsite, land pollution, metal recovery, extended producer responsibility, etc. Five thousand four hundred and forty-five (5445) data materials were returned during the search on the Google Scholar database but due to factors such as the abstract and title of papers published from the study, coupled with the fact that repeated pieces of information were removed. The data size was reduced to about 500 data materials. The study considered both criteria for inclusion and exclusion.

The criteria for inclusion and exclusion are given below.

Inclusion criteria

- Include peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, dissertations, and reports written in English.
- To ensure the literature is up to date, the study included research published within the last five years.

- Include empirical studies such as randomized controlled trials (RCTs), observational studies (cohort, case-control, cross-sectional), qualitative studies, and systematic reviews/meta-analyses that investigate the topic of interest.
- Include studies with persons 18 years and above who have a documented medical condition or risk factor related to the study research questions.
- Include studies that evaluate the impact of a specific intervention, exposure, treatment, or risk factor relevant to the study research questions.
- Include studies that assess important outcomes such as clinical outcomes (e.g., morbidity, and mortality), patient-reported outcomes (e.g., satisfaction, and quality of life), or intermediate outcomes (e.g., physiological measures, and biomarkers).
- Include research done in any geographical region to ensure an accurate representation of the literature.
- Include research undertaken in a variety of contexts, such as academic institutions, clinics, hospitals, and community settings.
- Include studies that have appropriate methodological quality, as determined by validated quality assessment methods or criteria relevant to the study design.

Exclusion criteria

- Exclude commentaries, editorials, opinion pieces, letters, and non-peer-reviewed publications.
- Exclude papers published more than five years ago to prioritise recent works of literature and ensure relevance with current practice.
- Excludes studies published in languages other than English owing to proficiency constraints.
- Excludes non-empirical studies, such as letters to the editor, commentaries, narrative reviews, and editorials.
- Exclude studies on pediatric populations or subgroups that are not relevant to the study research questions.
- Exclude studies that do not include any specific intervention, exposure, treatment, or risk factor of interest.
- Exclude studies that do not measure outcomes relevant to the study research questions or report outcomes of interest.

- Exclude studies done in geographical areas that are unrelated to the research scope or context.
- Exclude studies done in settings unrelated to the research questions or population of interest.

2.2 WEEE category

The record indicates that 40-70 million tons of WEEE are generated in the world annually, which is seen as a 3 percent increase (Menikpura, Santo and Hotta, 2014). Electrical and Electronic equipment close to the EoL period is creating a global problem, particularly in many developing countries of the world. WEEE continues to rise more than expected due to the manufacture of new EE devices, which makes the initial product obsolete (Lu *et al.*, 2017, Song and Li, 2014). In China, obsolete PCs and TVs are at an increasing rate of 24.69% and 8.2% annually (Ardi and Leisten, 2016). In India, WEEE annual generation was estimated to grow at 7% as recorded by (Dwivedy and Mittal, 2010). In most European countries, a disturbing growth rate was also recorded where 5-7 million tons are produced on a yearly basis (Singh, Li, and Zeng, 2016).

The growth of WEEE in every five years in European countries is increasing at the rate of 17-27%, amounting to three times the average municipal growth rate of WEEE generated yearly (Shah Khan *et al.*, 2014). In North and South America, the number of outdated EEE products stored or discarded as waste is growing at an alarming rate. In the continent, out of the millions of WEEE generated, only a few percent were recycled and landfilled, and some were transported to developing nations (Ongondo, Williams, and Keynes, 2011). In Europe, the annual volume of WEEE generated by households is estimated to be approximately 7 million tons/year (Chancerel *et al.*, 2013). WEEE stream globally may change drastically if disposal to landfill and incineration in North America is reduced and exports for reuse to developing nations increase.

Studies have indicated that 400-700 million units of outdated PCs in developing countries by 2030, as being compared with developed nations of 200-300 million (Yu *et al.*, 2010). Household WEEE generation exceeded an annual amount of 20 million tons in 2005, as recorded with the exclusion of Canada and North American nations. In 2005, a total amount of 3.8 million tons, totalling about 20% of the world WEEE stream was shipped to developing countries with landfilling as the option (Chancerel *et al.*, 2013). Basel Action Network reports millions of used computers at the end-of-life period are transported into Asian

and African countries from the US, and Europe adding to the WEEE generation and increasing the rate of WEEE disposal in developing nations. The ten (10) categories of WEEE according to Gap (2018) as shown in Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1 The 10 WEEE categories

Details of the devices in the ten WEEE categories according to WEEE (2014) are given in Table 2.1

Table 2.1 10 Categories Covered by WEEE Directive

S/no	WEEE category	Main products
1	Large household appliances	These include Large cooling appliances. Refrigerators. Freezers. Other large appliances used for refrigeration. Conservation and storage of food. Washing machines. Clothes dryers. Dishwashing machines. Cooking. Electric stoves. Electric hot plates. Microwaves. Other large appliances used for cooking and other processing of food. Electric heating appliances. Electric radiators. Other large appliances for heating rooms, beds, seating furniture. Electric fans. Air conditioner appliances. Other fannings, exhaust ventilation and conditioning equipment.
2	Small household appliances	These include Vacuum cleaners. Carpet sweepers. Other appliances for cleaning. Appliances used for sewing, knitting, weaving and other processing for textiles. Irons and other appliances for ironing, mangling and other care of clothing. Toasters. Fryers. Grinders, coffee machines, and equipment for opening or sealing containers or packages. Electric knives. Appliances for hair-cutting, hair drying, tooth brushing, shaving, massage and other body care appliances. Clocks, watches and equipment for the purpose of measuring, indicating or registering time. Scales
3	IT and telecommunications equipment	These include Centralised data processing. Mainframes. Minicomputers. Printer units. Personal computing. Personal computers (CPU, mouse, screen, and keyboard included). Laptop computers (CPU, mouse, screen and keyboard included). Notebook computers. Notepad computers. Printers. Copying equipment. Electrical and electronic typewriters. Pocket and desk calculators. Other products and equipment for the collection, storage, processing, presentation or communication of information by electronic means. User terminals and systems. Facsimile. Telex. Telephones. Pay telephones. Cordless telephones. Cellular telephones. Answering systems. Other products or equipment of transmitting sound, images or other information by telecommunications
4	Consumer equipment	This includes Radio sets. Television sets. Video cameras. Video recorders. Hi-Fi recorders. Audio amplifiers. Musical instruments. And other products or equipment for the purpose of recording or reproducing sound or images, including signals or other technologies for the distribution of sound and image than by telecommunications.
5	Lighting equipment	This includes Luminaires for fluorescent lamps with the exception of luminaires in households. Straight fluorescent lamps. Compact fluorescent lamps. High-intensity discharge lamps, including pressure sodium lamps and metal halide lamps. Low-pressure sodium lamps. Other lighting or equipment for the purpose of spreading or controlling light with the exception of filament bulbs.
6	Electrical & Electronic tools (with the exception of large-scale stationary industrial tools)	These include Drills. Saws. Sewing machines. Equipment for turning, milling, sanding, grinding, sawing, cutting, shearing, drilling, making holes, punching, folding, bending or similar processing of wood, metal, and other materials. Tools for riveting, nailing or screwing or removing rivets, nails, screws or similar uses. Tools for welding, soldering or similar use. Equipment for spraying, spreading, dispersing or other treatment of liquid or gaseous substances by other means. Tools for mowing or other gardening activities
7	Toys, leisure & sport equipment	These include Electric trains or car racing sets. Hand-held video game consoles. Video games. Computers for biking, diving, running, rowing, etc. Sports equipment with electric or electronic components. Coin slot machines
8	Medical devices (with the exception of all implanted and infected products)	These include Radiotherapy equipment. Cardiology. Dialysis. Pulmonary ventilators. Nuclear medicine. Laboratory equipment for in-vitro diagnosis. Analysers. Freezers. Fertilization tests. Other appliances for detecting, preventing, monitoring, treating, alleviating illness, injury or disability. 1
9	Monitoring and control instruments	These include Smoke detectors. Heating regulators. Thermostats. Measuring, weighing or adjusting appliances for household or as laboratory equipment. Other monitoring and control instruments used in industrial installations (e.g. in control panels)
10	Automatic dispensers	These include Automatic dispensers for hot drinks. Automatic dispensers for hot or cold bottles or cans. Automatic dispensers for solid products. Automatic dispensers for money. All appliances which deliver automatically all kind of products

2.3 Hazardous Components in WEEE

The rise in EEE, including communication, computing, and entertainment, is a result of the dynamic nature of changing applications that have accelerated technological advancement in all sectors of the economy. Increasing processing, energy efficiency, and speed in the operation of EEE are some of the anticipated specifications to meet product performance (Kumar and Dixit, 2018). Due to the continuous modification of shapes, functions, design of new products and applications, EEE contains a great heterogeneous mixture of materials for durability and efficiency in task executions. There are essential constituents in EEE including critical metals and precious metals (Palladium, Gold, and Silver), and special metals (Tellurium, Indium, Selenium, Tantalum, Bismuth, and Antimony) (Chancerel and Rotter, 2009). For the life cycle and environmental impacts of the EEE, the manufacture of components and their use is often a factor. There is a challenge associated with the use of the WEEE imported as the majority of the imported equipment cannot be reused and hence, it is usually dumped. This exposes the environment to toxic components (Iwenwanne, 2019).

Steel and Plastics are the two domineering materials used in EEE, and the weight distribution of the substances differs from value distribution and related environmental pressure. Gold accounts for less than 1% of the device weight (Mobile Phone), and at the same time accounts for over 50% of the material flow created by its production (Ongondo, Williams and Cherrett, 2011). Due to the heterogeneity of the EEE device to meet several functions and applications, they are not void of substances hazardous to health and threats to the environment. Hazardous substances capable of threatening human health and the environment if not handled and processed accurately in EEE are, Cathode Ray Tubes (CRTs) in old TVs and computer monitors, Printed Wiring Board (PWB), capacitors, batteries, and accumulators, toners and ink cartridges, liquid crystal displays (LCDs) and Printed Circuit Board (PCBs) (Salhofer and Tesar, 2011).

PWBs contain many metals and Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs), which are toxic and affect humans and the environment. The hazardous heavy metals found in the components of WEEE are Cd, Ni, Zn, Pb, Hg, Sn, Ba, Sr, Y, Eu, Se, Cr (iv), which are found in accumulators and batteries, solders, cathode ray tubes, screen coating, memory switches, thermostat, etc. The most prevalent used operation in the processing of WEEE for the extraction of precious metals, like acid leaching and the open burning of dismantled components. Have resulted in the release of toxic metals and pollutants into the environment, which is capable of causing considerable

damage to the environment and risk to human health (Birloaga *et al.*, 2013; Fu and Wang, 2011; Grant *et al.*, 2013).

Substances, devices in which they can be found as well as their potential effects as regards environment and health safety is as shown in Figure 2.2

Substances	Occurrence in WEEE	Possible adverse effects
Lead (Pb)	CRT screens, batteries, PCBs	Vomiting, diarrhea, convulsions, coma or even death, appetite loss, abdominal pain, constipation, fatigue, sleeplessness, irritability and headache
Mercury (Hg)	Fluorescent lamps, some alkaline batteries, switches	Brain and liver damage
Chromium VI (Cr ⁶)	Data tapes, floppy-discs	Irritating to eyes, skin and mucous membranes, DNA
Barium (Ba)	Getters in CRT	Brain swelling, muscle weakness, damage to the heart, liver and spleen
Cadmium (Cd)	NiCd batteries, fluorescent layer (CRT screens), printer inks and toners	Symptoms of poisoning (weakness, fever, headache, chills, sweating and muscle pain), lung cancer and kidney damage
Arsenic (As)	Gallium arsenide in light emitting diodes (LED)	Skin diseases, decrease nerve conduction velocity, lung cancer
Americium (Am)	Smoke detectors	Radioactive element
Antimony (Sb)	Flame retardants in plastics	Carcinogenic potential
Chlorofluoro carbon (CFC)	Cooling units, insulation foams	Deleterious effect on the ozone layer, increased incidence of skin cancer and/or genetic damages
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB)	Condensers, transformers	Cancer, effects on the immune systems, reproductive system, nervous system, endocrine system and other health effects
PBDEs, PBBs	Flame retardants in plastics	Hormonal effects, under thermal treatment possible formation of dioxins and furans

Figure 2.2 Substances, their occurrence in WEEE, and potential effects as regards environment and health safety (Kaya, 2016)

2.4 A review of past works of literature

Several efforts have been made in the past and more research is ongoing to manage WEEE. Among the numerous efforts made to manage WEEE previously are as given below:

Ikhlal (2018, p. 119), tried to tackle the public health and environmental challenges associated with informal WEEE recycling. The study designed a systematic concept for WEEE management. The concept is referred to as “integrated e-waste management (IEWM)”. The theoretical concept embraces both the management of WEEE and “municipal solid waste” collectively since both use similar disposal and treatment systems. Quantitative data collection was adopted in the study. The outcome of the study proposed the use of “integrated e-waste management” to tackle the public health and environmental challenges associated with informal WEEE management. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the adopted approach. This is because the focus of the study is the use of “integrated e-waste management” to tackle the public health and environmental challenges associated with informal WEEE management.

Rimantho *et al.* (2022, p. 1), attempted to proffer a solution to the public and environmental challenges associated with informal WEEE management in Indonesia by adopting the use of “waste bank system”. The study suggested the adoption of “waste bank system” model for the collection of WEEE. A conscious effort was also made in the study to engage DKI Jakarta stakeholders for value support and input, while some selected samples were collected for the purpose of the study. Data gathering for the study was achieved with the help of interviews. The outcome of the study proposes a waste bank WEEE collection system and calls for the attention of the government with regard to the creation of an enabling environment and regulations for the stakeholders. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges using the combined concepts. This is because the study focused on the use of “waste bank system” without considering measures to control the role of the informal recycler.

Ogbuanya and Afeez (2019, p. 90), tried to ensure WEEE approaches applied in the workshops of “electrical/electronic technicians” are advanced for sustainable public health.

Data collection was carried out using questionnaires administered to 54 “public health” senior staff as well as 87 Engineering lecturing staff. The data analysis was attained using “percentage, mean, and standard deviation white t-test and ANOVA”. The study findings reveal that providing “recycling sites”, introducing and applying policies are the major approaches required for the management of WEEE. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges using the combined concepts. This is because the focus of the study was to identify indicators that may be of help.

Juma *et al.* (2022, p. 238), carried out an assessment of the impact of WEEE stakeholders with respect to the sustainability of WEEE management “by evaluating their course of action”. The study proposed a conceptual framework for WEEE management based on the major stakeholders, which was validated using 346 highly positioned workers in key positions in 10 cities in Uganda. Data gathered for the study were analysed using “structural equation modelling (SEM)” method and “partial least square (PLS) technique”. The study outcome reveals that the effect of consumer role on WEEE management sustainability is insignificant while the role played by the producer, the media, local government, financial institution, and WEEE handlers have a significant impact on the sustainability of WEEE management. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the combined concepts and this is because the study only focused on the impact of WEEE stakeholders with respect to the sustainability of WEEE management.

Arya, Gupta, and Bhardwaj (2018), attempt to investigate the degree of understanding of informal recyclers, and users (individuals, organisations, and companies) as regards hazards created by WEEE. The study collected data via questionnaires administered to three different WEEE stakeholders namely, organisations, individuals, and those who are into the services of recycling WEEE. The composition of those who responded to the questionnaires are; 10 persons engaged in the services of WEEE recycling, 25 users of electrical and electronic appliances, and 35 organisations considered as users. The study outcome reveals that the individuals and the organisational users lack consciousness of the problems associated with WEEE. There is a lack of ideas as regards legislation on WEEE. There exists an absence of proper channels for the collection of WEEE. Conversely, the recycler in the informal sector

who is not aware of the risk associated with WEEE engages in unsafe disposal methods. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the combined concepts. This is because it primarily focused on the degree of understanding of the informal recyclers and users without considering measures to limit their activities in WEEE management. Besides, the study also failed to identify health and safety training as an avenue to gain awareness.

Woggsborg and Schröder (2019, p. 1), investigated the emerging impact of private-public partnerships in the management of WEEE in developing countries. The study adopted the use of two different concepts, and these are “the triple bottom line approach and the sustainable livelihoods approach” for the analysis of a case study carried out on the “Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) programme in Nigeria”. The study outcome identifies the available opportunities and offers recommendations with respect to the formation of an engagement model that can support informal sector participation by key players such as government agencies, and individuals in both national and international private sectors. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the study focused on the impact of private-public partnerships in the management of WEEE in developing countries.

George, Mapa, and Dinggai (2019), tackled WEEE management with households as its main focus using an assessment of the electrical and electronic device composition in the apartments of the people in the chosen area, and the way in which WEEE is managed. Data collection for the study was achieved using questionnaires. The study outcome reveals that the electronic and electrical appliances that appear the most in the area, are phones. Furthermore, the study outcome also reveals the selected area adopted an unsustainable system of managing WEEE. This is because they don't recycle WEEE but allow them to remain inside their homes or put them inside the waste bin. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches because no attempt was

made to put a check on the activities of the informal recyclers but recommendations were offered.

Maphosa and Maphosa (2020, p. 1), investigated the status of the sub-Saharan African WEEE management system by performing a critical review of the approach adopted for the management of electronic waste in the location. The study adopted “a systematic literature review (SLR)” approach on past works of literature collected from Sabinet, EBSCO host, and “Web of Science” databases with the help of keywords like recycling or e-waste management, or policy in Africa or sub-Saharan Africa. The study outcome shows that 80% of WEEE management research carried out in sub-Saharan Africa was performed in South Africa, Nigeria, and Ghana. The findings also indicate that the major obstacles to effective WEEE management in the region are inadequate infrastructure for recycling and shortage of viable policies. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the study focus is on the approaches adopted in the location for the management of electronic waste.

Ndunda and Ambole (2018, p. 73), made an effort to tackle the problems introduced by the informal method of WEEE recycling via the creation of “a product-service system” for its management. Those who support the move, from the provision of products to the “provision of systems of products and services” were put in place beside stakeholders' support for WEEE to be managed efficiently. The dematerialization technique was applied via stakeholders' collaboration; this hinders the consumer or recyclers in the informal sector from equipment possession after EOL. The outcome indicates the collaborative effort of those involved determines the success of the technique. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the problem associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the focus of the study is to tackle the problems introduced by the informal method of WEEE recycling via the creation of “a product-service system” for its management.

Donny and Suzianti (2022, p. 1636), proposed a WEEE collection application interphase design. The study adopted “a design thinking approach” to the collection of electronic waste with a specific focus on customer needs. In order to gather data for the study, the use of comprehensive interview techniques, personas, prototypes, etc., was adopted. The study

outcome reveals that the design-thinking concept enables individuals to formulate “user interphase prototypes” for WEEE collection applications. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the target of the study was the development of prototypes of the user interface for the WEEE collection application.

Aidonis et al. (2019), created a methodology to recognise an optimal management scheme for WEEE, in order to find another means of integrating WEEE. The study made use of a binary linear programming model to improve the effectiveness of nine (9) options to manage WEEE. Consideration was given to 12 criteria in terms of performance, which cover environmental, financial, social, and technical dimensions were given consideration. The study outcome reveals that the best approach is exporting residues of WEEE and mechanically recycling WEEE. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches because the technique proposed does not have the potential to tackle the menace of informal WEEE management activities, for example recycling. A technique that has the potential to minimize informal WEEE recycling may be more useful.

Mehmood Shad, Ling, and Karim (2020) carried out a detailed overview of WEEE management with a specific focus on three countries that are situated close to each other and that are also faced with the problems of WEEE management. These countries are Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore. The study outcome suggested that the WEEE management system in place needs to be enhanced, and the flow of WEEE, which is usually free, can be limited by formulating effective WEEE laws. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the study emphasised the need for WEEE free flow to be restricted but failed to consider placing any form of restriction on the informal recyclers.

Mihai et al. (2019), utilised waste statistical information and “thematic cartography to disclose how WEEE is moved from one geographical location to another. The approach utilized to

manage WEEE in numerous locations was examined, for instance, Europe, North America, South America, Oceania, Africa, etc. The findings indicate that inadequate amenity is the idea behind the poor technique of managing WEEE adopted in Africa. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches as it focuses on the properties of improper management of WEEE. Identifying a useful method that can tackle any of the challenges facing recycling in the informal sector may be helpful.

Franz and Da Silva (2021) made an effort to create an alignment with respect to WEEE legislation, management, and generation as well as its interface with reverse logistics, cleaner production, and ecosystem. A qualitative research approach was adopted for the study. The study data, which were obtained from secondary sources were analysed using content analysis. The outcome of the study reveals that the challenges associated with WEEE legislation, management, generation, and all others, can be tackled via the use of circular economy. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the focus of the study is the adoption of circular economy to tackle the challenges associated with WEEE legislation, management, generation, and all others.

Parajuly *et al* (2019), made an effort to investigate many facets of the challenges associated with WEEE management and offer ideas on future problems that may likely emerge. The study outcome indicates the need for future WEEE unforeseen opportunities and challenges to be introduced in public discussions so that such pressing issues can be investigated as early as possible. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only? The study did not address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using both approaches. This is because the focus of the study is to investigate many facets of the challenges associated with WEEE management and offer ideas on future problems that may likely emerge.

Research gap

Several efforts have been made by researchers in the past to proffer a solution to the challenges associated with informal WEEE management, but these challenges remain. No one has been able to address the challenges associated with informal WEEE management using the application of Just-in-time concept and limiting the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only. This research gap in this field forms the basis of this study. Besides, this study contributes to the existing literature in the area of specialisation.

2.4.1 WEEE practice with health impacts, common activities, and issues

The electrical electronic sector which includes computing, Telecommunications, and the entertainment industry is the world's leading industry in terms of the manufacturing of new devices used in its services. The growth recorded economically by the availability of new electronic goods in the market that have replaced obsolete household electrical and electronic equipment is high, which has generated an increasing number of WEEE in the world due to the production of new substitutes yearly. Recent research, (D'Adamo, Rosa and Terzi, 2016) state that valuable elements are recovered from the treatment of WEEE as an alternative and essential means of assessing valuable materials, but several challenges emerge from managing the electronic elements present in the WEEE.

At present, there is no globally accepted definition of WEEE. Every region and nation within its legal system sets up definitions and terms of usage. WEEE has diverse definitions from many researchers as it does not have a generally accepted definition (Adeola, 2018). According to EU Directive 2012/19/EU, WEEE is electrical, and electronic equipment that is a waste, including all components, consumables, and sub-assemblies that are part of the EE product at the time of discarding the waste. Bhutta, Omar, and Yang (2011) conclude e-waste incorporates broad and a growing range of electronic devices ranging from large household EEE, such as refrigerators, air conditioners, personal stereos, cell phones, consumer electronics, and personal computers (PCs) that have been discarded by the original users. Step Initiative (Step, 2014), considers WEEE term used to cover almost all types of EEE that enter the waste stream, including televisions, computers, mobile phones, white goods, fridges, washing machines, dryers, etc.

Among the list are home entertainment and stereo systems, toys, toasters, kettles, and any household appliances or office EEE with the circuit or electrical components with battery

supply for its functionality. In general terms, WEEE consists of obsolete electrical electronics equipment, which can be defined as electrical electronics equipment products, that work with batteries or connect to electricity for their function, and which have been obsolete due to the production of a new model of its kind or no longer wanted by the original owner (Chancerel and Rotter, 2009).

2.4.2 Waste Electrical Electronics Equipment Trends

Khan *et al.* (2014) shows that most of the WEEE that is globally generated yearly, which amounts to at least 40 million tonnes finds its way to developing countries as their dumping ground. Nigeria now appears as one of the dumpsites for Asia, US, and European e-waste as shown in Figure 2.3

Figure 2.3 E-waste dumpsite in Nigeria (Lawal, 2019).

In (Adeola, 2018), it was observed the amount of WEEE generated worldwide amounts to about “50 million tons”. In his work, he emphasized that WEEE production is one of the consequences of the manufacture and usage of electronic devices. Furthermore, the research work indicates that the multipurpose nature of most ICTs has made them desirable to consumers, and because of their comparatively short life, there has been a build-up of great capacity of WEEE, which constitutes problems at all levels. This calls for concern as such it has attracted a lot of awareness lately due to its uses and effect on the environment (Dagiliūtė *et al.*, 2019). The projected volume of e-waste generated globally according to Adeola (2018) is shown in Figure 2.4

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Figure 2.4 The projected amount of e-waste generated globally.

Similarly, the attempt made by some countries to regulate e-waste as well as the amount of e-waste generated is shown in Table 2.2

Table 2.2 Regulatory attempts on e-waste, the quantity, and generators (Adeola, 2018)

The system of information gathering in which waste and secondary products are unknown to national statistics in manufacturing, sale, and trade of new products stands as a barrier worsening the inappropriate database system of the WEEE stream. From records, only a few of the statistics of transported EEE products are categorically designed to differentiate new EEE from used EEE, which turns to WEEE depending if it is near the EoL period (Ongondo,

Williams and Keynes, 2011). With the unknown statistics of new EEE and used EEE, Australia, and Hong Kong were the first countries to generate guidelines for differentiating new EEE and used EEE for clarity (Chung, Lau and Zhang, 2011).

South Korea exports each year about 1.8 million used electronics (computers) to China, avoiding the recycling, disposal costs, and likely human and environmental impacts of recycling and disposal within its territory (Zoeteman, Krikke, and Venselaar, 2010). With the present rate of EEE generation, it can be deduced that the disposal of outdated EEE products is driven primarily by the production of newer versions or close substitutes of such EEE. The developed countries have seen the export of WEEE to Asia and Africa as a preferred option, instead of using the prospect to develop their national recycling infrastructure, develop an innovative design that stops the existence of further toxic material use and switching to cleaner sustainable technologies (Zoeteman, Krikke, and Venselaar, 2010).

2.4.3 The impact of COVID-19

Covid-19 has had a devastating impact on national and global economies, regardless of the extent of the viral impact on particular nations' citizens. The unique coronavirus knows no borders, no religion, and spreads regardless of caste or faith. It is very infectious and quite unpredictable in nature. The world wasn't ready for this type of pandemic, and we are now racing to create a vaccine to prevent its spread (Kumar Verma and Prakash, 2020). In terms of research, 80% of higher education institutions (HEIs) said that the COVID-19 epidemic had an impact on their institutions' research. The most prevalent impact "of COVID-19 has been the" cancellation or delay of overseas travel (83% of HEIs) and scientific conference cancellation or postponement (81% of HEIs). Furthermore, at slightly more than half of HEIs (52%), "scientific projects are at risk of not being" completed (Marinoni et al., 2020, p. 3). According to UKRI (2021) survey, some of the impacts of COVID-19 on research include:

- Shielding or lockdown had a detrimental influence on research time, according to 61% of researchers.
- 58% of respondents claimed that COVID-19 prevented them from doing the planned study.
- More than half of respondents claimed that COVID-19 constraints interfered with other work tasks, such as teaching and administration, which limited their time for research.
- 88% of those surveyed who had parental duties said those obligations interfered negatively with their ability to do research. This was gender-neutral.

- Less commuting and work-related travel, according to 56% and 43% of respondents, respectively, had a favourable influence on their time for research.
- 27% endorsed their study has benefited unexpectedly from COVID-19.

2.4.4 The Waste Ban in China

The Chinese government's ban on solid waste not only altered the global supply chain for recycled solid waste, diverting it to Malaysia and other Southeast Asian markets. It also prompted the development of new solid waste management infrastructure in these new destination nations, to come up with the capability to handle sudden increases in waste streams (Song *et al.*, 2021). Municipalities and waste management firms from Australia to the United States are looking for alternatives after China said it would no longer serve as the world's primary landfill for recovered garbage. However, experts claim it presents a chance to create better remedies for a culture that is increasingly becoming disposable. The action was taken as an effort to stop a flood of filthy and polluted materials from swamping Chinese processing plants and leaving the nation with yet another environmental issue that is not of its invention (Katz, 2019). Beginning at the end of 2019, China progressively ceased the importation of waste that is recyclable, that can be substituted by domestic waste. As a result, imports of home waste plastics and waste metal and electrical appliance scraps were prohibited by the end of 2017, and the end of 2018, respectively. The China Ban or China Shock is a sudden shift in policy that significantly affected the world market for plastic garbage (Katz, 2019).

China has created and disposed of a sizable amount of WEEE being the largest manufacturer, user, and importer of electrical and electronic equipment. China produced the most WEEE in the world, at 7.2 Mt, in 2016, and roughly 3.66 Mt (16.055 million units) of WEEE were recycled. However, the majority of the collection is made by lone collectors and dealers, whose work is loose and unsustainable because it is low-tech, low-paying, unrecorded, and unregulated. This is mostly due to the fact that an efficient formal WEEE collecting system, which is the first stage in recycling and is essential to its scope, scale, efficiency, and effectiveness, has not been fully established or consolidated (Zhang, 2021; Zuo, Wang and Sun, 2020).

2.5 The Need to Recycle WEEE or Dispose of WEEE

WEEE is important and must be properly managed for the following reasons: environmental and health effects, sources of materials, behavioural concerns, and the increasing amount of WEEE worldwide.

2.5.1 Environmental and Health Effects

The entire waste from EEE is composed of environmentally unfriendly elements. We dump WEEE easily into our landfills and with time, these items decompose and become a source of toxins to the water we use and the earth. This puts our lives and the entire environment at risk. The bulk of EEE is made of several materials such as plastics, lead, arsenic, mercury, etc. This compounded and hazardous combination of elements implies that well-trained professionals are required for WEEE recycling due to the health and environmental risks involved. (EnviroCraft, 2018). The all-around dumping and the challenges that come with the inappropriate disassembling and management of WEEE, observed in numerous countries that are still developing, results in numerous consequences, the increasing amount of WEEE worldwide, and Behavioural concerns.

2.5.2 Sources of Materials

WEEE serves as a potential source of elements like Gold, Aluminium, and Copper. If we don't make use of these elements in WEEE, new materials will need to be obtained for the production of this equipment which implies a waste of valuable materials. Besides the loss of valuable elements in WEEE, stockpiling by consumers may be inevitable (Ongondo and Williams, 2011).

2.5.3 Behavioural concerns

Shipping of WEEE illegitimately from rich countries to countries that are poorly developing, and that may not have the right mechanism in place for the treatment of the WEEE is now rampant. Furthermore, WEEE obtained via illegitimate shipping of WEEE is usually managed in a manner that does not consider safety and health standards (Ongondo and Williams, 2011).

2.5.4 The increasing amount of WEEE worldwide

The amount of "discarded EEE" is increasing rapidly, the trend is mostly in the OECD member countries, and this is because there are a lot of large quantities of newly manufactured EEE

which results in an increase in WEEE. A Large quantity of WEEE that has been discarded is found in several locations in the world (Ongondo and Williams, 2011).

2.6 How to dispose of WEEE.

According to CI (2019), WEEE can be disposed of in three major ways namely: Landfill, incineration, and recycling. In the case of the landfill, WEEE is disposed of by burying them. Due to the hazardous nature of WEEE coupled with the scarcity of space at most sites used as landfills, dumping of WEEE at sites used as landfills needs to be discouraged. Several hazards associated with landfilling according to Annamalai (2015) are shown in Figure 2.5

Figure 2.5 Hazards of landfills

For elements that are volatile and biologically not degradable eg Cd, Hg, CFC, or persistent for example Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB), treatment by landfilling is not environmentally friendly. Due to this mixture of e-waste materials, it is not feasible to eliminate the risk involved.

In the case of incineration, the WEEE is destroyed through burning, and the burning of the WEEE is done at a temperature that is high. Some of the benefits of this disposal method include: the energy can be recovered from the burning elements and used, secondly, there is depletion in the volume of WEEE. It also has demerits, and these are: it adds considerably to the amount of mercury and cadmium emitted annually, heavy metal content in the WEEE is

usually not released to the atmosphere via emission, they are converted to slag and residues from gas, and during disposal, these waste still shows up in the environment (Annamalai, 2015; CI, 2019). Some of the associated hazards with the incineration method of waste disposal are shown in Figure 2.6

Figure 2.6 Hazards associated with incinerator method of waste disposal

The recycling method of waste disposal converts WEEE or some elements of WEEE into brand-new forms. This helps to cut down on the use of new raw materials as the existing materials are converted to new forms (CI, 2019). In this method, elements of WEEE that are composed of harmful elements eg Hg, PCB, plastics, etc., are dismantled. The recyclers are exposed to danger by working with no masks and technical skills in an enclosed location with poor ventilation. According to Annamalai (2015), some of the hazards due to the recycling method include:

- The presence of mercury affects the development and functioning of the brain
- This method of WEEE disposal exposes the environment and human health to risk
- There is a risk of damage to the human kidney, blood system, peripheral and central nervous system due to the presence of lead.

In Okorhi, Omotor, and Aderemi (2020, p. 3), the record has it, that the collection, handling, and refurbishing of WEEE is carried out by informal recyclers, who are illiterates, of a low standard, without experience. They are usually “undocumented business” persons, they usually

lack training and investment, and they go about the streets and waste dumps with their handcarts to collect or buy in rare cases abandoned WEEE and other metal scraps, which “contain” important elements like Iron, Brass, Copper, Aluminium, etc. Ohajinwa *et al.* (2018), explain that the recycling of most of the WEEE generated is carried out in an informal/unsafe way such that toxic elements are released into the environment. According to Mihai *et al.* (2019), the informal WEEE recycling practice appears to dominate the Nigerian WEEE market. These informal recycling activities happened often in the backyards or little workshops in Nigerian cities (Port-Harcourt) where primary methods of manual disassembly and open burning are practiced. Primitive techniques like the performance of dismantling manually, melting of metals, acid dipping, and open burning are often utilised to recover valuable materials from WEEE. The informal recycler does not adopt optimized methodologies for material recovery, for example, metals are usually recovered via heating WEEE in a hot plate or open flame. In some instances, WEEE is shredded mechanically to help recover valuable metals (Hameed, Ali and Petrillo, 2020; Butturi *et al.*, 2020; Luo *et al.*, 2014; onwughara, Nnorom and Kanno, 2010), (Luo *et al.*, 2014).

The WEEE is recycled by removing components or valuable materials, and these materials are; integrated circuit (IC) plastics, condenser, Cathode ray tubes (CRTs), Printed wiring board (PWB), and metals, which were part of the system that are reprocessed directly as reusable components for raw materials (Salhofer, 2018). The commonly practiced process of harnessing most of the materials is through an open burning system that is injurious to human health and the environment (onwughara, Nnorom and Kanno, 2010). The actors in the informal sectors are the cart pushers, the scavengers (those who sort and recover materials that can be reused or recycled), the resource merchants, and the recyclers (Alabi and Wohlmuth, 2019). Despite the problems associated with the informal WEEE management system, it serves as a source of employment and a means of livelihood for several families (Ohajinwa, 2018).

The importance of recycling is not centered on WEEE requiring treatment, but to enhance the recovery of valuables in the discarded WEEE from the dumpsites. The crude methods employed by the informal recyclers cannot adequately recuperate the potential toxic elements (PTEs) in the EEE (Gangwar *et al.*, 2019). Thereby the call for funding by all stakeholders for the upgrading of the recycling sector and proper integration of the sectors in Nigeria is a necessity. However, studies have revealed that informal recycling methods and activities like dismantling, open burning of plastics and wire, and indiscriminate disposal led to a significant level of potentially toxic elements and persistent organic pollutant emission to air, soil, and

water. The existing pathways to the soil, environment, and impact on humans, methods and activities described of WEEE management in the informal sector (Ferronato and Torretta, 2019; Williams *et al.*, 2008).

Studies reveal that informal recycling activities such as open burning of wires and plastics, dismantling, and unregulated disposal result in the release of significant levels of heavy metals, and persistent organic pollutants to the soil, air, and underground water and surface (Ezeudu and Ezeudu, 2019; Gangwar *et al.*, 2019). However, a study carried out by Ezeudu and Ezeudu (2019), shows that Nigeria does not have the capacity for formal recycling methods, maybe due to the lack of modern recycling facilities in the country. Conversely, Omokaro (2018, p. 18), explains that the effort made to commence formal recycling in Nigeria failed due to “consumption habits”, political, social, economic “and cultural context”, which aids the services of the informal recyclers.

Presently, the WEEE management system at MTN phone village, in Port Harcourt city, Nigeria, is carried out by informal recyclers who lack the basic knowledge on the prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery, and disposal. This study attempts to change the existing WEEE management practice in the location as the focus is to prevent the harmful and primitive style of WEEE management carried out by recyclers in the informal sector in the area as well as other regions faced with a similar practice. Furthermore, the moment the activities of informal recyclers are drastically reduced at MTN phone village in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, the problems associated with recycling in the informal sector will come to an end.

2.7 WEEE management system proposed for MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

This study intends to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. This will be achieved via the combination of two different approaches namely.

- Recovering WEEE from residents, informal recyclers, and the remaining part of the public for sorting, processing, treatment, and recycling by government-approved agencies.
- Application of the just-in-time (JIT) lean management principles to the current WEEE management system in the location.

The WEEE management system ensures that only government-approved agencies are allowed to manage WEEE. WEEE is collected from residents, informal recyclers, and the remaining part of the public and this will help to cut down informal recycling and the challenges associated with it. The application of the just-in-time concept is applied by government-approved agencies after WEEE collection/gathering. Furthermore, the dismantling of WEEE is carried out by experienced and trained government personnel to ensure that the dismantled WEEE materials follow appropriate processing such as re-use, further treatment, refining.

2.8 Main conclusions

This section of the thesis reviews WEEE management system and this embraces the concept of WEEE management. It covers the methodology of the literature review (which includes the inclusion and exclusion criteria), WEEE category, hazardous components in WEEE, a review of past works of literature, the research gap, WEEE practice with health impacts, common activities, and issues, Waste electrical electronics equipment trends. Other areas reviewed are the impact of COVID-19, the waste ban in China, the need to recycle WEEE or dispose of WEEE, how to dispose of WEEE, WEEE management system proposed for MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, the research gap and finally, the main conclusion. The study contributes to the existing knowledge in the field of specialisation.

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Chapter 3:

Menace of informal waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

The material in this chapter has been published as “Menace of informal waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria” (Okwu *et al.*, 2022a). The paper titled "Menace of informal waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling at MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria" is most likely related to the International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology (IJEST), as it was published in that Journal. This implies that the article addresses environmental challenges of informal waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling in a specific site in Nigeria, namely the MTN phone village in Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt. The International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology (IJEST) is a peer-reviewed scientific journal that publishes research papers, reviews, and technical ideas on environmental science and technology. It covers a wide variety of environmental issues, such as pollution, waste management, sustainable development, and environmental impact assessments. Hence, the connection between the paper and the journal lies in the fact that the paper was accepted and published by IJEST. This signifies that the paper satisfies the Journal's standards for quality and relevance in the field of environmental science and technology.

Port Harcourt, a major city in the southern part of Nigeria experiences a rise in population, consumption of materials, waste electrical and electronic equipment, and several environmental contaminants due to the large number of individuals moving to the location to gain from the oil and gas companies financially. Consequently, there is a constant increase in the amount of WEEE generated in the location (Konya, Babatunde and Iniefe, 2015). The WEEE recyclers in the mobile telephone network (MTN) phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers) in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria do not adopt the formal technique of WEEE recycling. The informal technique of WEEE recycling is the main method in operation, and it is done mainly in the dumpsites where WEEE undergoes services such as sorting, dismantling, treatment, etc (Amadi and Chijioke, 2018). According to Ohajinwa et al (2017), informal recyclers are ignorant of their right or the

protection available to them. They offer WEEE recycling services at a low price, their working method is not safe, hence the health of individuals and the surrounding environment are not safe. Charles (2018) hold and state that WEEE serves as a good source of important raw materials, but it has to be properly managed to avoid its associated challenges.

This chapter sheds light on the consequences of informal recycling in the mobile telephone network phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers) in Port Harcourt. The level of education, health, and safety awareness of the informal recyclers, their willingness to obey government guidelines, and their knowledge of waste electrical and electronic equipment management were investigated. Other areas covered in this section of the thesis include the outcome of the survey questionnaires offered to the participants. The outcome reveals that informal recyclers in the research location lack knowledge and awareness of waste electrical and electronic equipment management best practices. They also lack awareness of the use of personal protective equipment and the application of health & safety in the discharge of their duties. In addition, the study outcome also shows that informal recyclers in the research locations are willing to obey government guidelines on waste electrical and electronic equipment management. Informal recyclers are willing to quit other waste electrical and electronic equipment management processes if they can be paid by the government for gathering them. The study recommends that the activities of the informal recyclers should be restricted to WEEE gathering only

3.1 Literature survey

The disposal of WEEE or e-waste, which appears to be a general practice in developing countries results in numerous consequences, for example, environmental pollution, which results in chronic and acute health challenges (Ferronato and Torretta, 2019). Several hundred chemical substances that are toxic can be contained in a single computer and these are Polyvinyl chloride, brominated flame-retardant, cadmium, mercury, and lead (Aas, 2015). When WEEE that comprises toxic elements is landfilled, there is a high probability that groundwater will be affected through leaching (Bożym, Król and Mizerna, 2021). According to Vaccari et al (2019, p.15), individuals who walk through the pathways and means of transportation along the dumpsites are usually affected by the “spread of pollutants” from the facilities utilised by the informal recyclers in the location. It was mentioned in several studies that a great amount of inorganic and organic contaminants exist “in the bodies” of individuals who reside or work in such areas. Njoku, Edokpayi and Odiyo (2019), put forward that those who reside close to

the landfill site and the individuals passing through the site experience severe air contamination due to the bad odour from the site. Residents are exposed to illnesses like weakness of the body, eye irritation, and flu. Similarly, those who pass through the site are at risk of contracting airborne diseases, etc. During the burning of debris, smoke tends to cover some part of the location, this affects the inhabitants. Besides, the decomposing WEEE gives out an offensive smell, especially in the wet season when the location tends to be filled with flies and other insects (Ferronato and Torretta, 2019). Furthermore, the recyclers make use of crude recycling techniques, hence they lack the right infrastructure that can guarantee the safety of life and the environment (Yu *et al.*, 2010). Waste electrical and electronic equipment, WEEE, and its associated challenges have become an issue with increasing concern as it comprises several toxic elements (for example, cadmium, mercury, lead, brominated flame retardants, and polyvinyl chloride) capable of causing severe harm to human beings and the environment. In developing countries, recycling is done in such a poor manner that it results in serious pollution of the environment. Hence, sediments, water, soil, and air in locations where informal recycling is carried out are associated with a great accumulation of organic and inorganic pollutants. The exposure of individuals and the environment to these pollutants puts them at risk. If urgent measures are not put in place, the situation will get worse (Al-Rahmi *et al.*, 2018; Cesaro *et al.*, 2019).

Globally, the need to utilise electrical or electronic devices is increasing, hence it has necessitated the development of new devices (Ohajinwa *et al.*, 2019). The challenges associated with WEEE are aggravating due to the increase in the manufacture of electronic or electrical devices coupled with the exportation of WEEE to developing countries from those that are developed (JK *et al.*, 2017). According to Herat (2018), it is almost certain that the amount of WEEE generated in countries that are still developing exceeds that of countries that are developed and equipped with the technology required to manage them. Amadi and Chijioke (2018), stated that the challenges associated with the style of execution of the duties of the informal recycler put their recycling system against “modern waste management practices” besides, the formal WEEE recycling system does not exist in Nigeria at the moment.

Okorhi *et al.* (2020), argue that services such as e-waste gathering, processing, and refurbishing are performed by recyclers in the informal sector, and these groups of individuals lack experience, they are usually of low standards, and are illiterate. Furthermore, the informal recyclers are generally “undocumented-business” persons, they operate without investment and standard training. They move from one street or waste dump to another “with their handcarts

to collect” or buy on rare occasions abandoned e-waste and other metal scraps that “contain” useful elements such as Aluminium, Brass, Iron, Copper, etc. Ohajinwa (2018), explains that a lot of toxic elements are released into the environment since the recycling of the majority of WEEE generated is done in a manner that is informal/unsafe. In a related study by Mihai et al (2019), it was gathered that the informal WEEE method of recycling dominates the Nigerian WEEE sector. In developing countries, for example, Nigeria, WEEE management is carried out by informal recyclers in a manner that is not professional, they tend to dispose of e-waste in a manner and location that are not regulated thereby exposing individuals and the environment to health challenges (Adeola, 2018). Some countries are more environmentally friendly and advanced technologically than others as regards the WEEE management approach adopted, yet it is difficult for the recycling process to be achieved without any form of impact on the environment (Arif and Afroz, 2013).

3.1.1 Challenges of Informal recycling in the selected location in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Informal recycling in MTN phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers), faces a lot of challenges, and this is because the strategies in place for WEEE management are affected by many factors identified in Okorhi et al (2014, p. 11). These factors are:

- a. WEEE declaration at the entry point is usually done in an incorrect manner for instance “second-hand goods” labelled as a donation/gift for “individuals or groups”
- b. It is difficult to differentiate WEEE from near-end-of-life electrical and electronic equipment.
- c. A localised standard recycling system is absent.
- d. It is difficult to initiate and “pursue take-back programmes” as regards WEEE
- e. There is an absence of general awareness of the toxicity of WEEE.
- f. The weakness of the government to declare a complete “ban on importation of” used electrical & electronic equipment (UEEE) or formulate long-standing “guidelines” on used EEE imported into Nigeria, to equip the importers with the required information to differentiate used EEE and WEEE.
- g. The loading together of WEEE, “near EoL EEE”, and second-hand vehicles.
- h. There is an absence of localised statistics on WEEE.

3.1.2 The need to reduce or stop the activities of informal recyclers in Port Harcourt

Lenz et al (2019, P. 25), individuals who carry out WEEE “treatment” usually expose themselves to “hazardous substances” via soil, food, dust, and water. This is capable of endangering their life. Alabi and Wohlmuth (2019), informal recyclers lack awareness of the associated risks with informal recycling and this gives rise to several health challenges such as brain and liver damage, skin irritation, decreased nerve conduction velocity, brain swelling, etc. Wideman (2019, p. 29), the various challenges associated with WEEE management “are man-made, and need man-initiated, man-volunteered solutions”. In terms of competency, Ogbuanya and Afeez (2019, p. 93), put forward that informal recyclers lack the right skills, and they have little or no exposure to state-of-the-art “technology, and personal protective equipment among others”. Informal recyclers usually referred to as scavengers, according to Popoola et al (2019, p. 5), do not like participating in a study involving WEEE management voluntarily, due to “the illegal status of their operation”. Some of the activities associated with WEEE recycling, for example, “dismantling of electrical devices” as mentioned in Osaretin (2018) expose recyclers to injuries. Herat (2018, p. 39), the services of “informal recycling” are carried out by individuals who are usually poor, hence, the government cannot ask them to pay heavy taxes since they won’t be able to afford it.

The study carried out by Alabi and Wohlmuth (2019), shows that despite the efforts made by informal recyclers to manage WEEE, they do not get any form of intervention or support from the government and private sector to create a conducive environment. Some of the discouragements are:

- i. They do not get any form of financial aid or recognition from the government.
- ii. Their activities and efforts are not supported with “basic amenities.”
- iii. No form of safety gadgets is provided to them to prevent them from exposure to health-related risks and “hazardous materials”.
- iv. They lack the opportunity for training on “environmental conditions”, finance, technologies, kinds of waste, and materials.
- v. No opportunity for “adequate medical facilities”.
- vi. No formal education, orientation, or training on the application of “first-aid treatment” in times of emergency.

WEEE contains several elements that are harmful to life and the environment which are usually not properly managed by the informal recycler. Some of those elements/substances, their

sources, and harmful effects on life and the environment, according to Ilankoon et al (2018, p. 266) and Lenz et al (2019) are shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Element/substance in WEEE, their sources, harmful effects, source of exposure, and their routes to exposure.

Element/substance	Sources of element/substance	Harmful effects of element/substance	Source of exposure	Route to exposure
Beryllium (Be)	Parts of electronics made of ceramic, X-ray machines, computers, and power supply boxes.	It may cause acute beryllium disease or beryllium sensitization. It attacks vital parts of the body, such as the lymphatic system, nervous system, heart, kidneys, and liver.	Water, food, and air	Ingestion, transplacental, and inhalation
Zinc, (Zn)	Batteries, coatings of metal, Cathode ray tubes	It results in a heightened “risk of copper” shortage which can result in “neurological abnormalities “as well as anaemia.	Soil, water, and air	Inhalation and ingestion
Barium (Ba)	Fluorescent lamps, cathode ray tubes (which usually comprise 2 – 9 percent of Ba)	It causes an elevation in blood pressure, twitching of muscles, paralysis, gastrointestinal disorder, respiratory failure, cardiac arrhythmias, and low potassium content in the blood.	Dermal contact, ingestion, and inhalation	Dermal contact, ingestion, and inhalation
PVC	Cables and wire insulation	Furans and chlorinated dioxins are produced during PVC incineration. Their effects on the environment are persistent when produced, they are harmful even when it is of low concentration.		
Lithium (Li)	It is present in Lithium batteries	It causes daze feeling, fatigue, weakness of the muscles, dizziness, diarrhoea, and nausea.	Food (plant), water, soil, and air	Dermal contact, ingestion, and inhalation
Persistent organic pollutants (POPs), this also includes brominated flame retardants	They are found in devices e.g. Mobile phones, and connectors. They are also present in electric motors, dishwashers, ceiling fans, fluorescent lights, generator coolants, lubricants, as “dielectric fluids in transformers and capacitors, as casings for cables and	The womb’s exposure to POPs is recently linked to behavioural challenges, it “interferes with thyroid and oestrogen hormone system”. Memory and learning activities are usually impaired after a long period of exposure, it is extremely “resistant to breakdown”	Soil, water, food, duct, and air	Transplacental, inhalation, and ingestion

	computers. They are also found in circuit boards.			
Lead (Pb)	Lamps, light bulbs, printed circuit boards (PCBs), monitors of personal computers, Television, CRTs (made of 4 – 22 percent Pb), and batteries.	It causes kidney damage, anaemia, severe neurotoxicity, and “intellectual impairment in children”. It also causes damage to the blood, reproductive, and nervous systems, especially in adults.	Soil. Water, dust, and air	Ingestion, dermal contact, and inhalation
Nickel (Ni)	“Electron gun” in cathode ray tubes, batteries made of Ni-Cd	It increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases, high blood pressure, cancer of the lungs, developmental deficit during childhood stage, and neurological deficits	Food (plant), water, soil, and air	Transplacental, dermal contact, inhalation, and ingestion.
Mercury (Hg)	Monitors, sensors, thermostats, “lighting devices for flat screen displays”, PCBs, CRTs	It causes damage to the central nervous system and brain, “neurobehavioral development” in children. Conversely, it also causes kidney damage, anaemia, and severe neurotoxicity.	Food (bioaccumulative in fish), soil, water, vapour, and air	Dermal contact, ingestion, and inhalation
Chromium (Cr)/hexavalent chromium	“Production of metal housings (anti-corrosion coatings), data tapes, floppy disks”	It is extremely toxic; it has effects on neonates, endocrine, and reproductive functions	Soil, water, dust, and air	Ingestion and inhalation
Cadmium (Cd)	Mobile phones, CRTs, switches, connectors, springs, batteries, “older” printed circuit boards (PCBs), CRTs, infrared detectors, toner or ink copiers, semi-conductor chips	It affects bones and kidneys; it causes damage to the lungs as well as the reproductive system. It is extremely toxic and extremely resistant to breakdown.	Food (particularly rice and vegetables), water, soil, dust, and air	Inhalation and ingestion

As stated this study sheds light on the consequences of informal recycling in the MTN phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers), Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, and other locations affected by similar challenges. The level of education, health, and safety awareness of the informal recyclers, their willingness to obey government guidelines, and their knowledge of WEEE management were investigated. Data gathering was achieved with the help of questionnaires administered to informal recyclers in the study location. The study was carried out in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt Nigeria in August 2020.

3.2 Materials and Methods

The methodical concept used for this study is based on reviews of past works of literature on problems associated with informal recycling, WEEE management strategies, and the outcome of questionnaires administered to informal recyclers in MTN phone village at Rumukurushi in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The survey strategy was adopted in this study since it is usually associated with “deductive research approach” (Rahi, 2017, p. 2). The questionnaires were used for data collection because the study requires quantifiable data that exist in a manner that is numeric (Queirós, Almeida and Faria, 2017). The positivist research philosophy was adopted since it required quantitative data collection (Rahi, 2017). Survey research is a frequently used approach for gathering quantitative data from a sample of individuals or groups to understand their behaviours, attitudes, opinions, or characteristics on a specific topic of interest (Mohajan, 2020). Questionnaires allow researchers to efficiently gather data from a large number of respondents, making findings generalizable to a broader population (Stantcheva, 2023). Survey instruments can be standardised to ensure data consistency and allow for comparisons across various respondents or groups (Aithal and Aithal, 2020). The study adopted the survey method of data collection for the purpose of efficiency. Surveys enable researchers to acquire data from an immense number of respondents in an effective manner. Researchers may collect data from several individuals or groups at the same time using standardised questionnaires, which saves time and resources when compared to other alternative data-gathering approaches (Brant *et al.*, 2015).

A qualitative research approach was adopted, as data were gathered with the help of questionnaires (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). The analysis of the questionnaires was achieved using graphical methods. This study adopted the questionnaire method for the purpose of confidentiality and anonymity. Surveys offer respondents some levels of confidentiality

and anonymity, allowing them to deliver unbiased and honest replies, especially to personal or sensitive issues. This anonymity encourages more openness and candour in participants' responses, which improves the validity of the data obtained (Kang and Hwang, 2022). The survey strategy of data collection was adopted by the study due to its flexibility in administration. In terms of administration, the survey strategy offers flexibility such as face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, online surveys, face-to-face interviews, or mailed questionnaires. This versatility enables researchers to reach out to a wide range of people while also accommodating participants' preferences or accessibility concerns (Okonkwo and Emeka, 2018; Seff *et al.*, 2021). Several responses were gathered from the participants on many issues that bother WEEE management, and the results were analysed graphically.

The study data was evaluated based on the quality and trustworthiness of the sources from which it was collected. This involves determining if the data were obtained from credible sources using reliable procedures. In this study, data collection was obtained on waste electrical and electronic equipment recycling at MTN Phone Village through the use of questionnaires. Assessing the accuracy and credibility of various data sources is critical in justifying the assessment of the data (Chen *et al.*, 2014). Quantitative analysis is based on statistical methods and numerical data, which can mitigate the impact of subjective biases. Researchers can improve objectivity by employing standardized data collection and analysis techniques, reducing the effect of personal opinions or interpretations on the results. This improves the validity of the findings by ensuring that they are based on empirical evidence instead of subjective opinions (Dehalwar and Sharma, 2023).

3.2.1 Study site

MTN phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers) in the city of Port Harcourt in Rivers State, Nigeria was the chosen site for this study. This is because of the extent of WEEE disposal in the location, the challenges faced by residents due to poor WEEE management system in practice, and the activities of the informal recyclers which exposed the life of the residents and the surrounding environment to risk. It is a very small location in Port Harcourt. Conversely, Port Harcourt formerly referred to as Rivers State Garden City several years ago is currently faced with the challenges of WEEE management (Okoli *et al.*, 2020). Waste in this part of the country is not properly managed and

forms part of the environmental challenges, the pathogens present in the waste are mainly carried by scavengers (Amadi and Chijioke, 2018).

3.2.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaires comprise of items shown below:

- Demographic information.
- Responses on waste electrical & electronics equipment awareness and behaviour towards good sustainable practice.
- Responses on waste electrical and electronic equipment, health, safety, and environmental issues

3.2.3 Demographic information

This covers several key information on the participants, and this includes their state of origin, gender, age, educational qualification, and years of working experience in the informal recycling business.

a. The state of origin of the participants

The respondents in this study are residents of the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria who do the business of informal WEEE recycling. The participants were drawn from the MTN phone village at Rumukurushi in the city of Port Harcourt. This is because the MTN phone village in the city of Port Harcourt in Rivers State, Nigeria was chosen as the research location for the study. Hence, gathering valuable information from individuals in the selected location will offer the study a better position to know the exact situation of things in the area.

b. The gender of the participants.

In this study, an effort was made to gather responses from both men and women involved in the informal WEEE recycling business. Out of the twenty-five (25) participants who took part in the study, only three (3) ladies were involved. This accounts for 12% of the population while the remaining 88% are men.

c. The age of the participants

The respondents were grouped into various age categories as shown in table 3.2.

Table 3.2. The age category of the participants

Age category of participants	Men	Ladies	Number of participants
Under 20	1	0	1
21 – 25	3	1	4
26 – 35	4	2	6
36 - 40	5	0	5
41 – 50	8	0	8
50 and above	1	0	1

d. Educational qualification of the participants

The result gathered from the study shows that twenty-three (23) participants (which accounts for 92%) attended only primary school while the remaining two, 2 (i.e. 8%) attended high school.

e. Years of working experience in the informal recycling business of WEEE.

The number of years of working experience in WEEE management achieved by each of the participants was taken into consideration in this study. Details of the years of working experience of the informal recyclers are shown in Table 3.3

Table 3.3 Number of years of working experience of the participants

Working experience (years)	Number of participants
1	1
2	2
3	2
4	6
5 and above	14

3.3 Results and discussion

To gather information on the level of awareness of the informal recycler on waste electrical & electronics equipment, and their behaviour towards good sustainable practice, some questions were asked. This includes the main reason the informal recyclers engage in WEEE management. Knowledge of the level of awareness is essential. This is because several environmental hazards are caused by informal WEEE dumping, and these are water pollution, land pollution, increase in disease vectors, air pollution, etc. It is also essential to ascertain the extent of awareness as informal recyclers are faced with the following health risks:

long-term cumulative poisoning, reproductive system damage, liver and brain damage, peripheral and central nervous system damage, etc.

According to this study, informal recyclers have several reasons for engaging in WEEE management. The numerous reasons are classified into four (4) different categories namely: no job availability, zero tax payment, extra income generation, and others as shown in Figure 3.1. Out of 25 participants who responded, 64% of the participants, which appears to be the majority, admitted that the main reason they engage in WEEE management is that, there is no job availability.

Figure 3.1 A plot of individuals’ engagement in WEEE management against the reason for engagement

To ascertain the frequency at which WEEE, and its associated components, are dismantled and disposed of on the site by informal recyclers, several questions were put forward to them. As regards the question, whether WEEE is frequently dismantled or disposed of on the site. Those who agreed with the idea amount to 48%, those who strongly agreed amount to 32%, while those who are unsure amount to 8%. On the other hand, 4% disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed. The proportion of respondents who are in support of the idea that WEEE is frequently dismantled and disposed of on the site outweighs those who are not in support. The frequency at which the refrigerator, electrical cables, and electronic circuit boards are dismantled and disposed of on-site was also investigated. Find details in Figure 3.2. As regards the refrigerator, 8% of the respondents disagreed that the refrigerator is frequently dismantled and disposed of on the site without the use of PPE. 8% strongly disagree, those who are unsure recorded 4% while 40% agreed, the remaining 40% strongly agreed. In JK et al (2017) and Touni (2019), “large household devices like refrigerators can be a potential source of

chemicals, for example, hydrochlorofluorocarbons, which serves as a threat to the informal recycler whose job is to dismantle refrigerators.

Dismantling of refrigerators must be carried out using the appropriate guidelines as it contains refrigerants such as CFC-12, HCFC-22, HFC-410A, and HFC-32, ammonia solution containing chromium-VI, critical blowing agents such as CFC-11, HCFC-141b. Conversely, it contains mercury, printed circuit boards (containing Lead, Cadmium, Hexavalent chromium), etc (Lenz *et al.*, 2019). As regards the frequency at which electrical cables are frequently disposed of or burnt on the site. 4% of the respondents are not sure if electrical cables are frequently disposed of or burnt on the site. Conversely, 4% and 8% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively, while 36% agreed and 48% strongly agreed.

An effort made to ascertain if electronic circuit boards are frequently disposed of or burnt on the site produced the following result. Respondents who strongly disagreed, disagreed and were unsure recorded 4% each. 44% agreed and 44% also strongly agreed. This shows that those in support of disposing of or burning electronic circuit boards on the site outweigh those who are against it. JK et al (2017) and Cesaro et al (2019), put forward that, the burning of WEEE to recover some valuable elements from electronic circuit boards usually provides an avenue for toxic chemicals, to be released into the environment. Hence, the practice needs to be discouraged.

Figure 3.2 A plot of the frequent dismantling of WEEE or WEEE components against participants' responses

A conscious effort was also made via the questionnaires to understand what the informal recyclers understand as WEEE management, hence several definitions of WEEE management were offered in the questionnaires. The outcome of the various interpretations of WEEE management gathered are shown in Figure 3.3. As regards the first idea, WEEE management implies throwing WEEE into an open dump. 16% of the participants each disagreed and strongly disagreed with the definition. Those who were unsure recorded 8% while 20% and 40% agreed and strongly agreed respectively.

As regards the second idea, WEEE management means the burning of WEEE. 12% and 8% of the participants disagreed and strongly disagreed with the definition respectively. Those who are unsure recorded 4% while 40% and 36% agreed and strongly agreed. Another idea suggested was that WEEE management means keeping WEEE in the storerooms. 20% of the participants each disagreed and strongly disagreed with the definition. Those who are unsure recorded 8%, 24% agreed while the remaining 28% strongly agreed. In one of the definitions offered, WEEE management means sorting, dismantling, processing, treatment, and recovery of valuable elements before disposal of the unwanted parts in a manner that allows for the safety of life and the environment. 24% of the participants strongly disagreed with the definition. 28% disagreed, 8% were unsure while 20% each agreed and strongly agreed.

Conversely, the responses gathered from the definition, WEEE management means dumping WEEE in water show that 16% and 12% disagreed and strongly disagreed with the definition respectively. Those who are unsure recorded 4%, 36% agreed while the remaining 32% strongly agreed. Finally, 32% and 20% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively, with the definition that WEEE management means dumping WEEE on the road path. Those who were unsure recorded 8% while 20% each agreed and strongly agreed with the definition. The outcome shows that the definition that WEEE management means throwing WEEE into an open dump has the highest percentage of those who strongly agree with the definition. While the definition, WEEE management implies burning of WEEE recorded the highest percentage of participants who agreed with the idea. As regards the definition, which appears appropriate, 28% strongly disagreed. This implies that the exact definition of WEEE management is not clear to the informal recyclers.

Figure 3.3 A plot of the definition of WEEE against participants' responses

The administered questionnaires were also fashioned to help identify if the informal recyclers know about health & safety and if they appreciate the concept of safety in the discharge of their duties. In Figure 3.4, the question seeks to find out if personal safety is enhanced by applying control measures and wearing personal protective equipment (PPE) during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning, etc. The outcome shows that 8% of the participants strongly disagreed with the idea, and 24% disagreed. 40%, which appears to be the majority, was unsure. 16% agreed and 12% strongly agreed. This can be as a result of a low level of awareness of the use of PPE and the application of health & safety in the discharge of their WEEE-related duties.

Figure 3.4. A plot of personal safety is enhanced by applying control measures and wearing PPE during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning, etc., against participants' responses.

An effort was made as shown in Figure 3.5 to ascertain the willingness of informal recyclers to adhere to government guidelines in the discharge of their WEEE-related duties. The outcome signifies that 52% agreed, and 48% strongly agreed with no form of disagreement recorded. The informal recyclers declared their willingness to obey government guidelines in the discharge of their WEEE-related duties.

Figure 3.5. A plot of recyclers are willing to obey government guidelines during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning, etc., against participants' responses

The idea in Figure 3.6 was introduced into the questionnaires to ascertain the willingness of the informal recycler to partner with government agencies in the discharge of their WEEE-related activities. The outcome indicates that 4% of the participants strongly disagreed with the idea, and 8% disagreed. 48% agreed while 40% strongly agreed. The percentage of participants willing to partner with government agencies in the discharge of their WEEE management-related activities outweighs those who are not in support. This shows that the informal recyclers in the location are ready to work with government agencies in the discharge of their duties.

Figure 3.6. A plot of informal WEEE recyclers are willing to work with government agencies against participants' responses

Conversely, an effort was made in the questionnaires to ascertain the willingness of informal recyclers to get payment for WEEE gathering or collection while they quit other aspects of WEEE management such as treatment, burning, etc. The result shows that 4% strongly disagreed, and another 4% also disagreed. 52% agreed while 40% strongly agreed as shown in Figure 3.7 This shows that the percentage of informal recyclers that are willing to quit all other activities involved with the process of WEEE management if they can be paid by the government for the gathering and collection of WEEE, outweighs those who are against the idea.

Figure 3.7. A plot of if WEEE recyclers are paid for WEEE collection services, they are ready to quit other WEEE management activities such as treatment, burning, etc., against participants' responses

3.4 Criticism of the Study Concept

- One critique is that the concentration on a single site (the MTN phone village in Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria) may restrict the findings' generalizability. The circumstances, obstacles, and dynamics of informal WEEE recycling might vary greatly among different areas or nations. Critics might argue that broader research or comparative analyses covering several locations could offer a deeper understanding of the problem.

- While the word "menace" conveys a negative connotation, some critics may argue that informal WEEE recycling has some beneficial aspects. For example, it might give livelihood possibilities for underprivileged populations, aid in resource recovery and reuse, and address gaps in formal recycling infrastructure. Focusing primarily on the negative elements while ignoring potential advantages may result in an imbalanced perspective.
- Critics may argue that tackling informal WEEE recycling solely as a "menace" ignores the underlying socioeconomic issues that drive this informal sector. Poverty, a lack of formal job opportunities, ineffective waste management systems, and restricted access to education and training may all contribute to the growth of informal recycling initiatives. Ignoring these core problems could impede efforts to establish equitable and sustainable solutions.
- Another critical approach may be on environmental justice concerns surrounding informal WEEE recycling. Critics may raise concerns about the disproportionate environmental and health dangers posed by underprivileged groups engaged in informal recycling operations. They may argue for a more holistic strategy that incorporates fairness, community participation, and participatory decision-making in tackling environmental concerns associated with WEEE recycling.

3.5 Why is Everybody Not Using This Concept or Doing This If It Is So Good?

Everybody is not using this approach or doing this largely due to lack of awareness that this approach discovered in this study can help to tackle the numerous challenges associated with informal recycling. Other reasons why not everyone is using this approach are given below.

Many locations, particularly developing ones, rely heavily on the informal sector to manage waste. Informal recyclers frequently fill gaps created by insufficient formal recycling infrastructure, especially with regard to WEEE. They have the potential to recover valuable materials from electronic gadgets in an effective manner, hence aiding resource recovery and reuse (Gollakota, Gautam and Shu, 2020). Many underprivileged individuals and communities rely on informal WEEE recycling to make ends meet. It provides work to persons who may not have access to formal labour markets or who have no other source of income (Davis and Garb, 2015). Stopping informal recyclers abruptly without offering other livelihood opportunities may have negative socioeconomic consequences (Yu *et al.*, 2017). In certain circumstances,

the prevalence of informal recyclers is due to inadequate formal recycling policies or infrastructure (Tiwari, Mehra and Gauba Dhawan, 2023). Governments and agencies may not have developed appropriate mechanisms for collecting and recycling electronic waste, resulting in the emergence of the activities of informal recyclers to meet the demand for recycling services (Nnorom and Osibanjo, 2008).

Governments and regulatory agencies may suffer some challenges like lack of finance, shortage of the appropriate technology, and as well as capable workers. This limits their ability to effectively enforce legislation and supervise informal recycling. This makes it difficult to totally exclude informal recyclers from engaging in WEEE management (Nnorom and Odeyingbo, 2020). While informal recycling may have advantages, it also has severe environmental and health consequences. Informal recyclers frequently lack sufficient training, equipment, and safety precautions, exposing them to harmful substances and pollutants. Governments and stakeholders are aware of these concerns but may struggle to address them adequately owing to the obstacles (Ogechukwu Okwu *et al.*, 2022). Addressing the issue of informal WEEE recycling necessitates a multifaceted approach that combines economic, environmental, and social considerations. This includes creating formal recycling infrastructure, enacting effective regulations and enforcement mechanisms, assisting informal recyclers in transitioning to safer practices, increasing awareness about WEEE management, and encouraging appropriate production and consumption patterns (Nandan *et al.*, 2023).

3.6 The Cost of Restricting the Activities of Informal Recyclers in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

In the study, the total number of informal recyclers is 25. The daily cost of restricting the activities of informal recyclers/stipends in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria = N10,000

The daily cost of restricting the activities of twenty-five (25) informal recyclers/stipends in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria = N10,000 X 25 = N250,000

The cost of restricting the activities of twenty-five (25) informal recyclers/stipends in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria in 30 days (ie monthly cost) = N7500000.

By using the Oanda currency converter on 23 March 2024 as shown in Figure 3.8, N1 = 0.00056
N7500000 translates to £4165.5.

The monthly cost of restricting the activities of informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt is N7500000 (=£4165.5). Therefore, it will cost the government of Nigeria, N7500000 (=£4165.5) monthly to restrict the activities of informal recyclers in the location.

Figure 3.8. Oanda currency converter exchange rate as of 23rd March 2024

Conversely, the value of N7500000 in GBP using the Oanda currency converter exchange rate as of the 23rd of March 2024 is shown in Figure 3.9

Figure 3.9 The value of N7500000 in GBP using the Oanda currency converter exchange rate as of the 23rd March 2024.

3.7 Conclusion

This study explain more on the consequences of informal recycling in the MTN phone village at Rumukurushi (a location believed to accommodate about 30 informal recyclers), Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, and other locations affected by similar challenges. The level of education, health, and safety awareness of the informal recyclers, their willingness to obey government guidelines, and their knowledge of WEEE management were investigated. The informal recyclers in the location were found to be more conversant with their usual primitive style of practice. They lack knowledge and awareness of WEEE management best practices. Notable among the findings is that the informal recyclers in the research location:

- Lacks awareness of the use of PPE and the application of health & safety in the discharge of their WEEE activities. 40% of the participants were unsure of the use of PPE to enhance personal safety during the discharge of their duties. 8% strongly disagreed with the use of PPE to enhance personal safety. 24% also disagreed with the use of PPE to enhance personal safety. The remaining fraction supported the use.

- Are willing to obey government guidelines in the discharge of their WEEE activities as only 4% and 8% strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. 48% agreed while 40% strongly agreed to obey government guidelines in the discharge of their WEEE activities.
- Are willing to quit all other activities involved with the process of WEEE management if they can be paid by the government for the gathering or collection of WEEE. This is because the percentage of the participants who strongly disagreed and disagreed amounted to 4% each. On the other hand, 52% agreed while the remaining 40% strongly agreed.

Finally, the study recommends that the activities of the informal recyclers in the research location, and other locations faced with similar challenges, need to be restricted to WEEE gathering or collection only while the other services are handled by government-trained and approved individuals. To ensure the safety of informal recyclers, the study recommends that the government should organise sensitization workshops and training regularly for informal recyclers. This is to increase their level of awareness of the dangers associated with their business and the importance of the use of PPE.

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Chapter 4:

New models to reduce the health risks of informal WEEE recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

The material in this chapter has been published as “New models to reduce the health risks of informal WEEE recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria” (Okwu *et al.*, 2022).

The connection between the paper "New models to reduce the health risks of informal WEEE recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria" and MDPI's *Toxics* Journal, lies in the fact that *Toxics* is a peer-reviewed scientific Journal that publishes topics in areas related to chemical safety, environmental health, and toxicology. The journal publishes research reviews, communications, and articles that focus on the impact of toxic substances on the environment and human health. Given the title of the paper, it addresses health risks associated with informal waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) recycling, especially in the MTN phone village in Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The paper may examine new models or techniques targeted at lowering the health hazards of informal WEEE recyclers, mainly via technological innovations, policies and interventions are all possible options.

The connection between the paper and the *Toxics* journal can be established via the scope of the Journal, which involves studies on mitigation strategies, exposure modelling, risk assessment, health hazards, and environmental toxins. Publishing the work in a journal such as *Toxics* demonstrates that the research is significant to the field of risk assessment, environmental health, and toxicology. It also implies that the publication was peer-reviewed by specialists in the field to guarantee scientific rigor, accuracy of information, and contribution to improving knowledge in the area of health hazards associated with informal WEEE recycling.

The work is relevant to the *Toxics* journal since the journal's focus covers research on environmental toxins, health risks, risk assessment, exposure modeling, and toxic chemical mitigation measures. Since the paper deals with health risks associated

with informal WEEE recycling, which may include exposure to hazardous chemicals and materials. It aligns with the primary focus of the *Toxics Journal*. The publication of the work in a Journal such as *Toxics* demonstrates that the research is significant to the field of risk assessment, environmental health, and toxicology. It also implies that the publication was peer-reviewed by professionals in the field to guarantee scientific rigor, accuracy of information, and contribution to improving knowledge in the area of health hazards.

Port-Harcourt, an oil-producing city in Nigeria, experiences a massive number of individuals arriving in search of financial benefits from the oil and gas industries. Because of this ever-rising number of inhabitants, there is an increase in the consumption of materials as well as the generation of waste electronic and electrical equipment (WEEE) and other environmental contaminants. The quantity of WEEE produced has been steadily increasing (Konya, Babatunde and Iniefe, 2015). Furthermore, according to the same study, this is largely a result of the increasing need for information and communications technology as well as enhanced technology in some parts of the world, resulting in the dumping of “old and discarded” electronic and electrical equipment to countries such as Nigeria, where such items are still useful. These items are usually obsolete or close to obsolescence before they are transported to poor nations, which tends to increase the quantity of generated WEEE.

According to Kalamaras *et al.* (2021), WEEE, which is among the biggest and constantly increasing streams of global waste, has become an issue of serious concern due to its associated challenges. The problem created by WEEE appears to be twofold. First and foremost, it is among the most rapidly increasing waste streams globally, presenting a potential threat to humans, animals, and the environment as a result of its mismanagement. Secondly, as a result of its composition, which is complex, WEEE is also one of the most difficult waste streams to manage effectively (Danz *et al.*, 2019)

This chapter deals with the need to eliminate or reduce the role of recyclers in the informal sector, in particular, to reduce health risks associated with the management of WEEE in Rumukurushi, in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. This applies to similar situations in other cities. WEEE recycling is predominantly managed by informal recyclers, who lack the skills to perform risk-free recycling. Hence raising health risks to individuals in associated communities and degrading the environment. Areas covered in this section of the thesis are

the outcome of the survey questionnaires administered to participants for the study, past works of literature in the area of specialisation as well as the details of the newly introduced concept for the management of WEEE by informal recyclers, which limits their activities or service to WEEE collection only.

4.1. Literature survey

In Port Harcourt, a city in the south–south geopolitical zone of Nigeria, the WEEE collectors do not practice formal recycling methods. The system in practice is the informal recycling method, carried out primarily at the dumpsite, where they engage in the sorting of WEEE as well as further recycling (Amadi and Chijioke, 2018). This begs the following question: how can we tackle the challenges associated with informal recycling? Ohajinwa et al. (2017), put forward the notion that informal recyclers engage in several activities, which include the recycling of WEEE. Their services are usually provided at a low cost, but the working procedure used is not safe; hence, their health is at risk from exposure to substances within the materials and from the operations used in recycling, such as burning to remove plastics. In a related study by Amadi and Chijioke (2018), WEEE and other waste are usually gathered unsorted at locations in Port Harcourt, such as Igwuruta, Elemenwo, and Abuloma. WEEE serves as a source of raw materials, but during the informal recycling process, the estimated recovery of useful metals is only 25% (Leung *et al.*, 2008; Starovoytova, 2018).

Study on WEEE generation by Mihai et al. (2019), state that growing waste stream and its inappropriate handling generate serious pollution and health-related challenges. This can result from the dismantling of WEEE being carried out under “poor conditions”. The dumping of WEEE in Africa has been significant for a long period, and its recycling is usually carried out by poorly educated individuals, under temporary conditions, with no infrastructure, which leads to exposure to harmful substances. Due to a lack of organised collection centres in Nigeria, WEEE is dumped together with waste from hospitals and other sources in the community, which causes the situation to be more complex. In some communities WEEE is dumped in bodies of water and on open fields, resulting in direct environmental pollution. Items considered to be of no use economically are usually burnt regularly to reduce their quantity or directly deposited on open fields or in water bodies. The indiscriminate discarding of WEEE has resulted in an increase in polybrominated diphenyl ether and polychlorinated biphenyl concentration in individuals. Fluorinated biphenyls and analogues are also toxic pollutants

emitted due to the indiscriminate dumping of WEEE (Awere *et al.*, 2020; Bimir, 2020; Bi *et al.*, 2007; Kitila and Woldemikael, 2019; Mihai and Gnoni, 2017; Zhu *et al.*, 2021).

Electronic appliances such as televisions and computer monitors contain potentially harmful elements and compounds, which are evident during disposal or recycling. The majority of those who make use of them are not aware of the associated risks of using them frequently (Needhidasan, Samuel and Chidambaram, 2014). The landfills, as well as unauthorised dumpsites, appear to be the terminal point of the majority of the gathered WEEE (Forti *et al.*, 2020). Harmful gases are usually released into the environment during the burning of WEEE (Kitila and Woldemikael, 2019; Mostafa and Sarhan, 2018). The disposal and recycling of cathode ray tubes (CRTs) have the potential to expose life to health risks due to the presence of lead in CRT funnel glass (at levels up to 22%). In addition to lead, CRTs consist of fluorescent powders, barium, and cadmium, all of which are toxic. The harmful elements contained in CRTs are easily absorbed in the soil over time and are consequently passed to humans and animals (Ciftci and Cicek, 2017; Lecler *et al.*, 2015; Ledwaba and Sosibo, 2017; Xu *et al.*, 2016).

The presence of devices that contain mercury causes soil pollution and contributes to increased health risks. Mercury is more poisonous than lead and cadmium, and it causes loss of hearing and vision as well as developmental delays (Ali and Al-Qahtani, 2012; Ismičić-Tanjo *et al.*, 2021; Natasha *et al.*, 2020). The tissue and surface of locally grown fresh vegetables can easily become contaminated when exposed to residues from waste processing directly deposited on fields and in water. Skin contact and drinking water have also been recognised as significant routes of exposure to toxic substances (Ahen and Amankwah-Amoah, 2021; Gebeyehu and Bayissa, 2020; Zhou *et al.*, 2016). Unprofessional WEEE burning and dismantling methods contribute significantly to the pollution of air. This can result in secondary exposure, as some of the pollutants are able to travel over a long distance to other locations from the recycling sites (Attia, Soori and Ghaith, 2021).

The soil, as well as the crops grown in the WEEE dumpsites, are usually exposed to a high concentration of metals, such as lead, zinc, copper, etc. The accumulation and uptake of them by plants constitute the major entry channel for metals, which are toxic in animal and human food. Examples of such toxic metals are metalloids such as lead, mercury, cadmium, selenium, and arsenic. Crops that grow in metal-polluted locations usually show a reduction in growth,

reduced biomass production, accumulation of metal, and alteration of metabolism. It is common practice for locals to grow crops around and within WEEE dumpsite areas, as they believe the land is fertile and that crops will grow well. Research has demonstrated that many locations contain high levels of potentially toxic elements (Clemens, 2006; Nagajyoti, Lee and Sreekanth, 2010; Omorogieva and Tonjoh, 2020; Sagbara *et al.*, 2020). The pollutants in WEEE migrate towards biological and environmental receptors via several pathways according to Marinello and Gamberini (2021), the channels are shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Channels pollutants in WEEE migrate to biological and environmental receptors.

Research conducted by George, Mapa, and Dinggai (2019), the increasing quantity of WEEE is shown to be associated with several factors, which include technological improvement, the availability of assorted electronic and electrical devices for sale, the reduction in prices of electronic and electrical devices, and the growing population, fuelling an

extremely “high demand” for them. WEEE is a potential source of rare metals and useful plastics, helpful in reducing the pressure on mineral resources, the exploitation of natural resources, as well as the environmental and cost implications of mining. Several methods have been adopted to extract metals. For example, studies have shown that the copper present in printed circuit boards (PCBs) can be extracted with the use of a mixture of aqueous acid and supercritical CO₂. Studies have also shown that rare earth elements can be recovered via electrochemical recovery. Important metals, such as copper, silver, and gold, were recovered from the printed circuit boards of computers that were no longer in use via physical separation, after which a leaching technique was applied. In addition, copper can be directly separated and recovered from waste PCBs via slurry electrolysis carried out with an acidic system. Product designs that are environmentally friendly have been encouraged in the European Union via legislation to support the recovery of valuable materials from WEEE (Hossain *et al.*, 2019; Hsu *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2019; Tanisalı, Özer and Burat, 2020; Wang, Zhang and Guan, 2016; Wang *et al.*, 2021; Zhang, Schnoor and Zeng, 2012).

Cole *et al.* (2019), “the recovery and treatment of WEEE” serve as an alternative source of important elements, for example, copper, gold, etc. However, the indiscriminate disposal of WEEE and the challenges that come with the inappropriate disassembling and management of WEEE, observed in many developing countries, put pressure on the environment and human health (Ferronato and Torretta, 2019). An assessment by Khan *et al.* (2014), indicates that most of the WEEE that is globally generated, amounting to at least 40 million tonnes per year, finds its way to developing countries. Nigeria now appears as one of the locations receiving WEEE from Asia, the US, and Europe (Lawal, 2019). A study by Ferronato and Torretta (2019), put forward the notion that developed countries have seen the export of WEEE to Asia and Africa as a preferred option compared to developing their own national recycling infrastructure, encouraging innovative design that limits toxic material use, or switching to cleaner sustainable technologies.

Adeola (2018), it was observed that the amount of WEEE generated worldwide amounted to approximately “50 million metric tonnes” in 2018. WEEE production is the direct consequence of the manufacturing and use of electronic devices driven by the multipurpose nature of information and communications technologies (ICTs). This increased consumption

and the comparatively short life of electronics result in a build-up of WEEE, which poses problems at all levels. The hazardous materials in WEEE pose problems for the government in terms of their management Wilson *et al.* (2015), and their effect on the environment (Dagiliūtė *et al.*, 2019). The estimated quantity of WEEE produced worldwide in 2018 increased to 49.8 metric tons. The major generators of WEEE as of 2014 identified in the same study by Adeola (2018), and of 2016 by Tiseo (2018), are shown in Table 4.1 and Figure 4.2, respectively. The statistics show that the United States tops the list in WEEE generated in 2014, while China tops the list in WEEE generated in 2016.

Table 4.1 Top ten global generators of WEEE, in total mass, and per capita, and the presence of national regulations, 2014.

SN	Country	Mass (kilo tons)	National regulation	Per capita (tons)
1	US	7072	No	22.1
2	China	6033	Yes	4.4
3	Japan	2200	Yes	17.3
4	Germany	1769	Yes	21.6
5	India	1641	No	1.3
6	UK	1511	Yes	23.5
7	France	1419	Yes	22.1
8	Brazil	1412	No	7.0
9	Russia	1231	No	8.7
10	Italy	1077	Yes	17.6

Figure 4.2 Global generation of WEEE in 2016.

The generation of WEEE and its collection in different continents is identified in Baldé et al. (2017) and is summarised in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 The generators of WEEE and its collection per continent.

Indicators	Oceania	Europe	Asia	America	Africa
Countries within the region	13	40	49	35	53
Population within the region (millions)	39	738	4364	977	1174
Water gauge, WG (kg/inh)	17.3	16.6	4.2	11.6	1.9
Indication WG (Mt)	0.7	12.3	18.2	11.3	2.2
WEEE documented to be collected and recycled (Mt)	0.04	4.3	2.7	1.9	0.004
Rate of WEEE collection within the region	6%	35%	15%	17%	0%

Baldé et al. (2017), reported that in the year 2016, the bulk of WEEE gathered in Asia, which amounts to 18.2 million metric tons (Mt) (i.e., 4.2 kg/inhabitant), only about 2.7 Mt was recorded for collection and will be recycled. Oceania produced the highest amount, 17.3 kg/inhabitant, and had only a 6% rate of collection and recycling; however, it appears to produce the smallest amount of WEEE in 2016: 0.7 Mt. The statistics for Europe, Asia, the Americas, and Africa are also shown in Table 4.2. These statistics imply that a large proportion of the WEEE that is collected and recycled is not documented. The focus of this segment of the dissertation is on the need to eliminate or reduce the role of recyclers in the informal sector to reduce health risks from the management of WEEE in Rumukurushi, in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. This applies to similar situations in other cities.

4.1.1. A Review of past works of literature on WEEE Management

Several studies have focused on improving the informal management of WEEE. Ogbuanya and Afeez (2019, p. 90), propose that the WEEE approaches applied in the workshops of “electrical/electronic technicians” can be advanced. Data collection was performed using questionnaires administered to 54 “public health” senior staff as well as 87 engineering lecturers. The data analysis was achieved using “percentage, mean, and standard deviation white t-test and ANOVA”. The study findings reveal that providing a “recycling site” as well as introducing and applying regulatory policies are the major approaches required for more effective management of WEEE. However, the study did not directly address the challenges associated with informal recycling but only attempted to identify indicators that may be of help. A study on effective methods that can help to proffer solutions for WEEE management will be valuable.

Arya, Gupta, and Bhardwaj (2018), investigate the degree of understanding of informal recyclers and users (individuals, organisations, and companies) regarding the hazards created by WEEE. The study collected data via questionnaires administered to three different WEEE stakeholder groups, namely organisations, individuals, and those who use WEEE recycling services. The composition of those who responded to the questionnaires was 10 persons engaged in WEEE recycling, 25 users of electrical and electronic appliances, and 35 organisations considered as users. The study outcomes revealed that the individuals and organisational users lack an understanding of the problems associated with WEEE management. This includes legislation for WEEE management and proper channels for the collection of WEEE. Recyclers in the informal sector were not aware of the risks associated with WEEE and subsequently engaged in unsafe disposal methods. The study did not address the challenges associated with informal recycling, because it primarily focused on the degree of understanding of the informal recyclers and users. The study identified health and safety training as an avenue to increase awareness.

George, Mapa, and Dinggai (2019), studied WEEE management with households as their focus, using an assessment of the electrical and electronic device composition in the apartments of the people in the area of study as well as the way in which WEEE was managed. Data collection for the study was achieved using questionnaires. The study outcomes revealed that the electronic and electrical appliances that appear the most in the area are phones. Furthermore, the study revealed that the selected area adopted an unsustainable system of managing WEEE. Study participants did not recycle WEEE, but simply kept them inside their homes or deposited them directly into the general waste stream. The study did not address the challenges associated with informal recycling because no evaluation was conducted on the activities of informal recyclers; instead, recommendations were offered. Introducing an approach with the potential to provide an effective recycling solution may be helpful in the informal sector.

Ndunda and Ambole (2018, p. 73), tackled the problems introduced by the informal method of WEEE recycling via the creation of “a product-service system” for its management. Supporters of a move, from product provision to “provision of systems of products and services” were

developed alongside stakeholders' support, for WEEE to be managed efficiently. Dematerialization technique was applied in the study by making use of the effort of stakeholders' collaboration, this hinders the informal recyclers or consumers from having possession of equipment after EOL. The outcome indicates that the collaborative efforts of those involved determine the success of the technique. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study was unable to address the problem because dematerialisation can only be attained through structural and technological changes in the area, which have yet to be implemented. Adopting an approach applicable to developing nations will be more useful.

Aidonis et al. (2019), a methodology was created to recognise an optimal management scheme to find another means of integrating WEEE. The study made use of a binary linear programming model to improve the effectiveness of nine options to manage WEEE. Consideration was given to 12 performance criteria, including environmental, financial, social, and technical considerations. The study outcome revealed that the best approaches were exporting WEEE residue and mechanically recycling WEEE. The outcome did not address the issues associated with informal recycling because the technique proposed does not have the potential to tackle the negative repercussions of informal recycling. A technique that has the potential to minimise informal recycling may be more useful.

Mihai et al. (2019), statistical information on waste and "thematic cartography" was used to disclose how WEEE moves from one geographical location to another. The approaches utilised to manage WEEE in numerous locations were examined, for instance, in Europe, North America, South America, Oceania, Africa, etc. The findings indicate that inadequate infrastructure leads to the poor management of WEEE in Africa. The findings did not address the issues associated with informal recycling, as the study focused on elements of the improper management of WEEE. Identifying a useful method that can tackle the challenges facing recycling in the informal sector may be helpful.

4.1.2. Research Gap

It is therefore clear that no major improvements have been achieved to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in Nigeria and other developing countries where WEEE management is predominantly managed by the informal sector. Our study addresses this issue by assessing

models for the continued participation of recyclers in the informal sector in the collection of WEEE only, while the e government agencies will handle the sensitive processes.

4.1.3. WEEE Status in Nigeria

Goel (2019, p. 8), reports that, as a result of the lack of proper waste management infrastructure and systems in Nigeria, the dumping of WEEE is usually carried out “alongside other municipal waste”; hence, the level of health and environmental risk awareness is “generally low”. The same study explains that the lack of appropriate mechanisms in Nigeria for WEEE “disposal” contributes immensely to the poor knowledge of WEEE disposal and the associated health risks. The inadequate rules and regulations, as well as the poor implementation of laws on sanitation, have created an enabling environment for informal recycling in some parts of Nigeria (Okorhi, Joe and Aderemi, 2014). The task performed by informal WEEE recyclers is significant and includes the collection of WEEE from streets for recovery, recycling, sorting, and disposal (Alabi and Wohlmuth, 2019). The job of the informal recycler entails material isolation, dismantling via the use of manual techniques, circuit board heating, the recovery of metal using poisonous acid, and disposal at an open dump (Ohajinwa *et al.*, 2017).

Informal recyclers also referred to as “scavengers”, usually lack formal skills and are unregistered (Okorhi *et al.*, 2017). A total of 277,000 tonnes of WEEE was generated in Nigeria in 2016. This puts Nigeria in the third position in the hierarchy of WEEE generators on the African continent, with the amount of WEEE expected to increase. No non-governmental or institutional organisation collects or updates data on WEEE, which can serve as a source of valuable information to support policymaking or government action. In addition, a large quantity of WEEE enters the country “from abroad” (Baldé *et al.*, 2017; Goel, 2019). Some locations in Nigeria, such as Lagos, stockpile WEEE, awaiting the provision of a means to recycle it (Lawal, 2019). The challenges associated with the management of WEEE in Nigeria and other developing countries are further amplified due to the absence of comprehensive and reliable data (Borthakur and Sinha, 2013; Ilankoon *et al.*, 2018).

The problems associated with WEEE management in Africa are well-known, but it still lacks the appropriate infrastructure, evidenced by the absence of appropriate regulatory protocols and enforcement (Wideman, 2019). In the informal sector, WEEE is recycled improperly, and the process exposes the community as well as the environment to risk. In general, workers

engaged in the informal sector are not aware of the risk associated with potentially toxic and hazardous substances contained in WEEE. Hence, their exposure to these substances can result in severe health challenges. The processing and discharge of toxic products from WEEE are typical of the informal sector. Recycling in the informal sector is carried out without the use of technology and proper protection; thus, individuals incur great risk when processing WEEE (Auclair *et al.*, 2020; Lu *et al.*, 2015; Perkins *et al.*, 2014). Developing countries, e.g., Nigeria, lack the infrastructure required for effective WEEE management (Bimir, 2020; Pérez-Belis, Bovea and Ibáñez-Forés, 2015).

Adequate awareness and sound understanding of WEEE, which are lacking in recyclers in the informal sector, are necessary to reduce risks to health as well as ineffective disposal, recycling, and reuse. Informal recyclers are usually not registered with the appropriate authorities in their location, and their services are thus illegal (Khurram *et al.*, 2011; Miner *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2013). There is a challenge with the adoption of extended producer responsibility in several parts of Africa, for example, Nigeria (Bimir, 2020; Gupt and Sahay, 2015). WEEE constitutes a great deal of waste material, both hazardous and non-hazardous. Informal WEEE recycling exposes the recyclers and the neighbouring environment to polybrominated biphenyls, chromium, mercury, cadmium, and lead. This can affect the liver, kidneys, nervous system, and brain. WEEE, which is usually present in municipal solid waste, can give rise to severe health challenges and environmental pollution from the facilities used for incineration and pulverising/disassembling, as well as from sanitary landfills and unauthorised dumping sites (Gupt and Sahay, 2015; Hoeltl, Brandtweiner and Müller, 2017; Olowu, 2012; Tsai, 2020).

Some of the elements in WEEE that can cause risks to human health and the environment are identified in Osayamwen (2017) and shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3. Typical WEEE components and their adverse health effects.

E-waste component	Adverse health effects	Electronic & Electrical appliances with these components
Sulphur	Throat & eye irritation, Liver, Kidney, and heart damage	Lead-acid batteries
Arsenic	It has negative effects on the Liver, skin, respiratory and nervous system	Phones, Microchips

Carcinogenic powder	Skin irritation, cancer	Ink Cartridges/toner
Brominated Flame retardants	Brain damage, thyroid, and liver problems	Most electronic plastics
Cadmium	Neuromotor deficit in children, severe damage to kidney and lungs	Phone battery, Nickel-Cadmium rechargeable lamps
Mercury	Kidney damage, dermatitis, slower growth, reduced fertility, muscle weakness, memory loss	Phones, flat screen TVs/monitors, mechanical doorbells, fluorescent tubes
Lead	Lower IQ, hyperactivity, attention deficits, behavioural disturbances, and nervous system damage.	Circuit boards, lead acid batteries, CRT monitors, some PVCs

4.2 Recycling Methods in Nigeria

The two types of recycling methods are those practiced by informal recyclers, also known as scavengers, and those practiced by formal recyclers. Both sectors have a target, which is the management of WEEE in a manner that is profitable and sufficient to ensure that waste is not diverted into the major public waste stream and landfills (Omokaro, 2018). Operations common to both informal and formal recyclers, as specified in Samantha *et al.* (2017), are collection, dismantling via the use of manual techniques, recycling, reconditioning, and extraction of cables, metals, plastics, and “printed circuit boards” present in WEEE. In most of the countries referred to as developing, the activities of the informal recycler commence from the moment WEEE is collected and end at the final stage, depending on the available options (Jain, 2017). The collection as well as the recycling of WEEE in Nigeria is primarily carried out by extremely poor rural Nigerians (Okorhi *et al.*, 2017). The informal recyclers carry out their recycling duties in workshops, which are usually small or in the open air (Cesaro *et al.*, 2019).

Countries that are industrialised, such as the US, UK, Sweden, Finland, and Germany, which usually have and maintain “stricter environmental laws and regulations”, practice formal WEEE recycling (Omokaro, 2018). Meanwhile, informal WEEE recycling is carried out in countries such as Nigeria, India, Pakistan, Ghana, and China, where environmental laws and regulations are not strictly enforced. Some studies have suggested that informal recyclers make use of common “extraction tools” and systems such as mallets, hammers, screwdrivers,

chemical leaching, and open burning, in contrast to formal recyclers who carry out their activities under controlled conditions and with standard equipment. Some of the differences between the informal method of recycling WEEE in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and the formal methods practiced in other countries, for example, Mexico, are shown in Table 4.4 (Samantha *et al.*, 2017).

Table 4.4. Differences between informal recycling in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and formal recycling in other countries, e.g., Mexico.

Informal Recycling	Formal Recycling
Pickers either collect WEEE or they are provided with it by consumers	WEEE is gathered via a collection service, logistic service, collection campaign, or at a clean point
Components are manually separated or dismantled	Components are mechanically separated or dismantled
No recycling facilities, only primitive recycling procedures exist	Recycling facilities exist
No delivery to qualified waste managers	Delivery to qualified waste managers takes place
No pre-treatment	Pre-treatment takes place

The informal waste management system is the dominant method in Nigeria; this is because formal waste management is faced with several challenges, as specified according to Alabi and Wohlmuth (2019), including:

- a. Endless “political interference”.
- b. An absence of the required facilities and insufficient funds.
- c. Unconcerned behaviour among staff members.
- d. Unwillingness of those who generate waste to pay service providers.
- e. The presence of “sophisticated equipment” without sufficient skills to operate such equipment.
- f. Corruption and mismanagement of funds.
- g. “Civil society” is usually not involved in the decision-making arrangements.

It is evident that the collection, handling, and refurbishing of WEEE is carried out by informal recyclers, who are largely illiterate, untrained, and without experience (Okorhi, Omotor and Aderemi, 2020). They are usually “undocumented business” persons, usually lack training and skills, and roam the streets and waste dumps with their handcarts to collect, or in rare cases, buy abandoned WEEE and other metal scraps, which contain important elements such as iron, brass, copper, aluminium, etc. Ohajinwa (2018), explains that the recycling of most of the

WEEE that is generated is carried out in an informal/unsafe way, such that toxic elements are released into the environment.

Mihai et al. (2019), report that informal WEEE recycling practices appear to dominate the Nigerian WEEE market. These informal recycling activities often happen in backyards or small workshops in Nigerian cities (Port Harcourt), where primary methods of manual disassembly and open burning are practiced. Primitive techniques such as manual dismantling, the melting of metals, acid dipping, and open burning are often utilised to recover valuable materials from WEEE. The informal recycler does not adopt optimised methodologies for material recovery; for example, metals are usually recovered via heating WEEE on a hot plate or over an open flame. In some instances, WEEE is shredded mechanically to help recover valuable metals (Butturi *et al.*, 2020; Hameed, Ali and Petrillo, 2020; Luo *et al.*, 2014; Onwughara, Nnorom and Kanno, 2010).

Metals can be recovered from depleted lithium-ion batteries using environmentally friendly techniques (Huang, Qiu, *et al.*, 2021). Nonferrous metals can be recovered from PCBs (Huang, Zhu, *et al.*, 2021). Plastic waste such as brominated resin can be recovered from WEEE using infrared heating (Zhu *et al.*, 2022). WEEE is recycled by removing components or valuable materials, including integrated circuits (ICs), plastics, condensers, cathode ray tubes (CRTs), printed wiring boards (PWBs), and metals, which can be reprocessed directly as reusable components for raw materials (Salhofer, 2018). The commonly practiced process of extracting these materials is through an open burning system, which is injurious to human health and the environment (Onwughara, Nnorom and Kanno, 2010). The actors in the informal sectors are cart pushers, scavengers (those who sort and recover materials that can be reused or recycled), resource merchants, and recyclers (Alabi and Wohlmuth, 2019). Despite the problems associated with the informal WEEE management system, it serves as a source of employment and a means of livelihood for many individuals (Ohajinwa, 2018).

The importance of recycling is not based on the proper treatment of WEEE but on the maximum recovery of valuables in discarded WEEE from dumpsites. The crude methods employed by informal recyclers cannot adequately remove the potentially toxic elements (PTEs) in WEEE (Gangwar *et al.*, 2019). Thus, funding by all stakeholders for the upgrading of recycling infrastructure and proper integration of the recycling and waste sectors in Nigeria is a necessity.

However, studies have revealed that informal recycling methods and activities, such as dismantling, open burning of plastics and wire, and indiscriminate disposal, lead to a significant level of potentially toxic elements and persistent organic pollutant emissions in the air, soil, and water. The existing pathways for soil pollution and its impact on humans are described in the following sections, detailing the methods and activities of WEEE management in the informal sector (Ferronato and Torretta, 2019; Williams *et al.*, 2008).

Studies reveal that informal recycling activities, such as the open burning of wires and plastics, dismantling, and unregulated disposal, result in the release of significant levels of heavy metals as well as persistent organic pollutants into the soil, air, and underground as well as surface water (Ezeudu and Ezeudu, 2019; Gangwar *et al.*, 2019). However, a study carried out by Ezeudu and Ezeudu (2019), shows that Nigeria does not have the capacity for formal recycling methods, in part due to the lack of modern recycling facilities in the country. Conversely, Omokaro (2018, p. 18), explains that the effort made to commence formal recycling in Nigeria failed due to “consumption habits” as well as the political, social, economic, and cultural context, which necessitates the services of the informal recyclers. The management of WEEE in Nigeria is faced with numerous challenges, as identified by Nnorom and Odeyingbo (2020), including the following:

- (a) The influx of used electrical and electronic equipment approaching their end of life is frequently combined with WEEE.
- (b) The rate of collection of end-of-life electrical and electronic equipment is poor, as owners usually keep them inside their cabinets and drawers, after which they are disposed of in the general waste stream.
- (c) The majority of the population appears to be ignorant of the “toxicity or hazardous nature” of WEEE.
- (d) WEEE is usually disposed of alongside other waste using the same bin and is taken to the open dump, thus necessitating/promoting sorting, scavenging, etc.
- (e) The flow of electronic waste via recyclers in the informal sector is more than that of formal recyclers, who are fewer in number.
- (f) It is difficult to source funds to establish profitable formal WEEE recycling practices.
- (g) There is weak enforcement of WEEE legislation.

- (h) There is a “non-implementation” of the extended producer responsibility (EPR) segment of WEEE regulations.
- (i) There is a lack of appropriate infrastructure for WEEE management.
- (j) The primitive techniques used by informal recyclers give rise to environmental pollution as well as energy and resource waste.

4.3. Challenges of Informal Recycling in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Goel (2019), puts forward that WEEE gathering or collection in Port Harcourt is predominantly carried out by informal recyclers. They are not just involved in WEEE management alone; they gather a variety of wastes at the same time to enable them to make a living from their activities, and thus it is difficult to ascertain who is uniquely responsible for WEEE management. According to ILO (2014), several informal WEEE recyclers “remain unaware of” some of the products or materials that they can recycle or recover. The same research effort explains that some of the problems of informal recycling are that it exposes human health and the environment to risk, in addition to the fact that its treatment is expensive and complex. In Vaccari et al. (2019), the “spread of pollutants” from the facilities used by informal recyclers in Port Harcourt tends to affect humans via pollution transportation mechanisms “and exposure pathways”.

A study by Yu et al. (2010), informal WEEE recycling poses many challenges, yet its practice is difficult to stop due to factors such as the increasing demand for second-hand electronics and second-hand parts (for local industries), as well as the increasing need for equipment/materials (as a result of the expansion of the manufacturing industries); this is the case with Port Harcourt. The recycling of lead–acid batteries by the informal sector during dismantling results in hazardous emissions. This can affect the environment as well as the health of individuals (Okorhi, Joe and Aderemi, 2014; Zeng *et al.*, 2020). According to Osaretin (2018), the disposal of WEEE puts the environment and human life at great risk as a result of them being “exposed to” chemicals that are hazardous while the electronic components are being dismantled. The recyclers in the informal sector in Port Harcourt utilise crude recycling procedures as they lack the required infrastructure to ensure the safety of the environment and human life (Yu *et al.*, 2010).

The informal recycling activities in Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt city are characterised by the following: the workers are predominantly young individuals; the working hours are about 9–

12 hrs daily, and those living around the location where open burning is carried out usually experience health-related challenges, as specified in (Cesaro *et al.*, 2019). In Omokaro (2018), the WEEE scrappers are usually faced with the problems of bad roads, roads flooded with water after rainfall, and the rising price of petrol, all of which affect “the availability of transport”. Awasthi, Shivashankar, and Majumder (2017), emphasised that the majority of “developing countries” are faced with the challenges associated with recycling WEEE using the informal approach, and this is because of the large population of jobless individuals who now collect and recycle WEEE at family-owned workshops.

The informal WEEE recyclers are faced with some limitations, which can be minimised with the intervention of the government and private individuals. These limitations are specified in Alabi and Wohlmuth (2019), and include:

- (a) A lack of essential facilities that can enhance their efforts and activities.
- (b) No monetary aid nor recognition from the government.
- (c) A lack of safety equipment to protect them from the health-related risks usually associated with hazardous elements.
- (d) A general absence of essential training on how to protect themselves, WEEE handling, environmental issues, etc.
- (e) Lack of access to adequate orientation, training, health facilities, as well as first-aid treatment in situations of emergency.
- (f) Informal recyclers do not have access to proper medical services.

Omokaro (2018), suggests that recycling carried out in the informal sector gives rise to several “negative environmental effects” and hence needs to be stopped.

4.3.1. Factors That Affect the WEEE Management System in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

The factors that affect the strategies adopted to manage WEEE in Port Harcourt are specified in Okorhi, Joe, and Aderemi (2014), and include:

- i. A lack of standardised local recycling systems.
- ii. Incorrect identification of WEEE at the entry point.
- iii. Lack of awareness of the toxicity of WEEE and the difficulty in differentiating near-end-of-life EEE from WEEE.

- iv. Take-back programmes are difficult to initiate and pursue, “co-loading of near E.o.L”, second-hand vehicles with WEEE and EEE, and a lack of localised statistics on EEE and WEEE.
- v. The inability of the government to proffer a longstanding and feasible approach to WEEE management.
- vi. Users of EEE tend to purchase considerably “used” ones that are close to losing their useful life as opposed to ones that are new.

Cole et al. (2019), suggested that it is advisable to consider a five-point waste hierarchy for WEEE management, as shown in Figure 4.3

Figure 4.3 Hierarchy of waste.

Presently, WEEE management at MTN phone villages in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, is carried out by informal recyclers who lack basic knowledge on prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery, and disposal, as shown in Figure 4.3. Our study looks at approaches to change the existing WEEE management practices at the location, as its focus is to prevent the harmful and primitive style of WEEE management carried out by recyclers in the informal sector in the area and find potential applications to other regions faced with similar practices. Furthermore, if the activities of informal recyclers are drastically reduced at MTN phone villages in Port Harcourt, Nigeria the associated problems with poor recycling in the informal sector will be greatly inhibited.

4.4 Materials and Methods

This research work is geared towards “prevention”, as shown in Figure 4.3. The research focuses on pragmatic opportunities to reduce informal recycling at MTN phone villages in Port

Harcourt by reducing the involvement of informal recyclers in the management of WEEE. Two different concepts were adopted in the study, and these were:

1. Ensuring that WEEE is recovered from informal recyclers, residents, and other areas and is sent to government-approved agencies for sorting, processing, and treatment.
2. Soliciting the support of informal recyclers to engage only in WEEE collection and gathering and to be paid for these services.

The study adopted the survey strategy of data collection due to its ease of analysis. Survey data acquired via questionnaires is often organised and quantitative in nature, making it relatively simple to analyse with statistical software tools. This streamlines the research process and allows for efficient data-driven decision-making (Aithal and Aithal, 2020). The study adopted the survey research strategy for data collection because it is cost-effective. Surveys are generally less expensive than other techniques of data collecting, such as interviews or focus groups, particularly when addressing large and geographically distributed audiences. The standardised design of survey questions eliminates the need for substantial interviewer training and lowers the logistical costs involved with data collection (Firchow and Ginty, 2017). This study also adopted the survey strategy because of its scalability. Surveys can simply be scaled up or down to meet different sample sizes, research aims, or geographical regions. Researchers may tailor the breadth and size of the survey questionnaire technique to the unique objectives of the research project, making it applicable to a variety of contexts and research settings (Belisario *et al.*, 2015). The use of survey questionnaires was adopted due to standardization. Questions for surveys can be standardised to ensure that data is collected consistently across various respondents or groups. This standardisation reduces interviewer bias and answer variance, making data more comparable and reliable among respondents (Jansen, Jung and Salminen, 2023).

Quantitative research frequently involves data collection using structured methodologies or instruments or procedures that can be replicated by other researchers. This replicability is critical to determining the reliability of results. When many studies employing identical quantitative methodologies provide consistent results, confidence in the findings grows, as does the general validity of the research (Augustus and.,2020). Quantitative analysis uses a variety of statistical approaches to examine data and reach conclusions (Mohajan, 2020). Researchers can use these strategies to find patterns, correlations, and trends in data. Statistical tests like hypothesis testing, correlation analysis, and regression analysis, enable researchers to

analyze the strength and significance of correlations between variables, therefore improving the validity of their findings (Ugwu, Opuware and Ambakederemo, 2021).

Quantitative research frequently includes reliability testing for instruments for measurement like surveys, questionnaires, and tests. Reliability tests measure these instruments' consistency and stability over time and under various settings. Establishing a high level of reliability suggests that the measuring instrument produces consistent results, which strengthens the general reliability of the study findings (Driver and Maslakci, 2020).

Quantitative research often requires greater sample sizes than qualitative research. A bigger sample size improves the findings' generalizability to the larger population from which they were collected. Ensuring that the sample is representative of the population of interest improves the research's external validity, making it more applicable in real-world contexts (Scârneci-Domnişoru, 2024).

The study participants were selected individuals from the chosen location in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The chosen research location was a small business village, locally known as Rumukurushi's MTN phone village. The location is very small, such that the number of informal WEEE recyclers operating in the area is estimated to be about 30 persons. The location, even though small, is faced with the challenge of indiscriminate dumping of WEEE. This study was carried out to establish a means to limit the role of recyclers in the informal sector and the associated problems. The informal recyclers who reside in the location were consulted in order to establish a clear picture of practices in the area. The participants in the study include both males and females (i.e., 22 men and 3 women). A total of 25 participants took part in the study. Male and female participation in the survey accounted for 88% and 12%, respectively. Out of the 25 informal recyclers who took part in the study, only two had attended secondary school: the remaining attended primary school only.

The study was given ethical approval after a review of the study design and documentation by the School of Computing, Engineering & Physical Sciences Ethics Committee, University of the West of Scotland.

4.5 Results and Discussion

This study attempts to identify the main reason why the individuals in the chosen research location engage in informal WEEE recycling. The options made available to the recyclers were

no job availability, zero tax payment, extra income generation, and others, as shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5 The reasons why informal recyclers engage in WEEE management.

S/n	Reasons for Individual Engagement in Informal Recycling	Number of Participants in Agreement	Participants in Agreement (%)
1	Unavailability of jobs	16	64
2	Zero tax payment	1	4
3	Extra income generation	3	12
4	Other	5	20

The outcomes show that the majority of the informal recyclers (64%) admitted that the unavailability of jobs was the key reason for participating in WEEE activities. An effort was made to ascertain if the informal recyclers intend to partner with government agencies for effective WEEE management if given the opportunity. The results show that 4% of the participants strongly disagree with a partnership with government agencies, 8% disagree, 48% agree, and 40% strongly agree. The number of participants who showed positive interest in partnering with government agencies exceeds those who are not in support by a great margin. See details in Figure 4.4

Figure 4.4 A plot of informal WEEE recyclers' willingness to partner with government agencies.

The readiness of the recyclers in the informal sector to accept payment for the collection or gathering of WEEE and to disengage themselves from other activities (e.g., burning, treatment, etc.) in the management of WEEE was carefully examined. According to the outcome, 4% of respondents disagree and 4% strongly disagree. Furthermore, 52% and 40% agree and strongly agree, respectively. This demonstrates the readiness of informal recyclers to restrict their activities to WEEE gathering or collection if an opportunity to be paid for by the government is offered to them. See details in figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5. A plot of the readiness of informal recyclers to restrict their activities to WEEE gathering only and be paid.

4.6 Advantages of the WEEE Management Approach in MTN Phone Villages, Rumukurushi, a Small Settlement in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

The advantages associated with this approach to managing WEEE are:

- The enhancement of sustainable and safe disposal methods for materials that can cause hazards.
- The creation of room for the recovery of important elements, such as copper, gold, etc., for recycling and reuse.
- The separation of materials that can cause hazards from those that do not during WEEE dismantling is enhanced.
- With this concept, the activities of recyclers in the informal sector are easily checked and curtailed.

- WEEE repurposing, recycling, reuse, reduction, and recovery can be achieved easily.
- It has the potential to reduce the volume of tasks carried out by informal recyclers.
- It will serve as a means of motivation for recyclers in the informal sector.
- It can offer policymakers valuable insights regarding the management of WEEE.
- With this approach in place, it is possible to minimise the hazards presented by recycling in the informal sector.
- It creates awareness of the importance of engaging experienced and well-trained workers to manage WEEE.

4.7 Conclusions

This study carried out a review of past publications on the management of WEEE in order to reduce risks to human health from activities in the informal recycling sector in MTN phone village located in Rumukurushi, a small settlement in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. A new concept of managing WEEE was introduced for Rumukurushi, which limits the activities of informal recyclers to WEEE collection only, in return for formal payment for their services. In this case, the informal recyclers do not take part in WEEE treatment, dismantling, refining, disposal, etc. Trained workers and government-approved offices are solely responsible for the management of WEEE. This provides increased productivity, efficiency, and safety. The study outcomes show that 48% agree to partner with government agencies, while 40% of those remaining strongly agree to the collaboration. The number of participants who showed a positive interest in partnering with government agencies exceeded that of those who were not in support by a great margin. In addition, 52% and 40% agree and strongly agree, respectively, to limit their activities exclusively to WEEE collection if the government is willing to pay for their services.

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Chapter 5:

Enhancement of WEEE Management Practices in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

The material in this chapter has been published as “Enhancement of WEEE Management Practices in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria” (Okwu *et al.*, 2021).

The quest to achieve monetary gains from the oil and gas sector in Nigeria necessitated the influx of individuals into the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. As a result of the continuously increasing population experienced in the location, there is a rise in population, WEEE, material consumption, as well as other contaminants that can affect the environment. This creates room for a continuous rise in the quantity of WEEE produced in the location (Konya, Babatunde and Iniefe, 2015). The study location’s mobile telephone network (MTN) phone village, Rumukurushi is faced with the challenge of informal recycling. It is believed that about a total of thirty informal recyclers carry out their recycling activities in the location. Informal recycling is the main WEEE practice in the location (Amadi and Chijioke, 2018). The informal recyclers in the location lack awareness of the accessible protection as well as their right. They engage in an unsafe WEEE management technique, hence exposing themselves, individuals in the location as well as the environment to risk (Ohajinwa *et al.*, 2017).

This chapter of the thesis attempts to minimise the role of the informal recyclers (in the selected location and other areas affected by similar challenges) in WEEE management in order to tackle completely the challenges associated with their method of practice. Areas covered in this section of the thesis are the literature survey and the outcome of the proposed waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) management system, which comprises the application of two key concepts. The first concept includes limiting the activities of Informal recyclers to WEEE collection only. This implies the remaining WEEE management activities, such as treatment, dismantling, etc., are carried out by government-approved agencies and experts. The second concept involves the application of the Just-in-time (JIT) management concept for managing WEEE. The concept ensures that WEEE is only requested from the recycler or the individuals in possession of it only on demand. To attain the aim of the study, a

qualitative research approach was adopted. Data collection and analysis were carried out through semi-structured phone interviews and thematic analysis respectively.

5.1 Literature survey.

Inappropriate disposal of WEEE and other forms of waste is typical of developing countries, for example, Nigeria. (Omosimua *et al.*, 2020). The consequences of the movement of waste electrical and electronic waste, WEEE across the African borders are no longer hidden as the location appears as the choice location for dumping e-waste. As such, it has emerged as an issue of great concern to those involved with policymaking in the location (Amechi and Oni, 2019). WEEE is a prevailing and growing challenge globally with an estimated value of more than 50 million metric tons annually generated (Wideman, 2019). Waste electrical and electronic equipment, WEEE comprises components as well as devices with the potential to bring about serious environmental harm due to its hazardous contents (Bilitewski, Wagner and Reichenbach, 2018).

Mercury, an element found in WEEE is a great source of pollution (Erhardt *et al.*, 2015). The management of WEEE is of key necessity, according to a study by Aidonis *et al.* (2019), and this is because it: (i) forms a segment of solid waste that is always increasing, and (2) contains scarce, valuable as well as hazardous elements. Conversely, according to Rai (2021), WEEE is diverse in nature, it comprises several systems that contain various classes of ceramics, plastics, and metals, hence, they are referred to as secondary sources of raw materials. There are some advantages associated with the recovery of WEEE and these are a reduction in the consumption of energy, or saving in terms of the usage of virgin materials, and raw material preservation (Grigorescu *et al.*, 2019). Herat (2018), created an awareness that WEEE does not only imply challenges as it also presents us with the opportunity to extract valuable materials. For instance, despite the numerous challenges associated with WEEE management, research has shown that there is a possibility to generate energy from the landfill, achieved either through thermal treatment or methane extraction. The potential to generate energy is faced with lack of experienced professionals as its key limitation (Kumar *et al.*, 2017).

A study has also demonstrated that when WEEE is properly managed, it facilitates the attainment of economic, social, and environmental benefits (Akon-Yamga *et al.*, 2021). WEEE serves as a source of important raw materials (Cui and Zhang, 2008; Hennebel *et al.*, 2015; Murakami, Nishihama, and Yoshizuka, 2015; Sethurajan *et al.*, 2019; Tan, Li and Zeng, 2015).

Mobile phone printed circuit boards contain elements such as Lead (Pb), Nickel (Ni), Silver (Ag), Gold (Au), Tin (Sn), and Copper (Cu) (Gorewoda *et al.*, 2020), (Monneron-Enaud, Wiche and Schlömann, 2020). Indium for instance can be recovered from LCD panels (Ueberschaar *et al.*, 2017). Unlike developing countries that are presently faced with economic challenges for example poverty, the developed nations have the required technology, finance, and other important facilities yet they export their WEEE into the developing nations as the cheapest option (Abalansa *et al.*, 2021). Informal recycling exposes both human life and the environment to substances that are toxic (Cesaro *et al.*, 2018; Daum, Stoler and Grant, 2017; Islam *et al.*, 2020; Wang, Qian and Liu, 2020).

Informal WEEE recyclers as well as their family are at risk of exposure to toxic elements (Ceballos, Dong and Frank, 2016; Grant *et al.*, 2013; Julander *et al.*, 2014; Lau *et al.*, 2014; Rautela *et al.*, 2021). The concentration of bacteria rises during the rainy season; hence, it affects life and the environment negatively (Shahady and Boniface, 2018). Individuals from low-income families tend to live close to pollution and are likely to suffer more (Charette, Collins and Mirowsky, 2021). The projected volume of WEEE generated globally rose to 49.8 metric tons in 2018 as in Adeola (2018), as shown in Figure 5.1

Figure 5.1 The projected amount of WEEE generated globally per year, population, and WEEE per capita

In a study carried out by Jaiswal *et al.* (2015), some of the factors that facilitated the ever-increasing volume of WEEE are as follows: (a) The rapid growth without restriction of the

electronic and “Information Technology” sector. (b) Production of electrical and electronic equipment with a shorter lifecycle, tends to make the devices outdated within a short time. (c) End user’s shortage of ideas on what next to do with the WEEE scrap. (d) There is no generally accepted procedure for the management of WEEE. (e) Reduction in product cost creates room for more devices to be bought, which implies more WEEE (f) Re-usability and recycling rate are limited (g) “Multifaceted processes of WEEE handling”. (h) The speedy technological innovation has made useable items old-fashioned. (i) Items like plastics that are non-degradable gained patronage due to low cost but expose the environment to risk. (j) The tendency of some consumers to use and discard makes it difficult for some products to be re-used.

Besides, Fang (2021), there is no mandatory policy that makes it compulsory for waste to be cleaned up by those who created it. According to Jaiswal et al. (2015), some of the factors that facilitated the ever-increasing volume of WEEE are as follows: (a) The rapid growth without restriction of the electronic and “Information Technology” sector. (b) Production of electrical and electronic equipment with a shorter lifecycle tends to make the devices outdated within a short time. (c) End user’s shortage of ideas on what next to do with the WEEE scrap. (d) There is no generally accepted procedure for the management of WEEE. (e) Reduction in product cost creates room for more devices to be bought, which implies more WEEE (f) Re-usability and recycling rate are limited (g) “Multifaceted processes of WEEE handling”. (h) The speedy technological innovation has made useable items old-fashioned. (i) Items like plastics that are non-degradable gained patronage due to low cost but expose the environment to risk. (j) The tendency of some consumers to use and discard makes it difficult for some products to be re-used. Besides, in Fang (2021), there is no mandatory policy that makes it compulsory for waste to be cleaned up by those who created it.

According to Lawal (2019), several pieces of land in Nigeria that would have been put to good use are currently being used as WEEE dumpsites. The main concern with WEEE management is the processes involved in its treatment, which presents risk to the environment as well as to human health. The informal recyclers that are involved in the WEEE management lack appropriate training for the task and are ignorant of the health and environmental consequences of the business (Charles, 2018; ILO, 2014; Işıldar *et al.*, 2019; Ndunda and Ambole, 2018). The health and environmental impacts of the release of hazardous elements are not easy to identify by those involved (Gervich *et al.*, 2016). Stopping the unlawful importation of WEEE into the country is not enough to put an end to the challenges associated with WEEE

management. WEEE generated domestically must be properly managed (Okorhi *et al.*, 2017). Ndunda and Ambole (2018, p. 77), state that recyclers are not adopting formal recycling techniques and that one of the reasons is because it is expensive. The study recommends that the government should ensure strict compliance with the “producer responsibility” for the proper management of WEEE.

One of the factors that have also contributed to WEEE generation is that there is no international legal agreement on the management of WEEE (Işıldar *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the creation of public awareness of the need to put in place a good policy for managing toxic or hazardous elements is of great importance, but yet to be adopted by the stakeholders (Richmond, 2016). Most developing countries are unable to practice informal recycling because they lack the right facilities to manage WEEE. The study recommends that the highest accepted method to manage WEEE is the “extended producer responsibility” (Bimir, 2020; Ilankoon *et al.*, 2018). Nigeria is a good example of countries with deficiencies in the management of WEEE (Mihai *et al.*, 2019). To combat the challenges associated with WEEE management, a collective collaboration of formal recyclers, the government, businesses, and the social-economic sector is a necessity (ILO, 2014). For WEEE to be properly managed, a strict policy must be established (Ogbuanya and Afeez, 2019). The focus of this study is to reduce the role of informal recyclers in WEEE management to tackle completely the challenges associated with their method of practice.

5.1.1 A Review of past research efforts to manage WEEE

Several attempts have been carried out in the past to tackle the challenges associated with informal recycling. Some of the attempts made to tackle the challenges previously are given below:

Mihai *et al.* (2019), an effort was made using statistical data on waste and thematic cartography in order to ascertain the geographical movement of WEEE at both national and global levels. The study considered the adopted style used for the management of WEEE in each of the geographical locations, for example, Africa, Oceania, South America, North America, Europe, etc. What was the outcome of the study? The findings show that a shortage of the required amenities is the reason for Africa’s poor approach to WEEE management. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study was unable to proffer a solution to the challenge, and this is because the study focused on the

indicators of poor WEEE management. Identification of an approach that may help to proffer a solution to informal recycling will prove more helpful.

Aidonis et al. (2019), a methodology was developed to identify a WEEE management scheme that is optimal for finding an alternative way in which the management of WEEE can be integrated. The study utilised a binary linear programming model to enhance the effectiveness of a total of nine WEEE management options. Twelve performance criteria that cut across social, environmental, technical, and financial dimensions were considered. What was the outcome of the study? The outcome of the study shows that recycling WEEE mechanically alongside the export of WEEE residues is the most effective strategy. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study was unable to address the challenges, and this is because the approach on offer cannot proffer a solution to the numerous challenges associated with informal recycling. An approach that can reduce the activities of informal recyclers will be more useful.

Ndunda and Ambole (2018, p. 73), an effort was made to tackle the challenges caused by the informal recycling of WEEE by creating “a product-service system” for its management. In this study, supporters of a move from product provision to the “provision of systems of products and services” were developed alongside the support of stakeholders in order to manage WEEE efficiently. The concept of dematerialisation was adopted in this study using the effort of the collaboration of the stakeholder; this prevents the informal recyclers or consumers from having possession of equipment after EOL. What was the outcome of the study? The findings of the study indicate that the success of the method depends on the combined effort of each of the stakeholders. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study did not proffer a solution to the challenge. This is because dematerialisation can only be achieved when there is a technological and structural change in the location, which appears to be lacking in the chosen research location. Adopting a concept that applies to developing countries is likely to make more contributions to locations where informal recycling techniques are prevalent.

IGeorge, Mapa, and Dinggai (2019), an attempt was made to address the management of WEEE, with emphasis on households, by assessing the make-up of the electrical and electronic devices in the apartments of the individuals in the selected location and the way they manage WEEE. A survey approach, with the help of questionnaires for data gathering,

was adopted by the study. What was the outcome of the study? The outcome of the study shows that the electrical and electronic devices that dominate the most in the location of the study are mobile phones. Conversely, the result of the study shows that the location of the study engages a WEEE management approach that is not sustainable, as they do not recycle their WEEE, but prefer to keep them in the house or drop them in the waste bin. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study was unable to address the challenges, and this is because no effort was made to reduce the effort of informal recyclers. Only recommendations were offered by the study. Designing a concept that can effectively proffer a solution to at least one of the numerous challenges associated with informal recycling will be valuable.

According to Arya, Gupta, and Bhardwaj (2018), a study was carried out to help ascertain the extent of awareness of both the recyclers and the users (organisations, companies, and individuals) on the hazards caused by WEEE. The study utilised a survey approach for data gathering using questionnaires from three different stakeholders, namely: organisations, individuals, and those involved with WEEE recycling. The survey carried out in this study comprises 10 individuals involved in WEEE recycling and 25 individual users of electrical and electronic devices, as well as 35 organisations classed as users. What was the outcome of the study? The outcome shows that both the individuals and the organisational users do not know the dangers of WEEE. They lack adequate knowledge of the WEEE legislature, and there is no good channel for WEEE collection. Finally, the informal recycler who lacks knowledge of the dangers associated with WEEE does not use a safe approach about disposal. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study was unable to address the challenges associated with informal recycling, and this is because the focus was on the extent of awareness of both the recyclers and the users. The researcher ought to have also suggested health and safety training as an alternative way to acquire awareness.

Study by Ogbuanya and Afeez (2019, p. 90), the researchers shed light on how WEEE techniques adopted in the workshops of “electrical/electronic technicians” can be improved. The study adopted the use of questionnaires for data gathering, and the individuals involved comprised 54 officers in the “public health” sector and 87 lecturers from the faculty of engineering. The analysis of the data gathered was carried out with the help of percentage, mean, and standard deviation using t-test and ANOVA. What was the outcome of the study?

The outcome of the study shows that provision of the “recycling site”, introduction, and application of policies are the main techniques for WEEE management. How has the study addressed the challenges associated with informal recycling? The study was unable to address the challenges associated with informal recycling. This study only identified indicators that may be helpful. Finding effective approaches that can help to tackle the challenge of WEEE management may be useful.

5.1.2 Research Gap

Several efforts have been made by researchers in the past to proffer a solution to the challenges associated with informal recycling, but the challenge remains. No one has been able to reduce the challenges. This is largely due to the difficulties associated with getting the informal recyclers to adopt WEEE best management practices since they are mostly illiterate. This makes the challenges associated with informal recycling an unending problem, especially in Nigeria and other developing countries faced with the same challenge. This research gap in this field forms the basis of this study.

5.1.3 The need to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in WEEE management in the study location.

Informal recycling appears as the key reason for the challenges associated with WEEE management (Yang *et al.*, 2018). Hence, a drastic reduction in the activities of informal recyclers will help to revolutionize the WEEE management practice in Nigeria and other developing countries that patronise similar recycling methods. The services of informal recyclers are faced with the following challenges, according to (Alabi and Wohlmuth, 2019).

- a. They lack training, orientation, and formal education on the use of personal protective equipment, PPE, and first aid treatment applications during an emergency.
- b. They lack the basic facilities required for effective WEEE management.
- c. The government does not offer them financial support or any form of recognition.
- d. Their WEEE management techniques expose them, individuals in the location as well as the environment, to risk.
- e. They usually do not adopt the use of safety gadgets to protect themselves from materials that are hazardous or health risks.

- f. No access to training opportunities on types of materials and waste, technologies, finance, and conditions of the environment.
- g. No access to required health facilities.
- h. They lack the appropriate facility and knowledge to manage substances/elements that are harmful to life and the environment.

5.1.4 How to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in WEEE management

Ceballos, Dong, and Frank (2016), lectured that observing the following tips can help to reduce the menace associated with WEEE management.

- Avoid purchasing electrical or electronic devices that you don't need.
- Patronise the manufacturers of electronic or electrical devices that adopt the use of "green technologies as well as take-back systems.
- Encourage WEEE recyclers in your community in your location. You can throw away your WEEE by visiting their location.
- Avoid discarding electrical or electronic devices such as solar panels, light bulbs, batteries, and Printed circuit boards into regular refuse.

This study attempts to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in the business of WEEE management through the design of a new management system that will still provide the informal recyclers with an opportunity to earn money. The WEEE management system allows informal recyclers to earn money from WEEE gathering or collection while other activities such as treatment, recycling, etc., are handled by government-trained experts. Furthermore, the just-in-time (JIT) lean management principles are also adopted to enhance the efficiency of the method.

5.2 WEEE management system

This study intends to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. This will be achieved via the combination of two different approaches namely.

- Recovering WEEE from residents, informal recyclers, and the remaining part of the public for sorting, processing, treatment, and recycling by government-approved agencies.

- Application of the just-in-time (JIT) lean management principles to the current WEEE management system in the location.

The WEEE management model is shown in Figure 5.2

Figure 5.2 WEEE management model

The WEEE management system ensures that only government-approved agencies are allowed to manage WEEE. WEEE is collected from residents, informal recyclers, and the remaining part of the public and this will help to cut down informal recycling and the challenges

associated with it. The application of the just-in-time concept is applied by government-approved agencies after WEEE collection/gathering. Furthermore, the dismantling of WEEE is carried out by experienced and trained government personnel to ensure that the dismantled WEEE materials follow appropriate processing such as re-use, further treatment, refining, etc.

5.2.1 *Lean concepts*

The word “Lean” implies a set of solutions or activities to remove waste, cut down “non-value-added (NVA) operations” and increase “the value-added” ones (Deranek, Chopra and Mosher, 2017; Wee and Wu, 2009).

Lean safety refers to a technique fashioned for the identification and reduction of waste in some processes and hence, cut down accidents and illnesses in the workplace (Rever, 2020). A research effort made by Hamja et al. (2017), explains that the key objective of the lean approach is waste elimination, as it helps to eliminate “waste of non-value process during production”. The same report shows that safety and success can be enhanced through the applications of lean tools such as lean principles, just in time (JIT), 5S, etc. The lean approach makes it feasible for the adoption of the 5S methodology which involves the application of 5 steps, and these are sort, straighten, shine, standardize, and sustain (Hamja *et al.*, 2017; Wee and Wu, 2009). Recent research work by Alkhoraif, Rashid, and McLaughlin (2019), concluded that the lean concept refers to more efficient utilisation of available resources when it matters the most as material and time waste are pinpointed and eliminated creating room for maintenance of quality with diminishing cost.

5.2.2. *Just-in-time concept*

This study adopts the Just-in-time concept in the management of WEEE. The just-in-time concept as investigated by McKinney and Scalia (2019), increases efficiency while waste is reduced by collecting goods or items only as they are demanded in the process of production. The concept decreases wastage, enhances productivity, efficiency, and the flow of the production process (Melanie, 2017). In Wu, Dong, and Wang (2019), the Just-in-time management concept can help to reduce “the waiting times of workers and equipment”. Just-in-time comprises three key objectives and these are the reduction or elimination of every form of inventory, the unmasking of the inefficiencies that exist in the production process, and the application of current production techniques to reduce inefficiencies identified in the process

(Singh and Ahuja, 2012). Just-in-time entails producing only that which is required, at the time it is required as well as the amount needed at a specific time (Davies, 2020). The Just-in-time concept is applied to WEEE management in the following ways: collection of WEEE from the residents, informal recyclers, and the remaining part of the public will only be done on-demand. This implies further collection of WEEE is done when those already collected have been processed and there is room to accommodate new ones.

The benefits of this concept are as follows:

- a. WEEE collection and gathering at government-approved collection centres will be done on demand.
- b. WEEE gathered are processed and the dumping ground at the government-approved collection centres is emptied for re-use.
- c. The health challenges associated with offensive odour from the decay of WEEE are eliminated since the WEEE collected is processed almost immediately.
- d. It helps to reduce waste of land or storage space, unlike the existing WEEE management system in which WEEE occupies a lot of space and produces an offensive odour that can cause health challenges.
- e. Collection and gathering of WEEE serve as a source of income to the informal recyclers and all those involved in WEEE collection.

5.3. Advantages of the WEEE management system for Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

The benefits of the WEEE management system include:

- It will enhance the safe and sustainable disposal of hazardous materials.
- Valuable materials or precious metals like gold, copper, etc., will be recovered for reuse and recycling.
- It will enhance the sorting of hazardous materials from non-hazardous materials after dismantling.
- It will help to check and reduce the activities of informal WEEE recyclers since they lack the required skills and experience for proper WEEE treatment, processing, and disposal.
- With this system in place, the recovery, reduction, reuse, repurpose, and recycling of WEEE are possibilities.

- It will create job opportunities.
- It will help make suggestions to policymakers on how to address the issues related to WEEE.
- It will help to reduce other risks associated with informal WEEE processing, treatment, and disposal in Nigeria.
- It will help to create awareness of the need for WEEE to be handled by properly trained and experienced personnel.

5.4 Materials and Method

The study methodology comprises the research philosophy, research approach, data collection method, and data analysis method. The interpretivist research philosophy was adopted in this study. In Kivunja and Kuyini (2017, p. 33), with interpretivist research philosophy, the theory does not come before research but comes after it, this implies, “it is grounded on the data generated by the research act”.

Utilising an interpretivist research methodology and semi-structured phone interviews may be advantageous in various ways, particularly in research environments that aim to examine and comprehend social phenomena from the viewpoints of participants (Falvo *et al.*, 2021). Interpretivism emphasises subjective understanding of individuals and the social system within which they operate (Lim, 2023). Semi-structured phone interviews enable researchers to dive deeply into participants' interpretations, experiences, and perceptions of the phenomena being studied. This method is especially useful when dealing with complicated and intricate issues that require different views (Sturges and Hanrahan, 2004). Semi-structured interviews provide freedom in questioning, allowing researchers to investigate emerging themes and follow up on intriguing replies. This flexibility allows participants to express themselves in their own words and researchers to delve deeper into fields of interest, increasing the variety and depth of data acquired (Mannan and Afni, 2020). Conducting interviews over the phone can increase participant comfort and accessibility. Phone interviews minimise the geographical and logistical limitations associated with in-person interviews, making it simpler to contact a wide range of participants. Furthermore, participants may feel more comfortable discussing their thoughts over the phone, resulting in more frank and honest responses (Azad *et al.*, 2021).

Semi-structured phone interviews can produce rich qualitative data by capturing the complexity and subtleties of participants' experiences and viewpoints. By allowing for open-ended questions and in-depth investigation of themes, researchers can collect detailed narratives and insights that quantitative approaches alone may not capture (Reyes and Greenfield, 2021). The interpretivist research philosophy stresses understanding occurrences in their social and cultural context (Pervin, 2022). Semi-structured phone interviews allow researchers to investigate the contextual factors that impact participants' perceptions and behaviours, resulting in a better knowledge of the social dynamics at play (DeSimone, 2020). Interpretivism recognises that people build meaning via their lived experiences and social interactions (Buriro, Ednut and Khatoon, 2020). Semi-structured phone interviews enable researchers to investigate how people build meaning around the phenomena under investigation, offering insight into the subjective interpretations and meanings assigned to various parts of the issue (Bulgren, 2020). Semi-structured interviews provide an iterative approach to gathering data, with early findings informing later interviews and data collection activities. This iterative method helps researchers to gradually deepen their grasp of the study issue while also delving deeper into emergent themes or discoveries (Busetto, Wick and Gumbinger, 2020). Semi-structured phone interviews allow participants to express their knowledge and thoughts in their own words. Giving participants a voice in the study process allows researchers to obtain a better knowledge of their lived experiences and ensure that their views are correctly represented in the findings (Iverson *et al.*, 2022).

To take a look at informal recycling in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria, a small location known as MTN phone village, Rumukurushi was used as a case study. Hence, a qualitative research approach was adopted for the study. In a study carried out by Ragab and Arisha (2017, p. 3), a new theory development can be achieved with the help of two approaches, it is either carried out with the use of “deductive reasoning” or through “inductive theory building”. According to the same research work, the deductive approach allows for quantitative data collection while the inductive approach allows for qualitative data collection. This study adopted the inductive approach since it requires qualitative data.

Data gathering for the study was achieved with the help of semi-structured phone interviews. The semi-structured interview method was adopted to enable flexibility in the nature and number of questions asked (Evans and Lewis, 2018). The study preferred a face-to-face

interview but it was not achievable due to the prevailing COVID-19 pandemic. The thematic analysis technique was adopted for the analysis of the data.

5.4.1 Data collection using semi-structured phone interviews.

Due to the prevailing COVID-19 pandemic during the period of data collection. A face-to-face interview was not feasible as it required traveling by flight from the UK to Port Harcourt, Nigeria, hence a semi-structured phone interview was carried out instead. The respondents are members of staff of a WEEE regulatory agency in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. According to a study carried out by Ragab and Arisha (2017, p. 12), two main kinds of interviews exist namely structured and unstructured. An interview that adopts the structured approach may achieve a few ranges of answers and this is because the entire participants are provided with a “set of identical questions which are asked in a predetermined order”. It takes the form of a questionnaire. The unstructured interview does not adopt the use of “a set of identical questions” i.e., they are not standardised. Furthermore, in between these two (2) kinds of interviews is the semi-structured interview that adopts the use of “a set of predetermined questions” and creates room for a reasonable amount of flexibility, for example, new questions can be asked, existing one can be thrown away, there is also room for new ideas to emerge from the conversation.

The respondents are residents of the city of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Each of the participants was interviewed for twenty (20) minutes with the conversations recorded with an audio recorder. The group of individuals interviewed is within the age range of 20 – 45 years of age. A total of twenty-five (25) participants were interviewed and their unique data are shown in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1 Interviewee unique data

Position of participants	Number of interviewees	Duration of the interview (minutes)
SM, dismantling	4	20
SM, treatment & packaging	4	20
SM, human resources	1	20
Storage officer	4	20
Officer I	4	20
Officer II	4	20
WEEE collector	4	20

5.4.2 Empirical findings

The organisation selected for this study is one charged with the responsibility to regulate WEEE management in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The Port Harcourt branch of the organisation is responsible for the enforcement of compliance with policies, standards, legislation, and guidelines for water quality, environmental health, and sanitation, including pollution abatement. Furthermore, among the numerous tasks carried out by the organisation also include: the enforcement of compliance with regulations on the importation, exportation, production, distribution, storage, sale, use, handling, and disposal of hazardous chemicals and waste, other than in the oil and gas sector.

5.4.3 Data analysis method

An edited transcription of the semi-structured phone interview was done, and a thematic analysis was also carried out to enable the separation and the performance of a critical discussion on the findings of the study. Thematic analysis also allows for the evaluation and identification of key findings and trends. In Caulfield (2019), thematic analysis is defined as a technique utilised to analyse qualitative data or information used when dealing with text, for example, interview transcripts. The thematic style of data analysis allows the user to thoroughly evaluate the data and pinpoint themes, which are common such as patterns, topics as well as ideas that appear frequently.

A study carried out by Caulfield (2019) and Nowell et al. (2017), opined that thematic analysis can be executed in several approaches, but the commonest, is carried out with the help of six (6) steps as stated below:

- i. Getting familiar with the data available
- ii. Initial code generation
- iii. Themes generation
- iv. Reviewing of themes
- v. Definition of themes as well as naming
- vi. Report writing up.

According to a study carried out by Nowell et al. (2017), thematic analysis is an approach utilised to organise, describe, analyse, and report themes that are present in a data set. Two major approaches are used when executing thematic analysis, they are the deductive approach which requires that many preconceived themes are introduced into the data, and the inductive

approach, which requires that the data is allowed to determine the theme (Caulfield, 2019). In Elliott (2018, p. 2851), code generation is the second stage of the thematic analysis technique, and this is because, “Text data are dense data, and it takes a long time to go through them and make sense of them”.

The term code generation implies that some parts of the text that are usually phrases or sentences are highlighted, then shorthand’s referred to as codes created to describe the content. Each of the phrases takes maybe a unique colour to differentiate it from others. Each of the codes stands for an idea or message conveyed in that particular section of the text, and as one continues to go over the text, the introduction of new codes is feasible. Eventually, the entire data is gathered together in groups that are defined by code. The codes enable one to achieve a more concise overview of the key points and ideas that appear repeatedly in the data (Caulfield, 2019; Poucher *et al.*, 2020; Vaismoradi and Snelgrove, 2019).

Nowell et al. (2017), posit that themes are important concepts, which join, considerable pieces of data, the moment they are identified. They are either deductively generated from earlier research, theory, etc., or inductively generated from the available raw data.

This study adopted the inductive approach of thematic analysis, and the results are given below.

5.4.4 Ethical issues

Each of the participants was handed a written informed consent. It was clearly stated in the study brief that they are free to withdraw at any time if they so wish. Each of the participants gave consent to the recording of the interview, while the contents were anonymized and transcribed. Each of the interviews was stored on an encrypted computer. There were no issues of ethical concerns from the start to the end of the process.

5.4.5 Interview procedure

Each of the participants was contacted via email and sent a copy of the outline on the purpose and requirements of the study. To ensure confidentiality, each of the participants was offered an explanation that their identity, for example, their names would be removed from the transcribed data and also that the idea would not be attributed to any of them in any way. The moment informed consent from the participants was achieved, each of them was also reminded of their right to put an end to the interview at any time. The interviews were conducted with

each of the participants. A semi-structured phone interview was carried out in this study instead of the face-to-face method, because of the prevailing COVID-19 pandemic. The procedure of the phone interview was carried out like that in Szedlak *et al.* (2015), where it was made conducive for each participant to emphasise on issues, they consider more relevant instead of depending on what the researcher deemed relevant.

5.4.6 Coding and theme generation

The data analysis process started with familiarisation, which entails listening to the audio recording of each of the participants. This was followed by an intelligent verbatim method of audio transcription to help with the elimination of irrelevant fillers like “hmm”, “yeah”, “you know”, etc. The coding of the data followed. Codes such as A, B, C, etc., were initially assigned to the participants as shown in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2 Codes assigned to participants

Position of participants	Code
SM, dismantling	A
SM, treatment & packaging	B
SM, human resources	C
Storage officer	D
Officer I	E
Officer II	F
WEEE collector	G

New codes were later generated to help with the capturing of key points that are relevant to the study. Furthermore, the collation of the quotations that relate to each of the themes made it possible for the relevant patterns to emerge.

5.5. Results

A total number of thirty-four (34) quotations was generated from the transcribed semi-structured phone interview, out of which, ten (10) first-order themes were generated, and these are:

- i. Manual dismantling practices adopted by the informal recyclers, and what good practice should be?
- ii. The treatment of cables by informal recyclers to recover copper and the associated risks.
- iii. Dismantling of printed wiring boards by informal recyclers and the processes involved.

- iv. The willingness of informal recyclers to obey government guidelines during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning, etc.
 - v. The enhancement of the activities of informal recyclers via training
 - vi. The willingness of the informal recyclers to get paid for WEEE collection while they quit other WEEE management activities such as treatment, burning, etc.
 - vii. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management and its impact on the reduction of waste and non-value-adding process.
 - viii. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management and its effects on storage space in the site.
 - ix. Application of Just-in-time (JIT) concept in WEEE management and how it relates to waste reduction.
 - x. The application JIT concept in WEEE management and how it relates to the reduction in storage and waiting time.
- a. *Manual dismantling practices adopted by the informal recyclers and what good practice should be?***

This theme refers to the way informal recyclers carry out their manual dismantling activities. Several opinions regarding both bad and good manual dismantling practices were raised. The first issue raised is on what appears to be bad or good practice in the technique adopted by informal recyclers during the manual dismantling of refrigerators. It appears that the manual dismantling done by the informal recyclers is not safe and needs to be replaced by good practice. Some of their responses are:

“The last time I visited one of the recycling sites, the informal recyclers engage in forced opening of the refrigerators, they either smash and/or break the plastic or metal encasing structure, that practice is bad...”, B₁, 22.07.2020.

Some of the participants claimed during their visits to the locations, they observed the informal recycler is less concerned about the use of PPE.

“I did not see them make use of safer devices like a screwdriver to help with controlled opening, they even

crush the inside part without any form of personal protective equipment, PPE...” A1, 20.07, 2020.

“What I observed during one of my visits to one of the locations is that they don’t make use of PPE, instead they just smash and break the refrigerator, without the proper separation and containment of hazardous constituents being released and this practice is bad...” C1, 23.07.2020.

According to some of the participants, the informal recycler exposes themselves as well as the environment to health risks and some try to explain what a good refrigerator manual dismantling should look like.

“As regards the dismantling of refrigerators, I think the informal recyclers need complete orientation and training on the dangers of their technique, as they are exposing themselves as well as the environment to health risk...” B2, 22.07.2020.

“The manual dismantling done by the informal recyclers is bad, a good practice begins with used refrigerators being returned by the public to authorized collection centres and facilities and none is existing, then they should be stored in a proper centre, before any treatment, fridges should be separated based on the type of refrigerants gases they contain...” B3, 22.07.2020.

“I think the informal recyclers should only be allowed to collect WEEE as their style of dismantling refrigerators is not safe, a good practice includes the use of tools fit-for-purpose, PPE, and training to increase their knowledge on WEEE management and the dangers associated with unsafe practice...” B4, 22.07.2020.

b. The treatment of cables by informal recyclers to recover copper and the associated risk.

This theme refers to how copper is recovered from cables by informal recyclers and the associated risk. To some of the participants, the informal recyclers set the cables on fire and extract the copper regardless of any associated health risk.

“On three different occasions, I observed the informal recycler burn off waste cables in open fires that incinerate the outer insulating plastic covering leaving copper as a residue, which is then collected without considering the associated health risk...” A2, 20.07.2020.

“The informal recycler is not concerned about any associated health risk, they just burn the waste cable to extract the copper...” D1, 17.07.2020.

One of them condemned the burning of the insulation part of cables as it releases harmful compounds to the environment.

“Burning of the insulation part of cables, dioxins, and mercury, as well as harmful chlorine, compounds e.g. Polychlorinated Biphenyls are released, these make the practice bad...” A3, 20.07.2020.

Furthermore, to some of the participants, there are better ways to recover copper from the cable as burning is an unsafe practice.

“Stripping and mechanical granulation of cables is a good technique, it is simple, its cost is relatively low, and the insulation part of the cable can be recovered safely instead of burning...” D2, 17.07.2020.

“Instead of using the burning technique, I think the use of chemical treatment is good, besides, heat recovery is another option where the cables can be incinerated in high-

temperature kilns with proper emission control, while the heat is captured for use...” E1, 15.07.2020.

c. Dismantling of printed wiring boards by informal recyclers and the processes involved.

This theme sheds light on the dismantling of printed wiring boards (PWB) by informal recyclers, the bad and good practices adopted in the process. To some of the participants, the techniques adopted to recover some elements from the printed wiring board tend to be hazardous.

“During my last visit to one of the shops owned by an informal recycler, I noticed they adopt the wet chemical leaching technique to extract metals such as gold or silver, the technique is hazardous and should be carried out only by experienced professionals in the laboratory...” F1, 16.07.2020.

“Some of the informal recyclers tend to apply heat to solder in order to de-solder certain components on PWB, they usually carry out this activity under uncontrolled conditions given room for the release of hazardous substances...” F2, 16.07.2020.

Others suggested it should be done in a manner that guarantees the safety of lives and properties and not through any of the primitive techniques adopted.

“I think the parts of the printed wiring boards should be removed by unscrewing and dislodging, goggles and gloves should be worn besides, it is better to store different fractions in their respective containers...” E3, 15.07.2020.

“It is advisable to work on one material at a time, e.g. first remove all Aluminium parts and store them in the Aluminium container, next, remove all the ferrous parts and store them in the relevant container, and so on, this will help to avoid mixing up materials...” G1, 14.07.2020.

d. The willingness of informal recyclers to obey government guidelines during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning, etc.

This theme was fashioned to assess the general opinion of the members of staff of the WEEE regulatory organisation on the willingness of the informal recyclers to obey government guidelines during the discharge of their duties. According to most of the participants, not less than 85% of the informal recyclers are illiterates and hence, it is difficult for them to gain awareness or knowledge on the need to follow government guidelines in the discharge of their duties.

“Majority of the informal recyclers do not have basic education as they cannot read or write in English language, some have English speaking deficiency, this makes learning and development extremely difficult...” C1, 23.07.2020.

“The few among them who have good English speaking and listening skills are willing to obey government’s guidelines on WEEE management...” A1, 20.07.2020

Some of the participants are of the opinion that the government should either stop or discourage the activities of informal recyclers.

“Yes, obeying government’s guidelines on the discharge of their duties is good but this may be difficult to realize as they are mainly illiterates..., maybe informal recycling should be discouraged...” G1, 14.07.2020.

“There is a lot to be done to make the informal recyclers obey government guidelines due to their level of education, I feel that the government should either put an end to the activities of informal recyclers or limit their services to WEEE collection only...” A3, 20.07.2020.

e. The enhancement of the activities of informal recyclers via training

This theme focuses on the response of the participants, on their opinion, regarding the training needs of the informal recyclers. The majority of the participants support the need for training

for informal recyclers but emphasised that illiteracy is the main challenge facing informal recyclers as this hinders development.

“Organising regular training workshops for the informal recyclers will enhance their skill acquisition but there is a high level of illiteracy among them...” G3, 14.07.2020.

“Illiteracy is the main challenge I observed with the informal recyclers the last time I visited their site to distribute fliers, some of them tend to hide for fear of being apprehended due to the illegal nature of their business” F4, 16.07.2020.

f. The willingness of the informal recyclers to get paid for WEEE collection while they quit other WEEE management activities such as treatment, burning, etc.

This theme embraces responses from the participants regarding offering payment to informal recyclers for WEEE collection while an effort is made to stop them from participating in other WEEE management activities. To some of the participants, it will be a welcome development if that can be implemented as the target of the informal recyclers is to earn money, with that approach in place, informal recyclers will concentrate more on WEEE collection to raise cash for themselves. To others, it helps to gradually discourage them from the other WEEE management activities such as dismantling, treatment, burning, etc.

“We have had several conversations with the informal recyclers, they engage in the recycling business to enable them to earn a living and will be happy if they can get money from the government or the private individuals for WEEE collection...” C1, 23.07.2020.

“They actually find it easy to gather WEEE, as such if the government can prepare to pay them for WEEE collection and in the process stop them from other activities like dismantling, treatment, etc., it will be a step in the right direction...” E4, 15.07.2020.

“...money is the target in the business, the moment they start getting paid for WEEE collection, they will concentrate more on that aspect, and gradually their concentration on the other WEEE management activities will depreciate...” F4, 16.07.2020.

g. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management and its impact on the reduction of waste and non-value-adding process.

This theme focuses on the lean concept, its implementation, and its effectiveness. An effort was made to offer some explanations to the participants on the meaning of the term lean. In Deranek et al. (Deranek, Chopra and Mosher, 2017), lean implies the development of a value stream that enables the elimination of all waste, including time, and facilitates a level schedule. In this context, waste is referred to as any activity that does not add value but becomes integral to the production. To most of the participants, the concept is new, and to some of them who claim they have heard about the concept before, seem not to understand the application of the concept to waste management.

“...Since the concept has to do with the elimination of waste, that’s fine, I am sure, this will help to cut down the amount of WEEE in circulation...” A4, 20.07.2020.

“I read online about this concept recently but yet to understand its application, but I think it is beginning to make sense to me now...” D2, 17.07.2020.

“One of the challenges we experience at WEEE dumpsites is that it occupies space that normally would have been put to good use...” D3, 17.07.2020.

h. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management and its effects on storage space in the site.

This theme focuses on the relationship between effective lean implementation on WEEE management and storage space on the site. Most of the participants attempted to think outside the box and came up with ideas on how the application of lean can facilitate the reduction in storage space.

“...from all I have gathered from you, with this concept, WEEE collection can be carried out on demand, it, therefore, means, any available space for storage can be put to good use...” D1, 17.07.2020.

“If more WEEE can be collected when there is a need, it means more will be collected if the available ones are processed and there is space for new intakes, this will go a long way to reduce the amount of space used for storage...” D2, 17.07.2020.

i. Application of Just-in-time (JIT) concept in WEEE management and how it relates to waste reduction.

This theme entails the application of the just-in-time concept and how it results in waste reduction. The participants feel with the timely processing of WEEE materials, there will certainly be a reduction in waste.

“WEEE collection, dismantling, etc carried out in a timely manner, implies a timely waste reduction...” B3, 22.07.2020.

“If collected WEEE materials are processed in a timely manner, it will lead to waste reduction...” F2, 16.07.2020.

j. The application JIT concept in WEEE management and how it relates to the reduction in storage and waiting time.

This theme embraces the participants’ opinions on the application of the JIT concept in WEEE management and its impact on the reduction in storage and waiting time. The majority of the participants believe it facilitates the reduction in storage and waiting times.

“Since this concept involves the on-time supply of WEEE for example, at the collection point when in demand, the waiting time of the workers as well as the duration at which they are kept or stored before demanded, also reduces...” A1, 20.07.2020.

“With timely response to WEEE management activities, idleness at the site is drastically reduced and consequently waiting time also reduces...” B2, 22.07.2020.

Quote “B₁, 22.07.2020” talks about the primitive dismantling techniques adopted by informal recyclers. Quote “A₁, 20.07, 2020” talks about the lack of concern as regards the use of PPE during the dismantling of WEEE. Quote “C₁, 23.07.2020” talks about the extent to which informal recyclers neglect the use of PPE while carrying out WEEE dismantling. Quote “B₂, 22.07.2020” emphasizes the need for informal recyclers to be offered proper orientation and training on the health risks associated with their technique of dismantling WEEE. The quote “B₃, 22.07.2020” condemns the manual dismantling carried out by informal recyclers and offers some of the best practices that can be adopted for refrigerator dismantling. Quote “B₄, 22.07.2020” emphasised the activities of informal recyclers should be limited to WEEE collection only as their dismantling method creates room for several health risks. All the quotes above align with and support the theme “Manual dismantling practices adopted by the informal recyclers and what good practice should be?”

As regards the theme, “The treatment of cables by informal recyclers to recover copper and the associated risk”. Quote “A₂, 20.07.2020” talks about the unhealthy approaches adopted by informal recyclers for the treatment of cables in order to recover copper regardless of the associated health risks. Quote “D₁, 17.07.2020” talks about the careless attitude of informal recyclers about the health risks associated with the burning of cable to extract copper. Quote “A₃, 20.07.2020” condemns the burning of the insulation part of cables, dioxins, and mercury, as well as harmful chlorine compounds, resulting in the release of Polychlorinated Biphenyls. Quote “D₂, 17.07.2020” suggested the adoption of stripping and mechanical granulation of cables as it is a good technique to remove the insulation part of cables. “Quote E₁, 15.07.2020” suggested the use of chemical treatment as well as heat recovery as methods to adopt instead of burning. The theme is supported by numerous quotes. This is because they are all aligned to the theme.

Quote “F₁, 16.07.2020” observes that informal recyclers now adopt chemical leaching techniques to extract metals like Silver and Gold, even when they lack the appropriate knowledge of the method. Quote “F₂, 16.07.2020,” noticed that some recyclers adopt solder to de-solder certain components on PWB, under an uncontrolled condition. In the

process, they expose themselves and the environment to harmful substances. Quote “E3, 15.07.2020” proposed that dislodging and unscrewing should be adopted for the removal of some parts of the printed wiring boards. Conversely, gloves and goggles should be worn while carrying out the task. Quote G1, 14.07.2020, suggested that the dismantling of printed wiring boards should be carried out in a way the task is performed on one material at a time. For instance, all the Aluminium materials can be removed first and carefully stored in a container. After which one can commence the dismantling of the ferrous parts. All the quotes above aligned with the theme, “Dismantling of printed wiring boards by informal recyclers and the processes involved”.

All the quotes under each of the themes aligned with the theme under which they are grouped.

Each of the quotes under each theme points out specific words or phrases that clearly address the theme. The quotes add to the existing knowledge base and also shed light on specific aspects of the theme that are important to the study objectives. These quotes help to strengthen the reliability and validity of the thematic analysis carried out. Furthermore, the quotes help to provide answers to the study research questions, as well as research objectives.

Furthermore, three (3) second-order themes were generated from the ten (10) first-order themes to facilitate effective WEEE management. The three (3) second-order themes are:

- i. Safety enhancement during the performance of WEEE management activities
- ii. Partnership for effective WEEE management
- iii. Strategies to enhance effective WEEE management.

The diagram of effective WEEE management and the associated themes is shown in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.3 Effective WEEE management and associated themes

5.6 Discussion

The focus of this study is to assess the activities of the informal recyclers, the knowledge of the WEEE regulatory body on the activities of the recyclers in MTN phone village in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and as well as their knowledge of the Just-in-time concept, as an applicable lean-approach. The interview was conducted to help with the understanding of the exact situation and besides, it is of importance to ascertain if there are any themes or patterns that are common in the experiences of the participants as emphasised in a study by (Vaismoradi and Snelgrove, 2019). The findings show that the manual dismantling of WEEE carried out by the informal recyclers in the study location is not safe. It is carried out without the use of personal protective equipment. Conversely, because of unsafe dismantling procedures adopted, they tend to expose themselves as well as the environment to health-related risks. For an effective and safe manual dismantling system to be in place, there is a need to adopt best practices in the management of WEEE (Lydall, Nyanjowa and James, 2017).

In Baldé et al. (2017), dismantling activities performed without adequate facilities, means, and skilled individuals usually create room for additional hazards to people and the environment. Adoption of best practices in manual dismantling is highly encouraged as a lot of work-related injuries are associated with it (Fischer *et al.*, 2020). WEEE material that requires dismantling

must first be made non-hazardous. This implies the removal of every hazardous component and for laptops and computers, data destruction has to be carried out with the help of designated equipment before dismantling (Lydall, Nyanjowa and James, 2017).

A lot of the participants are ignorant of the risk associated with improper burning of WEEE. Among the participants are also those who emphasised that there are better ways to recover copper from cable and that burning are unsafe. According to Lenz et al. (2019), the burning of the insulating part of waste cables using an open fire to extract copper is the worst technique to adopt. The burning of cables in the open air to extract copper has a serious effect on the informal recyclers' health as it produces hydrochloric acid, and a lot of other materials, which give rise to acute respiratory challenges (Jain, 2017).

It was also gathered from the interview that it is not going to be easy to train the informal recyclers on best practices or make them go into partnership with the government on WEEE management as they are mostly illiterates. Some of the participants are of the opinion that the government needs to either stop the activities of informal recyclers or discourage them. This is because their level of illiteracy hinders WEEE management knowledge acquisition and government partnership. Furthermore, it was made clear from the interview conversation that the main target of the informal recycler is to raise money for themselves. Any effort made by the government or private individuals to pay them money for WEEE collection is a step in the right direction. This is because, it has the potential to make them concentrate more on WEEE collection while they gradually get discouraged from the other activities that form part of WEEE management like treatment, recycling, burning, etc.

At the beginning of the conversation with most of the participants, the application of the Just-in-time concept, an aspect of lean principles appeared new but as the conversation continued, several of them tried to think outside the box and came up with their opinion on the subject. To some of them, the application of the lean concept facilitates the reduction in storage space. It was evident from the findings that timely processing of WEEE materials using the JIT approach will result in a reduction in waste, storage, and waiting times. Manzouri et al. (2014), the lean concept has the potential to reduce waste and cost. From the interview conversation, Idleness among the WEEE workers is one of the issues the just-in-time approach stands to cater for.

Cerra (2019), less space is required with the application of the Just-in-time concept as there is quicker processing of the collected WEEE hence, a place of storage or warehouse is not

required. Also, faster processing of WEEE gathered prevents the storage of already collected WEEE, hence reducing waste. According to Wu, Dong, and Wang. (2019), safety hazards that are hidden as well as idleness on the part of workers and devices are eliminated.

5.7 A Comprehensive Criticism of the Solution Proposed

Regarding the feasibility, although recovering WEEE for appropriate treatment, processing, sorting, and recycling by government-approved bodies seems promising on paper, the feasibility of this strategy must be carefully considered (Nnorom and Odeyingbo, 2020). Government agencies may encounter obstacles such as a lack of infrastructure, financing, and skilled staff when dealing with large-scale WEEE recovery and management (Ibitz, 2020). Putting in place a program of such nature requires effective logistics for processing WEEE, collecting, and transporting (Magalini, Khetriwal and Kyriakopoulou, 2019). In areas with poor infrastructure, particularly in informal settlements such as Rumukurushi, providing seamless logistics can be a major difficulty.

Involving informal recyclers, residents, as well as the public in WEEE recovery activities is essential for success (Okwu *et al.*, 2022). However, widespread involvement may be difficult to achieve due to issues like skepticism, lack of awareness, and unwillingness to dispose of electronic waste in the absence of incentives or education regarding the need for safe disposal (Sharma *et al.*, 2024). Applying JIT lean management approaches in the context of WEEE management necessitates adaptation to local infrastructural and socioeconomic realities (Walden, 2021). The informal recycling ecosystem in Rumukurushi may not be compatible with JIT principles. This is because, according to Louhelainen (2021) it prioritises efficiency, timely processing and minimal inventory.

JIT principles need effective resource use, streamlined processes, and well-trained personnel. It is important to review the willingness of current stakeholders, such as residents, informal recyclers, government agencies, to embrace and continue using JIT techniques (Kenyon, 2022). While JIT concepts seek to decrease waste and increase efficiency, its implementation should consider potential social and environmental consequences (Khan *et al.*, 2020). For example, rapid changes in collection or process techniques may have an impact on informal recyclers employment patterns or cause unanticipated environmental problems if not properly handled (Pegels *et al.*, 2023). Implementing JIT principles may need initial

investments in technology, infrastructure, and training. These investments' cost-effectiveness and long-term sustainability must be evaluated, particularly in resource-constrained contexts (Kategaya, 2021).

5.8 Generalizability of the Findings Expansion and Justification

The generalizability of the findings from the study on reducing informal recyclers' activities in MTN Phone Village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, can be expanded and justified in several ways.

Several urban areas in underdeveloped nations have issues with informal electronic waste recycling (WEEE) (Moyen Massa and Archodoulaki, 2023). The findings on the combination of two approaches, i.e. recovery by government-approved entities and the application of JIT lean management principles may be relevant to other areas with identical informal recycling ecosystems.

The engagement of government-approved agencies in WEEE recovery and management is a method that may be applied across different locations. Governments have an important role in regulating waste management procedures, and adopting this strategy in other sectors can enhance the formal handling of WEEE (Gollakota, Gautam and Shu, 2020).

JIT concepts may be used in any geographical area. These principles emphasize timely process, efficiency, and waste reduction, all of which are global concepts that apply to a wide range of companies and contexts other than electronic waste management (Louhelainen, 2021).

The study emphasizes the necessity of public involvement and awareness in effective waste disposal approaches. This part of the findings can be applied to other areas where education and involvement are important in establishing sustainable waste management practices (David, John and Hussain, 2020).

Many developing countries have resource, logistical, and infrastructural constraints (Quader and Abdullah, 2020). As a result, the research's insights on how to solve these obstacles can be generalized and applied to other areas, dealing with similar WEEE management issues.

Considering the fact that social and environmental implications of waste management initiatives are a wide concept that is applicable internationally (Forti *et al.*, 2020). The study's

emphasis on combining environmental goals with social issues creates a framework that may be generalised to a variety of cultural and economic contexts.

Examining the cost-effectiveness of waste management as well as the long-term sustainability solutions is an important feature that applies to each place (Mohanty *et al.*, 2022). The study's cost analysis and sustainability components can influence decision-making processes in a variety of situations.

The study's findings have generalizability potential since they are relevant to typical waste management problems. This includes the application of JIT principles, the adoption of government agencies, and considerations to take into account public engagement and the focus on social and environmental implications.

5.9 Conclusions

The research work reviewed past works of literature on WEEE management in an attempt to reduce the activities of informal recycling in Port Harcourt City in Nigeria. A new WEEE management concept for Port Harcourt city is being developed, which ensures the collection of WEEE from residents, informal recyclers, and the remaining part of the public coupled with the application of the just-in-time (JIT) management concept. In this study, the informal recycler is not involved with WEEE treatment, dismantling, refining, and disposal, but still gains revenue from the process. The study shows that providing a financial inducement to the informal recyclers by paying them for WEEE gatherings has the potential to make them partner with government agencies for a collective and effective WEEE management system. Furthermore, reducing the level of participation of informal recyclers in the aspect of WEEE management that requires experienced hands implies the reduction of the challenges associated with their involvement. WEEE management is now the sole responsibility of the government-approved offices and trained personnel, and this offers safety, efficiency, and increased process. The outcome of this study will help to reduce the activities of informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and other cities and nations faced with similar challenges. With this development, informal recyclers will be allowed to collect WEEE only as they will not be allowed to perform other WEEE recycling activities. This will help to revolutionise the WEEE management system in the city of Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and any other location that adopts the system.

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Conclusions, contributions, and recommendations

This Ph.D thesis provides research addressing the behavioural modification in a group of informal recyclers at the MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria, to lessen their exposure to potentially dangerous compounds. The strategy can be used in other areas that deal with comparable problems. All that is needed to stop environmental pollution and health issues in the chosen research location and other areas affected by comparable issues is to address the difficulties associated with informal WEEE management brought on by the unchecked activities of informal recyclers. The residents of the location are exposed to health challenges and other environmental problems associated with informal WEEE management. To tackle these challenges, this research became a necessity.

6.1 General conclusions

Informal WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment) management, which implies informal handling, processing, and disposal of electronic waste by individuals or small enterprises without the necessary authority or regulation is a known problem globally. Lead, mercury, and cadmium, among other dangerous substances, can be released when electronic waste is improperly handled and disposed of, endangering both the environment and human health. Informal WEEE management makes it impossible to track the quantity and destination of e-waste, resulting in lack of transparency in the management of electronic waste. Small-scale businesses that engage in informal WEEE management frequently lack the required tools and facilities needed to do it safely. Informal WEEE management can lead to the loss of valuable materials like copper and gold. All of which can be recovered through the adoption of formal WEEE handling system. It is challenging to enforce correct disposal standards and ensure that employees are treated properly and compensated sufficiently. This is because informal WEEE management frequently occurs outside of legal and regulatory systems.

This Ph.D thesis intends to revolutionise the WEEE management system in the selected location and other areas faced with similar challenges.

The backdrop and context of the thesis are introduced in chapter one, along with the research questions, goals, and methodology (which includes the research paradigm, approach, data

collection technique, and data analysis method used in the study). The contributions of the thesis, the outline of the thesis structure, the confidentiality and ethical issues observed during the study, and ultimately the list of publications are all discussed in this section of the thesis.

An overview of pertinent literature and research in the area of informal WEEE management is provided in Chapter 2. This portion of the thesis reviews earlier works of literature on various facets of WEEE management. The methodology of the literature review, WEEE category, hazardous components in WEEE, a review of previous literary works, the status of WEEE in Nigeria, WEEE practice with health impacts, typical activities and problems, and trends in waste electrical and electronic equipment. Other aspects also covered under the overview of relevant works of literature are the need to recycle WEEE or dispose of WEEE, how to dispose of WEEE, recycling methods in Nigeria, factors that affect the WEEE management system in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria and WEEE management system proposed for MTN phone village, Rumukurushi in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. This segment of the study also covered the research gaps and challenges in the existing literature.

Chapter 3 addresses the effects of informal recycling in the mobile telephone network phone village at Rumukurushi, in Port Harcourt' (where it is estimated that roughly 30 informal recyclers operate). The informal recyclers' degree of education, understanding of health and safety issues, desire to follow governmental directives, and familiarity with the proper disposal of old electrical and electronic equipment were investigated. Other areas covered in this section of the thesis include the research design and approach, data collection and analysis of the questionnaires administered to the participants, ethical considerations, and the outcome of the survey questionnaires offered to the participants.

Chapter 4 addresses the necessity to remove or limit the involvement of recyclers in the informal sector. The focus is to lower the health hazards connected with the management of WEEE in Rumukurushi, in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. This applies to similar situations in other cities. Other areas covered are details of the newly introduced concept for the management of WEEE by informal recyclers, which limits their activities or services to WEEE collection only. Tables, graphs, and figures used to illustrate the outcome of the questionnaires administered to participants are covered in this segment of the thesis. Also included is the interpretation and discussion of findings.

In order to fully address the issues related to informal WEEE management mode of operation, Chapter 5 embraces the efforts made to minimise the operations of informal recyclers (in the chosen region and other locations afflicted by similar concerns). The research's design, approach, data collection technique, and analysis method used while conducting semi-structured phone interviews are also addressed in this part. This section also examined the two main concepts used to address the problems caused by informal recycling. Also treated are the interpretation, and discussion of the findings of the outcome of the semi-structured phone interviews carried out using the thematic analysis method.

Chapter 6 covers the general conclusion, the study's major contributions, and recommendations.

6.2 Contributions of the Thesis

- It will enhance the safe and sustainable disposal of hazardous materials in the city of Port Harcourt and cities in other nations faced with similar challenges.
- Valuable materials or precious metals like Gold, Copper, etc., will be efficiently recovered for reuse and recycling.
- The study will help to revolutionise the WEEE management system.
- It will increase the process, efficiency, and safety.
- It leads to a reduction in the waiting time of workers and WEEE storage space.
- The study adds to the existing knowledge in the area of specialisation.
- It will enhance the efficient sorting of hazardous materials from non-hazardous materials after dismantling, a practice that is carried out improperly.
- It will help to check and reduce the activities of informal WEEE recyclers since they lack the required skills and experience for proper WEEE treatment, processing, and disposal.
- With this system in place, effective recovery, reduction, reuse, repurposing, and recycling of WEEE is possible.
- It will create job opportunities.
- It will offer the government an opportunity to manage WEEE treatment, processing, and disposal in the city of Port Harcourt and other locations faced with the same challenge.

- It will help to reduce other risks associated with informal WEEE processing, treatment, and disposal in the city of Port Harcourt and other locations faced with the same challenge.
- It will help to create awareness of the need for WEEE to be handled by properly trained and experienced personnel.

6.2.1 How the research offers novel contributions, including theoretical insights, practical implications, and, where relevant, potential policy implications

- This study has offered novel contributions, including theoretical insights, practical implications, and, where relevant, potential policy implications in several ways as given below
- The study reviewed several works of literature in the field of study and in the process identified a research gap. This research gap serves as an opportunity for the study to make a novel contribution.
- This study adopted the use of a mixed research approach and applied a combination of two different concepts to tackle the challenges associated with informal recycling. All of which help to offer unique insights and strengthen the novelty of the study.
- The study data was analysed rigorously to create new discoveries or knowledge. The study tried to look for relationships, patterns, and trends that have not been documented previously. All of which helps to uncover new insights.
- The study translated the research outcome into actionable strategies and recommendations for real-world applications.
- The findings of the study were published in reputable Journals that are relevant to the field.

6.3 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

Some of the limitations and suggestions for future research that can be considered include:

- The generalizability of findings may be limited due to a small sample size or a lack of representativeness. For future research, larger-scale studies with representative and diverse samples should be carried out improve to the external validity of the findings.
- Cross-sectional designs can present limitations in terms of establishing causal relationships or capturing temporal changes over time. For future research,

experimental or longitudinal designs should be carried out to better investigate temporal dynamics and causal relationships more effectively.

- Limited examination of contextual elements (for example, environmental, cultural, and economic) may limit the findings' application in a variety of scenarios. For future research, comparative studies should be done across different settings to investigate how outcomes and interventions are influenced by contextual factors
- The application of simplistic or incorrect methods for data analysis may result in misunderstanding or oversimplification of results. For future research, advanced qualitative or statistical analysis methods should be adopted and tailored to the complexity of the data and research questions.
- Publication bias, in which significant and positive findings are more inclined to be published, could skew the overall understanding of the research topic. For future research, publication bias should be addressed by considering gray literature, unpublished studies, or carrying out meta-analysis to offer a more balanced account of the evidence.
- Limitation: Inadequate focus on ethical considerations like privacy protection, informed consent as well as potential harm to participants may raise ethical concerns. For future research, ethical guidelines should be strictly adhered to and ethical considerations in publications and research protocols should be transparently reported.
- The absence of a solid conceptual model or theoretical framework may restrict the scope of analysis and interpretation of results. For future research, a theoretical framework should be developed based on theoretical insights and empirical findings to help guide future practice and research.
- The limited assessment of the sustainability of intervention or long-term outcomes may make it difficult to assess the effectiveness of intervention over time. For future research, longitudinal studies or long-term follow-ups should be done to assess outcomes of interventions and sustained impact.
- Lack of engagement with interdisciplinary points of view or collaboration with stakeholders from many sectors may result in the loss of valuable ideas or solutions. For future research: early engagement of stakeholders and promoting interdisciplinary collaboration in the research process should be done to improve the effect of research findings, applicability, and relevance.

6.4 Recommendations

Reducing informal WEEE management necessitates a multifaceted strategy that includes stakeholder participation, government regulation, and public involvement. Together, we can develop a more ecologically conscious and long-term strategy for handling WEEE.

Below are some recommendations for reducing informal WEEE management:

- To guarantee that all WEEE is handled in an environmentally friendly way, the government has to set and enforce rules. The entire WEEE lifecycle, including collection, transportation, storage, treatment, and disposal, has to be covered by regulations.
- Governments, NGOs, and other stakeholders should raise awareness about the dangers of improper WEEE management as well as the significance of proper WEEE recycling and disposal. Public awareness efforts should target informal recyclers as well as industry experts and the public.
- The formalisation of the WEEE recycling sector should be encouraged by governments and other stakeholders. This might entail offering incentives for informal recyclers to join formal recycling networks or providing training and support to help them comply with regulations.
- Governments and other stakeholders should invest in enhancing WEEE collection techniques. This can entail setting up drop-off locations, developing better transportation systems, or offering incentives for consumers to return their electronic waste.
- Manufacturers should be encouraged to design items that are more readily recyclable, repairable, and reusable. This might lessen the initial quantity of WEEE produced and make it simpler to handle and dispose of when it does reach the end of its useful life.

Appendix A

SCHOOL OF COMPUTING, ENGINEERING AND PHYSICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

The designed questionnaire is for the sole purpose of data collection, framework development for WEEE recovery from the public and for informal recyclers integration in WEEE sustainable management.

PART A: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Please for questions 1 to 3, tick the appropriate box that best describes your status.

1 Gender?

Male Female Cannot say

2 How old are you?

Under 20 21-25 26-35 35-40 41-50 51 and above

3 Educational level

Graduate high school primary others

4 What is your role in the recycling process?

Supervisor WEEE picker buy and sell WEEE scrap WEEE dismantler burn residue other

5. How long are you into the business of WEEE management?

Less than 1 year 1 – 2 years 2 – 3 years 3 – 4 years more than 4 years

6. In your opinion, what do you think is the main reason individuals engage in WEEE recycling?

Lack of job availability Zero tax payment Extra income generation Others

Please, rate the following statement on a scale of 1 to 25, the extent of agreement or disagreement by ticking the appropriate box as it best describes your opinion	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
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on waste electrical electronics equipment (WEEE) recycling process.					
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PART B: WEEE AWARENESS AND BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS A GOOD SUSTAINABLE PRACTICE

Case description	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
7. The waste electrical & electronic equipment (WEEE) is frequently dismantled and disposed of on the site?					
8. Frequent dismantling and disposal of fridge and its components on the site.					
9. Washing machines are frequently dismantled and disposed on the site					
10. Personal computers are frequently dismantled and disposed on the site					
11. Laptops are frequently dismantled and disposed on the site					
12. Television set is frequently dismantled and disposed on the site					
13. Electrical cables are frequently disposed or burnt on the site					
14. Electronic circuits board containing poisonous elements are disposed and burnt in the site					
15. Mobile phones are frequently dismantled and disposed on the site					
16. The WEEE generated is delivered to the site by the informal recyclers					
17. The WEEE generated is delivered to the site by other parties					
18. The majority of the WEEE stream gathered is generated within Nigeria e.g., Port Harcourt					
19 The majority of the WEEE stream gathered is imported from other countries					
20. WEEE management on-site means throwing WEEE into Open dump					
21. WEEE management on-site means burning WEEE					
22. WEEE management on-site means keeping WEEE in storerooms					

23. WEEE management on-site means sorting, dismantling, processing, treatment and recovering of valuable elements before disposal of the unwanted parts					
24. WEEE management on-site means dumping WEEE in water					
25. WEEE management on-site means dumping WEEE on the road path					
26. The recovered and useful components are sold to middlemen					
27. The recovered and useful components are sold to local manufacturing companies					
28. The recovered and useful components are sold to foreign manufacturing companies					

PART C: WASTE ELECTRICAL & ELECTRONIC EQUIPMENT HEALTH, SAFETY AND ENVIRONMENT ISSUES					
Case description	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
29. Personal safety is enhanced by applying control measures and wearing personal protective equipment (PPE) during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
30. The protection of individuals around the WEEE dumping site is enhanced by applying control measures and best management practices during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
31. The environmental pollution is reduced by applying control measures and best management practices during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
32. Work efficiency is enhanced by applying best management practices during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
33. Recyclers wear PPE (such as coverall, hand gloves, goggles, earplug) for enhanced safety during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
34. The use of PPE is a good practice					
Possible injuries sustained by WEEE recyclers					
35. Workers sustained injuries during the WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					

36. Hand and leg injuries and backache are sustained during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
37. Recyclers are willing to obey government guidelines during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning etc.					
38. Good training would help WEEE recyclers do their job safely					
39. WEEE recyclers are willing to work with government agencies					

PART D: GOVERNMENT REGULATORY AGENCY

Case description	Strongly agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
40. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to implement a WEEE management plan					
41. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to safeguard the environment against unregulated dumping of WEEE					
42. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to encourage WEEE management policies, regulation, and strategies					
43. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to inform the public on penalties indulging in unregulated WEEE management methods					
44. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to encourage reuse, reduce, recover and recycle to lessen WEEE generation					
45. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to educate the public on the best WEEE management method					
46. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to create a WEEE management plan for stakeholders					

47. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to keep a documented record of WEEE volume generated weekly, monthly or quarterly					
48. Do your organisation have the required resources and experienced personnel to put recovery policy for WEEE at the end of useful life					
49. In your opinion, is the implementation strategies on WEEE management suitable?					
50. Lack of technologies and essential equipment to manage WEEE generation is one of the factors limiting the implementation process of WEEE management strategies					
51. Lack of continuity of viable policies due to changing political and leadership structure is one of the factors limiting the implementation process of WEEE management strategies					
52. Inadequate finance is one of the factors limiting the implementation process of WEEE management strategies					
53. Lack of adequate manpower (Personnel) is one of the factors limiting the implementation process of WEEE management strategies					
Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management					
54. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management results in the eradication of all forms of waste and non-value adding processes					
55. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management enhances levelling to reduce waste during production					
56. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management reduces start-up time/changeover					
57. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management reduces storage space in the site					
58. Lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management helps to develop effective leadership					
The advantages of the Just-in-time (JIT) concept in process management					
59. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is smaller investments					
60. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is waste reduction					
61. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is smooth production flow					

62. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is pulled method of production					
63. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is equipment maintenance					
64. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is less space needed					
65. One of the advantages of the JIT concept in process management is the reduction in storage and waiting time					

Thank you for your time

Appendix B

Interview questions

- i. What do you understand by waste electrical and electronic equipment, WEEE management?
- ii. What is your opinion about the manual dismantling practices adopted by informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and what good practice should be?
- iii. What is your viewpoint with respect to the treatment of cables by informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria to recover copper and the associated risk?
- iv. What is your idea on the dismantling of printed wiring boards by informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria and the processes involved?
- v. What is your opinion regarding the willingness of informal recyclers to obey government guidelines during WEEE handling, dismantling, treatment, burning, etc?
- vi. What is your view as regards the enhancement of the activities of informal recyclers in in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria via training?
- vii. What do you have to say regarding the willingness of the informal recyclers to get paid for WEEE collection while they quit other WEEE management activities such as treatment, burning, etc?
- viii. What do you think about lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management and its impact on the reduction of waste and non-value-adding process?
- ix. What is your opinion with respect to lean implementation effectiveness in WEEE management and its effects on storage space in the site?
- x. What is your viewpoint regarding the application of Just-in-time (JIT) concept in WEEE management in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, and how it relates to waste reduction?
- xi. What do you have to say about the application JIT concept in WEEE management and how it relates to the reduction in storage and waiting time?

- xii. What do know about the operation of the informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, with respect to the use of personal protective equipment, PPE.
- xiii. What is your opinion about the level of awareness of the informal recyclers in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, with respect to the challenges associated with their WEEE management practice?
- xiv. What method or approach do you suggest should be adopted to tackle the challenges associated with informal recycling in MTN phone village, Rumukurushi, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.